

Societal & Political Engagement
of Young People in Environmental Issues

D5.3: Final Evaluation of STEP Pilots

WP5 – Pilot Operation and Evaluation

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1 *Executive summary*

This Final Evaluation Deliverable reports on the use of the STEP platform by the pilot partners in carrying out e-Participation activities with Young People across the various European municipalities and regions involved in the project.

The current deliverable presents the case for each STEP pilot, the experience gained and the lessons learnt by each pilot partner. As part of the evaluation activities we conducted a number of qualitative interviews with relevant actors in the STEP pilots. Additionally we conducted two questionnaires, one with Public Officers and a second with Young People in the pilot countries. The results of the evaluation are discussed in relation to a number of core objectives and targets defined originally for the STEP project. The data analysis conducted for this evaluation show positive results for STEP in the achievement of the project objectives. STEP is indeed seen by both Young People and Policy Makers as a useful platform for the conduction of e-Participation on environmental issues and the actors generally said they would use the platform again and would suggest its use to their respective peers. Overall the evaluation has also shown that some improvements may still be required for fine tuning the usability of the platform. Results have shown further that the mistrust of Young People toward policy makers still persist, however STEP is seen as a platform which can help in the conduction of participatory policy making in the area of environmental issues.

The deliverable is organized as follows: we begin with a general presentation of the project success indicators and objectives, a detailed presentation of each STEP pilot and an initial breakdown of the data collection for the evaluation; this is followed by an overview for each pilot of the results achieved and some of the problems identified directly by the pilots; then the qualitative data is presented, starting with the Public Officers/Policy Makers and then turning to Young People; then there is the presentation of the analysis of the questionnaires again following the order of Public Officers/Policy Makers and then turning to Young People; we then present an overall SWOT analysis for STEP before concluding the deliverable.

2 Introduction

This deliverable reports on the results of the final evaluation process for the STEP platform, presents the story of each STEP pilot and highlights the key elements. By combining methodologies from previous research of both online and traditional public participation projects and elements from different evaluation frameworks (but drawing heavily from Loukis, 2012), the STEP project has proposed the following methodology for evaluating the Pilot e-Participation process. The methodology is based on three evaluation perspectives: Process (PRO), system (SYS) and outcomes (OUT); each includes a number of evaluation criteria.

- Process (PRO) aims to evaluate the process that has been followed in the project (based on the efficiency evaluation)
- System (SYS) aims to evaluate the ICT system used in the project (based on the ease of use concept and the technical evaluation concept)
- Outcome (OUT) perspective aims to evaluate the outcomes from a political viewpoint of the project (based on the effectiveness evaluation and the usefulness concept of the TAM)

See Loukis (2012)¹ for more in depth discussion of the various criteria.

The evaluation process has also been mapped onto the STEP measurable project objectives, whilst considering the various methodologies described in the literature. A combination of qualitative and quantitative techniques have been used to evaluate the user experience with the STEP platform itself and with the interaction with the policy makers/public officers from the local municipalities / regions involved in the Pilots. We deployed a self-completion online questionnaire whose objective was to evaluate the achievement of the high level project goals such as the increase of trust and interest of Young People in political activities or how the project helps public authorities to open their decision-making process to citizens. The format included both rating scale questions (Likert) and open prompt questions allowing both a quantitative and qualitative assessment of participant responses from the user perspective (all users, ie. both Young People and policy makers/ public officers). This has provided information on the achievement of the project goals considering national specificities, user perceptions and future use of the platform. Our main rationale was to ensure that we successfully evaluate the STEP project Success Indicators (shown in Tables 1 and 2 below) and for those that require user input, to ask clear Likert scale questions that will produce quantitative results, as well as the inclusion of some more in-depth, open-ended questions. Qualitative data was also gained by conducting in-depth interviews with a sample of end-users² (both Young People and Public Officers/Policy Makers).

The deliverable is organized as follows: we begin with a general presentation of the project success indicators and objectives, a detailed presentation of each STEP pilot and an initial breakdown of the data collection for the evaluation; this is followed by an overview for each pilot of the results achieved and some of the problems identified directly by the pilots; then the qualitative data is presented by starting with the Public Officers/Policy Makers and then turning to Young People; then there is the presentation of the analysis of the questionnaires again following the order of Public Officers/Policy Makers and then turning to Young People; we then present an overall SWOT analysis for STEP before concluding the deliverable.

¹ Loukis, E. (2012). Evaluating eParticipation Projects and Lessons Learnt. In *Empowering open and collaborative governance* (pp. 95-115). Springer Berlin Heidelberg.

² Qualitative interviews cover in this evaluation the aspects of the ABCD approach described in early deliverables, which encountered some implementation limitations. Different aspects of the ABCD approach were used for D5.2.

3 Success Indicators and initial breakdown of data

In this section we present the indicators associated with the project objectives and an initial mapping of the data collected. We present the mapping of questions for the questionnaire against the project objectives. The qualitative interview questions are instead attached in the appendix of this deliverable. For full discussion about these indicators and for full discussion of the evaluation methodology it is possible to consider the Deliverable 5.1 and 5.2 of STEP. Table 1 includes the success indicators for the project. Table 5 presents the project objectives, indicators and the targets defined for the submission of the original STEP proposal. Table 6 presents those objectives that are evaluated, in particular through the questionnaires conducted with Young People and Policy Makers/Public Officers. These same objectives have also been evaluated with qualitative data.

Table 1 Success indicators measured during the Evaluation process

Indicator of success	Measurement technique	Target achieved until 20 th November 2017	Target value ³
Demonstration, Validation and Usability			
Number of Young People involved in pilot	Demonstration in 4 pilot countries	Italy: 1.583 Spain: 1.466 (Valdemoro 206; MdV 1.260) Greece: 1.009 (RoC 883, Thessaloniki 126) Turkey: 3.146 Other countries from EU pilot: TOTAL: 7.475	Italy: 1.500 Spain: 1.200 Greece: 3.000 Turkey: 3.500 TOTAL: 8.200
Number of policy makers involved in pilot	Demonstration in 4 pilot countries	Italy: 20 Spain: 20 (Valdemoro 12, MdV: 8) Greece: 26 (ROC 20, Thessaloniki:6) Turkey: 25 TOTAL: 91	Italy: 20 Spain: 20 Greece: 20 Turkey: 25 TOTAL: 85
Number of decision-making procedures piloted through STEP	Demonstration in 4 pilot countries	Italy: 7 Spain: 19 (Vald:5, MDV:14) Greece: 48 (RoC: 46; Thessaloniki: 2) Turkey: 14 TOTAL: 88	Italy: 15 Spain: 15 Greece: 15 Turkey: 20 TOTAL: 65
Number of downloads of STEP app	Demonstration in 4 pilot countries	Italy: 314 Spain: 216 Greece: 136 Turkey: 1.274 Other countries: 118	Italy: 1.000 Spain: 1.000 Greece: 2.000 Turkey: 2.500 TOTAL: 6.500

³ The target value estimations are based on the assumption that 20% of the population of Young People of the pilot locations will be reached through the STEP dissemination activities, and that approximately 2 – 5% of these will actually use the STEP platform.

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		TOTAL: 2.058	
Legal and Ethical Compliance	Based on a detailed ethical and legal review, all relevant national and European level requirements are met, enabling the solution to be delivered competitively across the EU and participating countries.	0 complaints so far	All pilots should comply with the ethical guidelines in this sector. Minimum amount of complaints (less than 1% among the service's users) should be expressed.
Sustainability and Awareness			
Number of additional public authorities interested in adopting STEP	Demonstration in 4 pilot countries	Italy: 7 Spain: 14 Greece: 4 Turkey: 6 TOTAL:31	Italy: 2 Spain: 2 Greece: 2 Turkey: 2 TOTAL: 8
Number of Young People informed about STEP	Demonstration in 4 pilot countries	Italy: 10.000 Spain: 15.434 Greece: 32.000 Turkey: Over 80.000 TOTAL: Over 137.434	Italy: 4.500 Spain: 3.500 Greece: 19.000 Turkey: 54.000 TOTAL: 62.000
Number of Young People informed about STEP beyond the pilot area	Demonstration in 4 pilot countries 5% of the national youth population 18-29	Italy: 460.000 Spain: 648.190 Greece: 55.000 Turkey: Over 2.000.000 TOTAL: 3.163.190	Italy: 350.000 Spain: 300.000 Greece: 50.000 Turkey: 500.000 TOTAL: 1.200.000

Indicator: "Number of Young People involved in pilot"

As far as the first indicator of success is concerned, "Number of Young People involved in pilot", it should be noted that the total number of people, who visited the STEP platform, were informed about the dialogues and/or participated, is 9.929. This number refers to all 7 STEP pilots (6 local and the EU pilot) and includes both the users who were registered and those who participated in the dialogues anonymously. Although the project activities were targeted to young citizens, older people were not discouraged to participate (as was requested by the pilot partners, with the aim to conduct inclusive procedures). Since there is a number of users who didn't fill in the "age" field and there were also a lot of anonymous users, the total number of young users was based on an estimation. First we calculated the percentage of the registered users who belong in the age group of 16-30 years old. Then we applied this percentage to the number of the anonymous users. Based on the above, we estimate that the number of the young citizens (16-30 years old) who participated in the STEP local pilots is 7.204 users. It should be noted though that around 400 European citizens participated in STEP open dialogues through the EU pilot. If we calculate the percentage of young EU pilot users, and add this number to the number of young users who participated in local pilots we can see that the total number of young users in the STEP platform is 7.475. The table below presents the total number of users for each STEP pilot:

Table 2 Number of users on the STEP platform

STEP pilot	Total Number of users	Percentage of young users (16-30 years old)	Estimated Number of young users
Locride	1.740	91%	1.583
Mollet del Vallés	2.377	53%	1.260
Valdemoro	290	71%	206
Region of Crete	1.210	73%	883
Thessaloniki	213	59%	126
Hatay	3.701	85%	2.616
EU pilot	398	68%	271
TOTAL	9.929		6.945

As one notices in the tables above, the targets have been reached for Italy and Spain.

The pilot of Locride managed to succeed its target since the number of young users who participated in the pilot is 1.583 from a total number of 1.740 registered. An analysis on the sex of the users shows that female users seem to be more active in digital participation in Locride, since the percentage of female users goes beyond 50%.

Locride pilot area: Users percentages per age group

Locride pilot area: Users percentages per gender

Figure 1 Locride Pilot Demographics

The total number of users in MdV's pilot is 2.377, 53% of which are between 16-30 years old. MdV managed to reach the target for the whole Spain achieving more than 1.200 young users. Additionally, we notice that the percentages of male – female users are almost absolutely balanced.

MdV pilot - users age group

MdV pilot area: Users percentages per gender

Figure 2 MdV Pilot Demographics

The case of Valdemoro is different. Although the Municipality of Valdemoro is located in Spain, the total number of users is 290, from which 71% are young citizens. It should also be noted that male users hold a percentage of 59% compared to female who hold the 36%.

Valdemoro pilot area: Users percentages per age group

Valdemoro pilot area: Users percentages per gender

Figure 4 Valdemoro Pilot Demographics

There was participation of young people in Greece and especially in Turkey, but these two pilots didn't reach the expected targets. The number of users in Greece is 1.423, from which 1.009 belong to the ages between 16-30 years old. However, it should be noted that ROC and Thessaloniki hold the higher percentage of female users (57% and 60%).

Crete pilot area: Users percentages per age group

Crete pilot area: Users percentages per gender

Figure 3 Crete Pilot Demographics

Thessaloniki pilot area: Users percentages per age group

Thessaloniki pilot area: Users percentages per gender

Figure 5 Thessaloniki Pilot Demographics

Turkey's pilot was the one that managed to gather the higher number of users, 3.078 in total. A percentage of 85% were young users. Additionally, Hatay has the highest percentage of male participants compared to all the STEP pilots.

Hatay pilot area: Users percentages per age group

Hatay pilot area: Users percentages per gender

Figure 6 Hatay Pilot Demographics

Even though EU pilot has not a separate indicator, it should be noted that it reached almost 400 users in total; 271 of which belong to the age group of 16-30 years old. The majority of the users of the EU pilot are female with a percentage of 56%.

EU pilot: Users percentages per age group

EU pilot: Users percentages per gender

Figure 7 EU Pilot Demographics

Indicator: “Number of policy makers involved in pilot”

As far as the indicator “Number of policy makers involved in pilot” is concerned, all pilot partners achieved their target, while Creete exceeded it. The names of the policy makers, as well as their positions are indicated in the table below.

Table 3 Policy makers involved in STEP pilots

Number of policy makers involved in pilot	Name / Position
Locride	1. Domenico Stranieri mayor of the Municipality of Sant’Agata del Bianco
	2. Anna Romeo Deputy Mayor of the city of Siderno (RC)
	3. Rosario Rocca Mayor of the Benestare and President of the Municipalities association of Locride area
	4. Federica Roccisano – Regional ministry of education Calabria region
	5. Franco Candia Mayor of the Municipality of Stignano ad President of the assembly of mayors of Locride area
	6. Giorgio Imperitura - Mayor of the Municipality of Martone
	7. Giuseppe Rossi – vicemayor of the Municipality of Sant’Agata del Bianco
	8. Maria Cecilia Gerace – vicemayor of the city of Siderno in charge of youth policies
	9. Gianna Lanzafame – vicemayor of the city of Siderno
	10. Giuseppe Strangio - councilor of of the Municipality of Sant’Agata del Bianco
	11. Pasquale Brizzi - Mayor of of the Municipality of Sant’Ilario Jonio
	12. Sara Tedesco - councilor of of the Municipality of Sant’Ilario dello Jonio
	13. Jaime Gonzales Molina - councilor of of the Municipality of Sant’Agata del Bianco
	14. Letizia Monteleone - councilor of of the Municipality of Sant’Agata del Bianco
	15. Domenica Bumbaca – couicilor of the city of Locri in charge of youth policies
	16. Domenico Maio – President of the Municipality council of Locri
	17. Giuseppe Certoma - Mayor of the Municipality of Roccella Jonica
	18. Domenico Panetta - Head of Municipality technical office of Sant’Ilario Jonio
	19. Paolo Commisso - Responsible of Municipality office of youth and social affair of the city of Siderno
	20. Chiara Stalteri - Responsible of Municipality office of social affairs of San Luca
Mollet del Vallés	The first 7 shortlisted politicians work at the municipality of Mollet del Vallés, while the 8 th is a representative of another Municipality

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	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Josep Monràs i Galindo, Mayor 2. Mireia Dionisio, responsible for urban and economic development, sustainability and housing 3. Josep Maria Garzón, economy and innovation 4. Mercè Pérez, culture, social right and occupation 5. Ana Maria Díaz, social services and civism 6. Raúl Broto, education, labor market, young people, international relations and EU projects and IT 7. Martí Turegano, urban landscape and neighborhoods 8. Albert del Amor, representative from the municipality of Figaró-Montmany, where he is responsible for transparency, local development, participation and young people
Valdemoro	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. M^a Teresa Montero Catalina: Technician and head of the Department of Education 2. Gonzalo Martín González: Technician of the Department of Education 3. Pedro Frontelo; Technician of the Department of Environment 4. Cesar Puerta; Technician of the Department of Environment 5. Ana Bárcena: Technician and head of the Department of Informatics and New Technologies 6. Luis Miguel Martínez: Technician of the Department of Informatics and New Technologies 7. Santiago Bretones: Technician of the Department of Youth 8. Amaya Prado: Psychologist of the Department of Youth 9. María Dávila: Educator of La Morda (House with youth at risk of social exclusion). 10. Roberto González: Educator of La Morda (House with youth at risk of social exclusion). 11. Edelmiro Galván: Head of the Department of Communication 12. Olga Moreno: Technician of the Department of Tourism
Region of Crete	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Arnaoutakis Stavros, Governor 2. Kalogeris Nikolaos, Vice Governor of Environment, Spatial Planning and Energy 3. Alexakis George, Vice Governor of European and International Issues 4. Lymperakis Petros, Member of the Environmental Committee 5. Daskalaki Kalliopi, Member of the Environmental Committee 6. Giannoulis Nikolaos, Member of the Environmental Committee 7. Tzedakis Stavros, Member of the Environmental Committee 8. Fasoulakis Konstantinos, Member of the Environmental Committee 9. Levaki Olga, Member of the Environmental Committee 10. Papadakis Aristidis, Member of the Environmental Committee 11. Mataliotakis George, Member of the Environmental Committee 12. Deiktakis Ioannis, Member of the Environmental Committee 13. Alexakis Nikolaos, Member of the Environmental Committee 14. Xilouris Nikolaos, Member of the Environmental Committee 15. Orfanos Stilianos, Member of the Environmental Committee 16. Apostolos Voulgarakis, Vice Governor of the Regional Union of Chania 17. Lioni Maria, Vice Governor of the Regional Union of Rethimno, 18. Koukiadakis Evripidis, Vice Governor of the Regional Union of Heraklion

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 19. Petraki Pelagia, Vice Governor of the Regional Union of Lasithi 20. Lampros Kampourakis, Regional Councilors of Education
Thessaloniki	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lina Liakou, Deputy Mayor 2. Maria Sitzoglou, External Consultant (Resilient Thessaloniki)
Hatay	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ömer Faruk Çelebi Mayor's Adviser 2. Lütfü Savaş Hatay Metropolitan Municipality (HBB) Mayor 3. Mehmet Maden Hatay Metropolitan Municipality Secretary General 4. Hasan Maden Former HBB Secretary General 5. Prof. Dr. Nazan Savaş 6. Mustafa Dönmez HBB Head of Parks and Gardens 7. Mehmet Bozkurt HBB Head of Cultural Affairs 8. Sevilay Bardakçı HBB Parks and Gardens Senior Architect 9. Samim Kayıkçı HBB Parks and Gardens Phd. Dr Senior Engineer 10. Çise Akın 11. Fevzi Kilisli 12. Sait Günel Former HBB Deputy Secretary General 13. Neçmettin Çolak Former City Clerk 14. Orçun Kılıçoğlu Acting city Clerk 15. Mehmet Mursal HBB Deputy Secretary General 16. Ceyhun Çiviroğlu HBB Head of Public Relation 17. Selim Matkap Deputy Mayor 18. İlmitin Boz Deputy Mayor 19. Fevzi Kilisli Mayor's Adviser 20. Ahmet Saldıran Government Project Office 21. Mehmet Güzelmansur Regional Political leader

Indicator: "Number of decision-making procedures piloted through STEP"

As it is indicated in Table 1, Italy and Turkey could not reach the 3rd indicator of success. These partners decided to focus their resources on fewer dialogues than, but with a high impact. However, Greece and Spain overexceeded their target.

Indicator: "Number of downloads of STEP app"

An indicator that was quite difficult to be reached by all the pilot partners was the "Number of downloads of STEP app". According to the the feedback that was gathered from the the pilot partners this indicator could not be reached for several reasons, presented below:

- Young people tend to download apps that they use at least a couple of times per day; otherwise they are not interested in downloading them.
- Limited access to internet - not all young people have data on their mobile phones and they have to go to civic and/or cultural centers as well as to libraries to have access to public wifi connection.
- The majority of base smartphone versions have limited capacity in terms of memory.
- Most of young users preferred to register in the platform using their computer.
- At the beginning of the open pilot, there were some technical problems and bugs at the app. The current situation of the apps market and usability is very competitive and users do not accept errors in an App.

- Some scenarios, such as the “Questionnaire” is not supported by the app, so a lot of users who participated in such kinds of dialogues could only have access through the desktop.
- Young people are not interested in a new app if it is not known and their friends do not use it. Also, they are not attracted by a platform focused only on one topic, because they want to express their concerns of any topic in the same platform; like Twitter, Instagram or Facebook.

Additionally, analysing the STEP.green access data (Google Analytics data) we can identify a divergence between reach and engagement within youths’ behaviour. This divergence in terms of visiting-engaging (web & mobile browser) and downloading-engaging (mobile App) can be justified in a number of reasons.

As with the rest of the mobile Apps in Google Play or Apple Store, same trends apply to STEP.Green Apps⁴; and as highlighted by latest surveys (including an EU-wide small scale survey conducted in 1300 persons by DRAXIS) and literature, mobile applications tend to receive less than 50% of the browser traffic (either for products, services, information channels, etc.) with the exception of a handful of mobile Apps (facebook, Youtube, messaging apps etc.)^{5,6}.

The starting point of understanding this trend is to recognize that most people use on average 5 apps on their mobile device and ignore the rest that are already installed there by default^{7,6}. Most people have no legit information about which apps are available and in their majority they do not engage in searching randomly in an app store. Instead, the majority goes to their browser on their mobile device (phone, tablet etc.), access the page that interests them⁸, e.g., the website of the newspaper of their choice and then use the browser to read the newspaper instead of searching and downloading the respective app⁹. This is also obvious in the figure below, where we can see that 31% from the total visits to the step.green platform derive from browsers in mobile phones/tablets.

Step platform users access point

Figure 8 STEP Platform Demographics

⁴ The Global Mobile Report: How Multi-Platform Audiences & Engagement Compare in the US, Canada, UK and Beyond, comScore Whitepaper, 2015

⁵ Mobile Marketing Statistics compilation 2017, Smart Insights.

⁶ comScore Mobile Advisor Report, 2017

⁷ Morgan Stanley Research note on comScore Data, 2017

⁸ Mobile Apps vs. Mobile Web: Do You Have to Choose?, Business.com, 2017

⁹ Morgan Stanley Research note on comScore Data, 2017

Secondly, considering that smart devices still face memory constraints and that a substantial amount of available apps is of mediocre quality (negative intentions towards apps from unhappy previous installations and uses), users are only going to download and engage with a small fraction of the apps available on the market¹⁰.

Users are nowadays highly selective about which apps that they select to install to their phone and if they do, they compare the functions and usefulness they receive of having the app installed to the functions and usefulness they receive while browsing the available web-mobile version^{11, 12}. Given that the majority of the sites, including step.green platform site, are fully responsive, easily accessible and share the same number and quality of functions, users prefer to refrain from using the App. The result is high App download rates and low retention rates within a small period of time (on average 2-3 days)¹³.

Conclusively we can conclude in two facts for the users in general and for the STEP users:

- a) The desktop and mobile browser have and retain much greater audience in contrary to the respective apps &
- b) Users prefer to spend the majority of their mobile time with a very few heavily used apps, while utilising the browser for the rest of their web engagement.

It should be noted that apart from the citizens, who participated in the local pilots another 118 people outside the pilot countries downloaded the STEP app. Given the wide reach that the EU pilot dialogues had and the respective promotion actions that were performed, it is expected that some users outside the “pilot countries” have been reached and participated.

Indicator: “Number of additional public authorities interested in adopting STEP”

As far as the “Number of additional public authorities interested in adopting STEP” indicator is concerned, this indicator was exceeded by all the pilot partners. The template below presents the authorities that were informed and showed a specific interest for STEP. The Municipality of Thessaloniki, in Greece is already using STEP, as an additional pilot partner. For the rest of the authorities, additional time is needed, since engaging citizens in digital participation is a process that demands a lot of time and human resources.

Table 4 Additional public authorities interested in adopting STEP

Target per STEP pilot country	No of additional public authorities interested in adopting STEP	Name of the Authority
Italy: 3	7	Municipality of Siderno (main city in the Locride areas) Metropolitan city of Reggio Calabria Aspromonte National Park Municipality of Bologna Municipality of Florence

¹⁰ Geertjan Wielenga, Oracle Product Manager, Oracle Blogs, 2017

¹¹ How Mobile Apps Stack Up Against Mobile Browsers, eMarketer, 2016

¹² comScore Mobile App Report, 2016

¹³ Pinch Media Analytics Report, 2016.

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		Municipality of Genoa Municipality of Turin
Spain: 12	14	Ajuntament de Badalona Ajuntament de Barberà del Vallès Ajuntament de Cerdanyola del Vallès Ajuntament de Girona Ajuntament de Granollers Ajuntament de Mataró Ajuntament de Prat del Llobregat Ajuntament de Rubí Ajuntament de Sabadell Ajuntament de Santa coloma de Gramanet Ajuntament de Terrassa Ajuntament de Vic Balearic Islands Municipality Lucena Municipality
Greece: 2	4	Municipality of Thessaloniki (already adopted) Municipality of Chalandri Municipality of Amaroussion Municipality of Athens
Turkey: 2	6	Samandağ Municipality Defne Municipality Besiktas Municipality Bursa Municipality Istanbul Municipality Izmir Municipality

Indicator: “Number of Young People informed about STEP” & “Number of Young People informed about STEP beyond the pilot area”:

The targets of the last two indicators have also been achieved by all pilot partners. Since the dissemination activities addressed a quite high number of young citizens, in order to calculate these numbers, the pilot partners took into account both the online and offline dissemination activities, as well as interviews in Regional and National TV channels, radios, newspapers/press, presentation of STEP in big fairs, festivals, etc. Once they came up with the total number of people, who were informed about STEP, they estimated the percentage of young people, who belong in the age group of 16-30 years old. In order to find the final number, each pilot extracted a percentage estimating that there were some citizens who were informed about STEP more than one times.

The table below presents the project objectives, indicators and the targets defined for the submission of the original STEP proposal, while Table 6 presents those objectives that are evaluated, in particular through the questionnaires conducted with Young People and Policy Makers/Public Officers.

Table 5 Project Objectives, Success Indicators and Targets

Objectives	Success Indicators	Unit	Target value
O1: To enable public authorities to quickly open their decision-making processes to Young People	a. Environmental policy making services delivered through the STEP platform	No.	15
	b. Adoption of STEP solution by the public authority	%	70%
	c. Increased understanding of opinion of Young People	%	70%
O2: To enable young citizens to participate in decision-making on issues with environmental impact	a. Increased participation of young citizens in environmental policy making processes	%	100%
	b. Increased trust of young citizens in political activities	%	100%
	c. Increased involvement of youth organisations – institutions	%	100%
	d. Relevance of content presented to the user through social media mining tool	%	100%
	e. Accuracy of automatically translated content	%	80%
O3: To develop engagement and motivation strategies for increasing youth participation in environmental decision making	a. Increase in efficiency of social media campaigns	%	100%
	b. Young People engaged / Young People informed	No.	> 0.1
O4: To pilot test the services in an operational environment in terms of technical, organisational and legal feasibility, with the participation of end users (young citizens) and policy makers	a. End users involved in pilots	No.	8,200
	b. Policy makers involved in pilots	No.	85
	c. Acceptance of the STEP platform	%	70%
	d. Involved representatives from all participating and effected social levels (Social Map)	No.	10%
O5: To assess the usability, effectiveness and impact of the project in embedding open engagement in public sector processes, and to identify the key barriers for wide scale deployment	a. Stakeholder satisfaction with organisations' performance in meeting its charter	%	60%
	b. Utility level of the STEP solution	%	100%
	c. Legal and Ethical Compliance	y/n	y
O6: To ensure appropriate (state of the art) dissemination and realistic exploitation of project activities and results	a. Visits to the project website	No.	45,000
	b. Young participants in the open events	No.	4,800
	c. Distributed dissemination material	No.	10,000
	d. User downloads of STEP app	No.	6,500
	e. Total end users informed	No.	1,500,000
	f. Total policy makers informed	No.	250
	g. Additional public authorities interested in adopting STEP	No.	8
	h. Prices and business models defined	y/n	y

Table 6 Mapping of Survey Questions to Objectives and Evaluation Criteria Type

Objective	Success Indicator	Evaluated by Question (via YECs YEC YEC Questionnaire)	Evaluated by Question (via Public Officers Questionnaire)	Evaluation Criteria Type
O1c	Increased understanding of opinion of YP	8, 11	8b, 8d, 8e, 13b	OUT (Outcome)
O2a	Increased participation of YP	14	8b, 10, 13c	OUT
O2b	Increased Trust	5d, 5e, 6g, 12	13a, 20	OUT, PRO
O2d	Relevance Content presented via Social Media Mining Tool	7d, 8f	9a	SYS (system) & PRO (process)
O2e	Accuracy translated content	7c, 8g	15	SYS
O4c	Acceptance of STEP platform	6, 7, 13,14, 15	17, 18	OUT
O4d	Involving all social levels	-	8b, 10, 11,12	PRO & OUT
O5a	Stakeholder satisfaction with organisations performance in meeting its charter	5f, 8a	13d, 16	PRO
O5b	Utility level of STEP	5, 7	5,6 7, 8, 13b, 13c, 14,19	SYS, PRO
	🔴 Usability/Accessibility	6a, 6b, 6c, 6d, 6e	6, 7,	SYS
	🔴 Effectiveness	9, 10	8, 9	SYS, PRO, OUT
	🔴 Barriers	16,17	14, 19	PRO & SYS
O5c	Legal & Ethical Compliance (NB: SYS evaluation will be done but not as user evaluation)	6h	13e	PRO

The numbers in Table 6 have been amended from D5.2 due to the inclusion of extra questions in the survey and slight re-ordering. We can see that a number of project objectives/indicators have been clearly mapped onto the questionnaire questions.

Table 7 Number of questionnaire responses obtained from each pilot

Number of Survey Respondents	Young European Citizens	Public Officers	Total
Mollet del Vallés	16	1	17
Valdemoro	57	3	60
Region of Crete	40	4	44
Locride	61	4	65
Hatay	71	6	77
Thessaloniki	25	1	26
TOTAL	270	19	289

Total number of responses received from the user questionnaires was **270** Young People and **19** Public Officers, **289** in total (Table 7). A discussion, analysis and a breakdown of responses are provided in the sections of this deliverable associated with the questionnaire (the whole section 5). Below in table 8 we report on the qualitative interviews conducted, with 12 Young People and 9 Public officers, 21 in total.

Table 8 Interviews conducted in each pilot

Number of Interviews conducted	Young European Citizens	Public Officers	Total
Mollet del Vallés	2	2	4
Valdemoro	2	1	3
Region of Crete	2	2	4
Locride	4	2	6
Hatay	2	2	4
TOTAL	12	9	21

3.1 Report on pilot operation

In what follows we present the STEP public participation framework, as well as the procedures of the STEP pilot implementation.

3.1.1 The STEP public participation framework

The implementation of the STEP pilot was based on the STEP public participation framework. In order to develop this framework the STEP team took into consideration a number of guidelines and toolkits (described in D5.1, Chapter 2.2.1) selecting at the end the most suitable ones according to the STEP project characteristics.

STEP public participation framework structure is mainly based on the PanEuropean Best Practice Manual on eParticipation¹⁴. This approach includes 5 basic steps:

STEP 1: Background

This step is about mapping the general context of the pilot, and starts at the beginning of the project.

STEP 2: Planning:

The planning step includes the main preparation activities and sets concrete goals, timeframe, responsibilities, and rules. This is the first step for realizing what has been sketched out in the Background.

STEP 3: Action:

The actual pilot execution of the e-participation process, once the environment is prepared and the whole process planned.

STEP 4: Communication:

This is a key step that includes all the communication activities which will be performed throughout the pilot lifetime. The most important mission of this step is to engage young people and increase STEP popularity.

STEP 5: Feedback and evaluation:

¹⁴ <http://eparticipation.eu/>

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Feedback is an iterative process as the collected input by the platform users enhances and enriches the evaluation process, while the quality of the evaluation enables continuous improvement and learning through its implementation.

The duration of the 5 basic steps along with the project activities is presented in the Figure below.

Figure 9 STEP public participation timeline

The work on Step 1 started at the beginning of the project, so as to map the decision making processes and the legislative framework and identify the key stakeholders.

The work on Step 2 also started at the beginning of the project, when the pilot partners identified the issues of environmental interest that they would bring under public dialogue. A detailed pilot plan was presented in D 5.1 and updated in D5.2. This was an ongoing process, as the STEP pilot partners were coming up with additional environmental topics.

The work for Step 3 started on Month 18 and included the training of the pilot partners, the testing of the platform with the core team and the STEP open pilot, which started when the platform was launched to the general public.

The basic work for Step 4 started on Month 10 and was based on the local dissemination plans (D7.1 1st Dissemination Plan and D7.7 2nd Dissemination Plan). However, the promotion of STEP started since the very beginning of the project.

The work for Step 5 started on Month 18, when the platform was ready and the STEP pilot began. This period encompasses two reports, an Intermediate Evaluation report (D5.2) which has already been submitted, as well as the current deliverable.

As it is indicated in D 5.2 – Intermediate Evaluation (Chapter 2.1), the STEP pilot is broken down into 4 phases.

1st phase: (M18-M19): Training of the public officers on the STEP platform (M18-M19)

2nd phase: (M19-M20): Establishment of the core group and implementation of internal testing on the STEP platform. During this phase all partners were invited to share their feedback and report any issues, problems and bugs. The ultimate goal of this phase was to ensure that the platform meets users' needs and is ready to go public. The dialogue under the name "User Feedback on STEP Platform" that was created in this period remained open and can be accessed not only by all partners, but also by users in case they want to report any issue or problem they encounter.

3rd phase: (M21-M29): Implementation of the STEP pilot. The STEP platform was launched to the general public by the pilot partners in order to be tested by young citizens in real context. The launching of the STEP platform was initially planned in M21 (February 2017) and dialogues were uploaded on the platform by the pilots at this time period. The STEP Platform with its main functionalities was available and ready as planned in February 2017. However, due to some minor bugs, like broken links to download mobile apps, invitation email issues, translation quality issues and lack of tutorials for PA administrators to manage their dialogues, there was a short delay to the launching of the platform. These issues were resolved and the pilots started their official dialogues at the beginning of March 2017. Generally, the pilots were implemented based on the initial plan (described in D5.1.) and the updated one (described in D.5.2). It should be noted though that this plan was dynamic, and each pilot adjusted it according to its special needs and the timeframe that was more convenient. Additional dialogues were uploaded on the platform by some pilot partners, while a number of online and offline activities took place in order to promote the STEP platform to the young citizens. All these activities are described in detail in D7.8 3rd Report on Dissemination Activities. This Chapter describes each local pilot operation in terms of dialogues uploaded, evaluation of completed dialogues, number of citizens registered in each pilot, lessons learnt by each pilot, etc.

4th phase: (M18-M30): The 4th phase which refers to the evaluation of the pilots was an ongoing phase that took place along the pilot implementation.

3.1.2 *The STEP Scenarios*

A set of scenarios describing the different use cases of the STEP platform were defined during the first year of the project. These scenarios incorporate both top-down and bottom-up approaches and are presented in detail in Chapter 3 of D5.1 - Definition of STEP pilots and evaluation methodology. The scenarios that use the top-down approach are the following:

- Consultation
- Consultation on Environmental Impact Assessments
- Round table discussion
- Timeline
- Conversation

The scenarios with a bottom-up approach are:

- Call for petitions
- Call for ideas

During the 2nd phase of the pilot (M19-20) the STEP pilot partners together with the core team used these scenarios for internal testing purposes. During the internal testing period the pilot partners realized that the most appropriate and applicable to their needs scenarios were the "Consultation" and the "Call for ideas", so these two scenarios were the main that were essentially used during the STEP open pilot. Consultation on Environmental Impact Assessments was used only by the Region of Crete, as it was specifically included for this partner.

As the STEP pilot was moving forward, an additional scenario was added into the list with the top-down scenarios' approach, the "Questionnaire". This scenario has been extensively used by the STEP pilots and included Single-answer, Multiple-answer questions, or a combination of both according to the environmental issue that was brought under public participation and the needs of each pilot.

At the time that the pilot plans were formulated, the other scenarios (Round table discussion, Timeline, Conversation, and Call for petitions) seemed less attractive to the STEP pilots, who considered that they were not that interesting for decision making on environmental issues but they suggested that they might work better for other topics such as education.

3.1.3 Moderation

The Moderation framework was defined during the first year of the project and is fully described in Chapter 3.7 of D5.1 – "Definition of STEP pilots and evaluation methodology the project". The moderation framework sets out recommendations on how the STEP pilot teams should react on user generated comments and posts. It highlights the rules used by the administrators, identifies good practices with respect to moderating user comments and general guidance on how to manage the online performance.

According to the Moderation framework, the pilot administrators are in charge of controlling the posts on the platform and intervening when it is necessary. All platform administrators visited the platform on a daily basis in order to review all the dialogues for inappropriate user-generated comments or posts, spamming, insulting user-generated dialogues, as well as to review the new user profiles. The accounts of the users, who didn't comply with the terms of the platform, were deleted, a number of posts with inappropriate content were removed from the platform, while spam posts were also detected and removed as well. Additionally, the inappropriate content in the STEP platform that was a result of the social media mining tool was removed by CERTH.

3.2 A summary of each Pilot's use of STEP

This chapter intends to give further insight in the STEP pilot and to highlight the key elements of each STEP local pilot in order to identify the unexpected wins or the missing links within the entire process from designing the platform till conducting e-participation process within diverse cultural and political contexts, local pilots in 6 cities and 1 European level pilot. The STEP platform was officially launched to the local pilots on March 2017, while the EU pilot went public in July 2017. Since then all the pilot partners have been uploading dialogues on the STEP platform. The activities performed from November 2016 until May 2017 are described in detail in D 5.2 – Intermediate Evaluation. Each STEP pilot used the platform in different settings (cultural characteristics, types of dialogues, environmental issues, etc.), which has enabled the consortium to collect useful experience for conducting e-participation procedures with young citizens.

The total number of citizens, who visited the STEP platform, were informed about the dialogues and/or participated, is 9.929 in total. The figure below presents the age groups of the STEP users. As one notices the 80% of the STEP users belong in the age group of 16-30 years. Additionally, it should be noted that there is almost a perfect balance in the percentages of the female and male users. The 50% of the registered users are female, while the 49% are male. The two indicators of the age group and the gender are also presented below for each STEP pilot separately.

Step platform : Users percentages per age group

Step platform: Users percentages per gender

Figure 10 STEP Platform Demographics

Within a time period of 9 months (March - November 2017) 101 dialogues in total were uploaded onto the STEP platform from the 7 STEP pilots; 4 private and 97 public dialogues. From these 101 dialogues, 17 were reported as concluded in D 5.2, while the rest 81 are reported in the next subsections of this chapter. The 101 dialogues that were uploaded on the platform included, public dialogues on environmental issues, public dialogues about additional topics, indirectly linked to the environmental sector, as well as engagement dialogues. The main goal of the engagement dialogues was to attract the interest of young citizens, so as to register in the platform and get familiar with the STEP platform. Both the STEP platform, and the dialogues were promoted by the local pilot partners through a number of online and offline activities. These activities are reported in detail in D7.8 “3rd Report on Dissemination activities.

In what follows we present a summary of the piloting activities for each of the STEP pilot. More specifically, among others the following report makes an overall assessment of the STEP platform usage and impact regarding the following aspects for the 7 pilot projects:

- Local youth engagement
- Policy makers comprehension of STEP as an e-participation tool
- Level of interaction between policy makers and young people
- Integration of STEP outputs into the local policy development (existing or new)
- Overall effectiveness of STEP into the different types of cultural and political context of the pilots

The evaluation process duration was 2 months and was conducted according to the following steps:

1. Review of the STEP deliverables:

- D2.1 Report on decision-making procedures
- D5.1 Definition of STEP pilots and evaluation methodology
- D5.2 Intermediate Evaluation

2. Main Questionnaire for each of the 7 pilots (see [Appendix C](#))

3. 50’ Skype Interview with the administrator of each pilot

4. Data Harvesting and Processing

5. SWOT Analysis for each of the 7 pilots

This brief evaluation is based on the content of the previous STEP deliverables and responses of the administrators of each pilot.

Additionally, the dialogues and the results of each STEP pilot are presented, as well as the changes in the local pilot plans. The most successful dialogue and the lessons learnt from each pilot follow. We present this from their own perspective of each pilot, reporting on what has been achieved, what lessons have been learned, what has worked well and also what has not worked. This helps in having a clear idea about the specific aspects of the piloting activities of STEP.

3.2.1 Region of Crete (RoC)

The Region of Crete managed to gather 1,210 users from which 883 were between 16-30 years old. The primary goal for the RoC pilot was to achieve youth participation in the public consultation of the Environmental Impact Assessments Studies (EIAs), carried out for medium- and large-sized projects and activities, as well as for performing debates on crucial environmental issues, such as the management of aquatic resources, climate change, land use etc. Although the primary goal was not achieved, it is fair to acknowledge that the dialogues on the STEP platform managed to raise awareness regarding environmental issues and most importantly introduce to the young citizens the concept of participating in the local decision making. The awareness campaigns had a considerable impact as it increased the number of young users and it influenced the decision making process for the topic discussed on the STEP dialogue.

The SWOT analysis that follows, presents the internal and the external environment of RoC's pilot case.

Table 9 SWOT Analysis of the RoC pilot

<p><u>Strengths</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Committed core team willing to expand their skills ● Strong & fruitful Partnerships (ex. ARCELLON) 	<p><u>Weaknesses</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Access to young audience ● Communication ● Short dialogue timeframe ● Dialogue Content /Dialogue Text (ex. titles) ● Limited responsibility on issues that have direct impact on everyday life of the citizens ● Lack of short term implementation projects ● Limited portfolio ● Lack of previous experience in interactive participatory processes with youth ● Basic understanding of the participatory process (insufficient training)
<p><u>Opportunities</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Existing legal framework ● Existing vision for a stronger regional e-governance model ● Promoting E-participation ● Potential appropriate topics for public consultation(environmental awareness) 	<p><u>Threats /Challenges</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Political will ● Bureaucracy

Strengths:

- Regardless of the lack of previous experience or specific expertise on civic participation in decision making, the administrative team of the RoC pilot showed great commitment and will to invest time and explore the new potential of establishing a communication channel process with local youth through using the STEP platform.
- The administrative team managed to establish new partnerships with local stakeholders that led to greater engagement of the local youth and broaden the scope of the discussions on the STEP platform.

Weaknesses:

- The titles used for the majority of the dialogues were not very attractive to the young audience. The primary goal of the RoC pilot was to achieve youth participation in the public consultation of the Environmental Impact Assessments Studies, which is a very explicit subject with specific terminology. Although the dialogue text was simplified for the purpose of the dialogue, the titles remained long and descriptive. Users of digital tools and especially young people who mainly use social media to communicate, stay updated and express themselves, get exposed everyday to massive influx of information. In order to attract their attention, the headline of the message needs to be brief, attractive and ideally visualized too.
- The single-sector portfolio of the STEP administrative team (all members were employees from Environmental Departments) deprived the team from a liaison- facilitator between the local authority and the local youth. Additionally, it limited the spectrum of topics posted on the STEP platform.

Opportunities:

- Environmental issues is a subject that can be tangible / visible / understandable to everyone. It is an appropriate subject for public consultation and has the potential to become particularly interesting to young people.
- The existing legal framework for civic participation in the local decision making alongside with the vision of the regional authority for a stronger e-governance model, provide the opportunity to establish a structured public consultation process by leveraging the momentum that has been developed during the STEP pilot - testing phase.

Threats:

- The team who was administrating and creating the dialogue content had limited flexibility for the dialogue content, since the Environmental Impact Assessments Studies that were released for consultation were predetermined. Dialogues including contests also needed additional bureaucracy in order to be approved.
- Internal communication was challenging in this pilot as the team members were located in different cities. They were referring to different local audiences, since the priorities and daily issues differ from place to place. Creating a unified dialogue that could spark the interest in young residents of three different cities can be particularly challenging.

In summary, the RoC pilot had two main challenges to overcome in order to achieve participation of young people. Firstly, being a Regional Authority and not a Municipality limited their dialogue content to more high level decision making rather than issues/projects that affect the citizens' daily life. Secondly, the administration core team was consisted of employees exclusively from Environmental Departments which limited both their variety on dialogue subjects and their access to young audiences. Additionally, the overall environmental decision making procedures in Greece, as well as the procedures in Crete, are complicated and include a lot of legislation and technical information with which the young people are not familiar. Even

though the Region of Crete tried to simplify the dialogues and include features to attract young people, it didn't work so well. The most of the "call for ideas" dialogues used were also of the same philosophy, since they had to be included in a procedure of the Region of Crete. Petitions with a "yes" or "no" answer would have more audience, but such possibility is not legally provided to the authority.

The Region of Crete released the highest number of dialogues of all the Pilots, with a total of 46. The dialogues concerning the consultation on Environmental Impact Assessments were 33 in total; 12 were reported in D5.2, while the rest of them are reported in the current deliverable. The table below provides more quantitative data for each dialogue. As one notices the number of people who participate in Consultation of Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) Studies is quite low. It should be noted that even though there are not many comments on the studies, the Region of Crete believe that the online consultation procedure is quite important, since it is an easy way for citizens to find information about local projects and post their comments promptly and conveniently. Moreover, if we compare the number of the people who participated in EIA dialogues in the first three months of the STEP pilot (reported in D5.2), with the numbers below, we notice that this number has been slightly increased. This is an important advancement for the Region of Crete since the Environmental Impact studies do not belong in the main areas of interest of young people and prior to STEP not even one young person participated in the offline procedure of the consultation of the Environmental Impact studies.

Table 10 RoC Dialogues

Issue	Scenario	Type	Start	End	Questionnaire respondents	Total posts
Environmental Impact study of the project for the protection of the road in Kourtalioti forge from rocks falling	Consulation EIAE	Public	14/12/2016	14/6/2017	18	7
Energy savings and greenhouse gas emission reductions	Call for ideas	Public	23/3/2017	31/7/2017	51	16
Environmental Impact study for a new unit for the incineration of dead livestock and pet animals as well as animal by-products	Consulation EIAE	Public	18/4/2017	2/6/2017	-	7
Environmental Impact study for the wastewater treatment unit of Palaikastro, Lasithi	Consulation EIAE	Public	18/4/2017	2/6/2017	0	0
Environmental Impact study for the Digea's antenna located in Ierapetra	Consulation EIAE	Public	18/4/2017	2/6/2017	-	6
Call for ideas for the Southern Road of Crete	Call for ideas	Public	20/4/2017	31/08/2017	6	1
Make your everyday life greener	Call for ideas	Public	20/4/2017	31/12/2017	-	20
Environmental Impact study for the hotel "ELEFThERIA", located in Agia Marina, Chania	Consulation EIAE	Public	24/4/2017	2/6/2017	-	11

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Environmental Impact study for a new hotel with 770 beds which will be built at Petre, Rethymno	Consulation EIAE	Public	24/4/2017	4/6/2017	-	12
Environmental consequences from uncontrolled uses of land	Call for ideas	Public	11/5/2017	31/10/2017	26	2
Call for Ideas about the Natura 2000 areas in Crete	Call for ideas	Public	18/05/2017	15/09/2017	49	18
Environmental Impact study of improvements in the Bramianon Dam in Ierapetra, Lasithi	Consulation EIAE	Public	5/6/2017	15/07/2017	3	0
Environmental Impact study of setting the boundary lines and adjusting the flow in a part of the stream at the location 'Kouremenos', Sitia, Lasithi	Consulation EIAE	Public	5/6/2017	15/07/2017	-	5
Environmental Impact study of the hotel "Blue Bay" at the location Achlada, Municipality of Maleviziou, Heraklion	Consulation EIAE	Public	5/6/2017	15/07/2017	-	7
Environmental Impact study of a new hotel in the location "Madaros", at Karoti of Rethymno	Consulation EIAE	Public	5/6/2017	15/07/2017	-	9
Environmental Impact study of port infrastructure in Kastri-Keratokampos beach	Consulation EIAE	Public	5/6/2017	15/07/2017	0	0
Environmental Impact study of a new bypass road in Paxia Ammo, at the Municipalities of Ag. Nikolao and Ierapetra, at Lasithi	Consulation EIAE	Public	5/6/2017	15/07/2017	-	4
Accessibility in public space	Call for ideas	Public	11/6/2017	30/6/2017	-	15
Environmental Impact study of a new hotel (5 stars category) outside Gerani village of the Municipality of Platanias, Regional Union of Chania	Consulation EIAE	Public	24/07/2017	31/08/2017	4	0
Environmental Impact study of a new hotel with golf facilities in Chersonisos, Heraklion	Consulation EIAE	Public	24/07/2017	31/08/2017	3	0
Environmental Impact study for the oil mill of the Agricultural Cooperative of Kritsa, Municipality of Ag.	Consulation EIAE	Public	24/07/2017	31/08/2017	3	0

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Nicholas, Regional Union of Lassithi						
Environmental Impact study for the project of rehabilitation of the Katsambas traffic junction in Nea Alikarnassos, Municipality of Heraklion	Consulation EIAE	Public	24/07/2017	31/08/2017	0	0
Environmental Impact study for the construction of walls and pavements from Gournes to a former American base	Consulation EIAE	Public	24/07/2017	31/08/2017	-	0
Consultation on the modification of the Environmental Impact Study of the Plakiotissa dam of Messara, Heraklion	Consulation EIAE	Public	24/07/2017	31/08/2017	2	0
The protection of Caretta-Caretta in Crete	Call for ideas	Public	16/06/2017	10/10/2017	91	22
Water protection and management in Crete	Call for ideas	Public	6/9/2017	15/11/2017	66	15
Environmental Impact study of existing hotel by the beach of Kavros, at the Municipality of Apokoronas, Regional Union of Chania	Consulation EIAE	Public	6/9/2017	14/10/2017	12	2
Environmental Impact study of the hotel RINELA BEACH at the location Konnini Chani, of the municipality of Chersonisos, Regional Union of Heraklio	Consulation EIAE	Public	6/9/2017	14/10/2017	19	3
Environmental Impact study for the Hazardous Healthcare Waste Management Unit in the industrial area of Heraklion	Consulation EIAE	Public	6/9/2017	14/10/2017	0	3
Adaptation to climate change	Call for ideas	Public	20/09/2017	10/11/2017	64	30
Photography Contest "Crete-Environment"	Call for ideas	Public	20/09/2017	31/10/2017	-	16
Environmental Impact study for modification of the Chania airport	Consulation EIAE	Public	1/11/2017	10/12/2017 Open dialogue	9	1
Environmental Impact study for the establishment of a new dairy plant in Rethimno	Consulation EIAE	Public	1/11/2017	10/12/2017 Open dialogue	0	0
Environmental protection and management of Kourna Lake	Call for ideas	Public	1/11/2017	31/01/2018 Open dialogue	0	1

The last three dialogues remain open after the end of the project in RoC’s pilot. A more specific dialogue was initiated about the protection of Kournas Lake in Chania, in order to record the willingness of young people for the sustainable touristic exploitation of the area and the required actions for reclamation. It is intended that the results of this dialogue will be used for the next year action plan of the Directorate of Environment and Spatial Planning.

The table below presents the results of Crete’s pilot dialogues. As far as the EIAs are concerned, citizens’ feedback has been taken into consideration during the consultation procedure. Additionally, for each study, the comments were taken under consideration by the Directorate of Environment and Spatial Planning in the in order to form an opinion and to make a suggestion to the Environmental Committee of the Region of Crete in order to express a positive or negative opinion about the study. Apart from the EIAs, the Region of Crete uploaded additional 13 dialogues on general environmental issues that are further described in the following table. It is quite obvious that young users of the platform were more interested in debates on environmental issues than in the EIAs. Environmental issues put on debate were easier to understand and were more directly connected with the everyday life of Young People, in a way that allows them to take actions for the environment.

Table 11 Results of RoC’s dialogues

Dialogue	Brief Description
Environmental Impact study of the project for the protection of the road in Kourtalioti forge from rocks falling	25 citizens participated in this dialogue, with 18 opinions expressed. The outcome of the questionnaire indicated that young people consider the environmental impacts of the activity shall be prioritized and taken under serious consideration when improving road network accessibility. Further to the consultation procedure for this study, the Region of Crete is also responsible for the construction of the project. All feedback received in this dialogue with regards to the environmental impacts will be taken under consideration and addressed during the construction phase as well. The constructor and his supervisor will be informed about the results of the public consultation of the study.
Energy savings and greenhouse gas emission reductions	11 posts and 51 answers of the questionnaire received. The outcome was a great variety of suggested actions that should be taken to reduce greenhouse emission (energy saving, renewable energy sources etc). Furthermore, the answers of the questionnaire highlighted public transportation and bicycles as preferred alternatives in order to reduce emissions from transportation. In addition, it was highlighted that improvements in the shell of buildings are also needed to reduce energy consumption. All feedback received will be taken into consideration during the ongoing Energy Planning of Crete and some of the suggestions could potentially be included as pre-required conditions for granting new investments. In addition, suggestions were made to disseminate the energy saving concept to schools etc. The Region of Crete intends to consider and implement those suggestions by promoting energy saving at

	<p>schools. The specific dialogue was also used during the STEP project and platform presentation in a number of dissemination events (launch events, technical university etc) and the young people were encouraged to participate.</p>
<p>Environmental Impact study for a new unit for the incineration of dead livestock and pet animals as well as animal by-products</p>	<p>This dialogue was created to open the Environmental Impact Study consultation procedure for a new dead animal incineration unit. Two comments were made in this dialogue. Respondents indicated that the incineration is necessary to avoid risk of infection from dead animals. The comments received were taken under consideration in the document that was sent to the Environmental Committee of the Region of Crete, in order to express a positive or negative opinion about the study. The announcement of the dialogue on the Region of Crete website was very useful, as well as the invitations that were sent, since they gave the feeling that a more direct channel of communication exists between the policy makers and the people.</p>
<p>Environmental Impact study for the wastewater treatment unit of Palaikastro, Lasithi</p>	<p>This dialogue was created to open the Environmental Impact Study consultation procedure for the waste water treatment unit in the area of Palaikastro in Lasithi. No comments were received. The lack of comments is probably because most of the already registered users do not live in the Regional unit of Lasithi, or perhaps are not interested in this specific dialogue.</p>
<p>Environmental Impact study for the Digea's antenna located in Ierapetra</p>	<p>This dialogue was created to open the Environmental Impact Study consultation procedure for the DIGEA antenna located in Ierapetra. One comment and 5 responses were received to this dialogue/questionnaire. The comment expressed the inappropriateness of environmental studies for existing antennas. The user considers that electromagnetic radiation should be measured for public health reasons. The questionnaire outcome identified the most important impacts of the antenna. The result showed that the young people think that landscape deterioration and electromagnetic radiation are the main impacts. The user feedback was taken under consideration during the consultation procedure. Feedback received was quite general and not sufficient to start any other action on behalf of the Region of Crete (RoC).</p>
<p>Call for ideas for the Southern Road of Crete</p>	<p>This dialogue was created to engage citizens and youths allowing them to express their opinion and thoughts regards a new road that is planned in the southern Rethimno. A questionnaire to record the priorities of the people about the transportation network and their perceptions in the southern Rethimno was also included. The respondents highlighted that a quick and safe transportation network shall be the priority. The dialogue was</p>

	<p>mostly used to engage youths in the platform, allowing them to express their opinion and thoughts as well as to provide ground for creative dialogue.</p>
<p>Make your everyday life greener</p>	<p>This dialogue was created to provide valuable grounds for the young people to improvise about environmental ideas. The dialogue enabled young people to suggest their own actions in order to ensure a better environment for themselves. 20 posts were received in the dialogue. Youths referred to a great variety of things- suggested actions to be implemented such as: recycling, green spots inside the town, energy consumption, bicycles use, greenhouse emissions, plastic bags etc. The posts received, are probably influenced by ongoing campaigns of international environmental organizations, social media references etc. and they clearly show that users ask for a change in everyday behavior of the people, especially with regards to behavioral changes in common habits that affect the everyday life of the town.</p>
<p>Environmental Impact study for the hotel "ELEFThERIA", located in Agia Marina, Chania</p>	<p>This dialogue was created to open the Environmental Impact Study consultation procedure for the hotel "ELEFThERIA". One comment and 9 responses were received to this dialogue. The comment highlighted the significance of the area for touristic reasons. Questionnaire responses highlighted "Waste water treatment" as the most important impact of the hotel unit in the area. The user feedback was taken under consideration during the consultation procedure. Feedback received was quite general and not sufficient to start any other action on behalf of the RoC.</p>
<p>Environmental Impact study for a new hotel with 770 beds which will be built at Petre, Rethymno</p>	<p>This dialogue was created to open the Environmental Impact Study consultation procedure for a new Hotel unit in the Petre area. One comment and 11 responses were received to this dialogue. The comment highlighted the "impact" that the new unit will have to the area. The questionnaire outcome identified the most important impact of the new Unit in the area and highlighted the significance of proper waste water treatment establishment. The users' feedback was taken under consideration in the document sent to the Environmental Committee of the Region of Crete in order to express a positive or negative opinion about the study.</p>
<p>Call for Ideas about the Natura 2000 areas in Crete</p>	<p>This dialogue was created a) to engage citizens -youths within a fruitful discussion about Natura areas, and b) to provide them with information, through maps, video and links for further information, about the Natura areas in Crete. A simple questionnaire was included in the dialogue to understand how familiar are Crete citizens, with the term Natura. From the 49 responses to the questionnaire, provides an</p>

	<p>overview of the people’s perception about the Natura area. The comments made by the users in the dialogue highlighted the need for better dissemination and promotion of the Natura area. The concept and the results of the dialogue are in an agreement with the strategy of the Region of Crete about the Natura area and the recent project assignment to the Natural History Museum of Crete to further study the biodiversity of the island.</p>
<p>Environmental consequences from uncontrolled uses of land</p>	<p>This dialogue originated from the Spatial Planning Dept. of the Region of Crete. The scope of the dialogue was to record the thoughts-opinions of people with regards to mixed activities inside the cities, e.g. their thoughts about their urban environment, urban development etc. Feedback of this dialogue will be taken under consideration by the Department of Spatial Planning. Although the users participated in the dialogue, the dialogue itself was not very suitable for the purposes of the Step Crete pilot, since spatial planning has many legal limitations and does not allow or include public consultation.</p>
<p>Environmental Impact study of improvements in the Bramianon Dam in Ierapetra, Lasithi</p>	<p>This dialogue was created to open the Environmental Impact Study consultation procedure for the improvements that are to be undertaken in the Bramianon Dam. Zero comments and 3 responses were received to this dialogue. The questionnaire responses showcased that young people consider the reduction of water and solid materials downstream, because of the dam, as the most important impact. The users’ feedback was taken under consideration in the document sent to the Environmental Committee of the Region of Crete in order to express a positive or negative opinion about the study. Even though the dialogue was promoted on behalf of the RoC, the participation was low.</p>
<p>Environmental Impact study of setting the boundary lines and adjusting the flow in a part of the stream at the location 'Kouremenos', Sitia, Lasithi</p>	<p>This dialogue was created to open the Environmental Impact Study consultation procedure for the setup of the boundary lines and of the flow adjustment performed in a part of the stream at the location 'Kouremenos'. Zero comments and 3 responses were received to this dialogue. The questionnaire responses showcased that young people consider that encroachments are the most important problems in rivers and streams. The users’ feedback was taken under consideration in the document sent to the Environmental Committee of the Region of Crete in order to express a positive or negative opinion about the study. Even though the dialogue was promoted on behalf of the RoC, the participation was low.</p>
<p>Environmental Impact study of the hotel: Blue Bay” at the location Achlada,</p>	<p>This dialogue was created to open the Environmental Impact Study consultation procedure for the “Blue Bay” hotel. Zero comments and 4 responses were received to this dialogue. The</p>

<p>Municipality of Maleviziou, Heraklion</p>	<p>questionnaire outcome identified the most important impact of the hotel unit in the area and highlighted the significance of proper waste water treatment establishment. The users' feedback was taken under consideration in the document sent to the Environmental Committee of the Region of Crete in order to express a positive or negative opinion about the study. Even though the dialogue was promoted on behalf of the RoC, the participation was low.</p>
<p>Environmental Impact study of a new hotel in the location "Madaros", at Karoti of Rethymno</p>	<p>This dialogue was created to open the Environmental Impact Study consultation procedure for the new hotel unit at "Madaros" area. Zero comments and 5 responses were received to this dialogue. The questionnaire outcome highlighted the significance of proper waste water treatment establishment. The users' feedback was taken under consideration in the document sent to the Environmental Committee of the Region of Crete in order to express a positive or negative opinion about the study. Even though the dialogue was promoted on behalf of the RoC, the participation was low.</p>
<p>Environmental Impact study of port infrastructure in Kastri - Keratokampos beach</p>	<p>This dialogue was created to open the Environmental Impact Study consultation procedure for the new infrastructures along the beach at Lasithi. No comments were received. Even though the dialogue was promoted on behalf of the RoC, users did not engage with the dialogue.</p>
<p>Environmental Impact study of a new bypass road in Paxia Ammo, at the Municipalities of Ag. Nikolao and Ierapetra, at Lasithi</p>	<p>This dialogue was created to open the Environmental Impact Study consultation procedure for the new bypass road in Paxia. Zero comments and 4 responses were received to this dialogue. The questionnaire respondents highlighted the disposal of a large amount of waste soil from the excavations the most important environmental impact of the project. The users' feedback was taken under consideration in the document sent to the Environmental Committee of the Region of Crete in order to express a positive or negative opinion about the study. Even though the dialogue was promoted on behalf of the RoC, the participation was low.</p>
<p>Accessibility in public space</p>	<p>This dialogue was created taking advantage of the P_public festival, that was sponsored by the Regional Unit of Chania, in order to further open the public discussion of the limitations with regards to the accessibility in public spaces in the towns of Crete. Two comments and 15 responses were received in this dialogue. The questionnaire respondents highlighted a substantial number of issues that Chania are facing, causing several accessibility problems to citizens. The user feedback will be taken under consideration when new constructions in public spaces are</p>

	<p>planned, so that interventions that improve accessibility are also included. The STEP platform had the opportunity to participate in the the p_public festival, organized by young architectures in Chania, and present the dialogue and the project. An information point with leaflets, banner and on the spot access of the platform were secured in the festival venue.</p>
<p>Environmental Impact study of a new hotel (5 stars category) outside Gerani village of the Municipality of Platania, Regional Union of Chania</p>	<p>This dialogue was created to open the Environmental Impact Study consultation procedure for the new hotel unit outside Gerani village. Zero comments and 4 responses were received to this dialogue. The questionnaire respondents are worried about the impacts in the caretta-caretta reproduction area. The users' feedback was taken under consideration in the document sent to the Environmental Committee of the Region of Crete in order to express a positive or negative opinion about the study. Even though the dialogue was promoted on behalf of the RoC, the participation was low.</p>
<p>Environmental Impact study of a new hotel with golf facilities in Chersonisos, Heraklion</p>	<p>This dialogue was created to open the Environmental Impact Study consultation procedure for the new hotel with golf facilities in Chersonisos. Zero comments and 3 responses were received to this dialogue. The questionnaire respondents are worried mostly about the water consumption by the golf facilities. The users' feedback was taken under consideration in the document sent to the Environmental Committee of the Region of Crete in order to express a positive or negative opinion about the study. Even though the dialogue was promoted on behalf of the RoC, the participation was low.</p>
<p>Environmental Impact study for the oil mill of the Agricultural Cooperative of Kritsa, Municipality of Ag. Nicholas, Regional Union of Lassithi</p>	<p>This dialogue was created to open the Environmental Impact Study consultation procedure for the oil mill of the Agricultural Cooperative of Kritsa. Zero comments and 3 responses were received to this dialogue. The questionnaire responses showed that young people are worried mostly about the pollution of the ground water. The users' feedback was taken under consideration in the document sent to the Environmental Committee of the Region of Crete in order to express a positive or negative opinion about the study. Even though the dialogue was promoted on behalf of the RoC, the participation was low.</p>
<p>Environmental Impact study for the project of rehabilitation of the Katsambas traffic junction in Nea Alikarnassos, Municipality of Heraklion</p>	<p>This dialogue was created to open the Environmental Impact Study consultation procedure for the rehabilitation of the Katsambas traffic junction in Nea Alikarnassos. No comments were received. Even though the dialogue was promoted on behalf of the RoC, the participation was low.</p>
<p>Environmental Impact study for the</p>	<p>This dialogue was created to open the Environmental Impact</p>

<p>construction of walls and pavements from Gournes to a former American base</p>	<p>Study consultation procedure for the project of developing current infrastructures (walls and pavements) on the road from Gournes to the American base. No comments were received. Even though the dialogue was promoted on behalf of the RoC, the participation was low.</p>
<p>Consultation on the modification of the Environmental Impact Study of the Plakiotissa dam of Messara, Heraklion</p>	<p>This dialogue was created to further open the consultation procedure of the Environmental Impact Study for the modifications required in the Plakiotissa dam of Messara. No comments were received. The questionnaire respondents perceive the landscape degradation as the major impact of the project. The users' feedback was taken under consideration in the document sent to the Environmental Committee of the Region of Crete in order to express a positive or negative opinion about the study. Even though the dialogue was promoted on behalf of the RoC, the participation was low.</p>
<p>The protection of Caretta-Caretta in Crete</p>	<p>The dialogue was created to provide the users general information about the legal requirements for the protection of the sea turtles Caretta Caretta. The dialogue was developed with the help of Archellon, a NGO that is active in Crete. The dialogue was supported by a simple questionnaire in order to identify how familiar are the users with the implementation of those requirements. Users were also invited to post their ideas and suggestions on measures and actions that could strengthen the protection of Caretta-Caretta. 22 comments and 91 answers of the questionnaire were received, and the respondents showed that they are familiar to the problems and aware of the legislative framework and of the actions needed to be implied by local businesses and from the Region of Crete. Some of the users posts expressed complains about the degradation of the beaches where Caretta Caretta make their nests, because of the tourism. However, some others provided their suggestions to improve the nesting environment and asked for further informative campaigns for the public. All suggestions and opinions were discussed during the meeting between the Department of Environment and Hydronomy of Chania- Rethimno, the Department of Environment of Heraklion and Archellon, that took place at the end of the season (October 2017) in order to develop and coordinate their strategy for the next year.</p>
<p>Water protection and management in Crete</p>	<p>This dialogue was developed for the needs of the consultation procedure of the Strategic planning of water protection and management in Crete. The dialogue included promotion video from the Ministry of Environment, maps and photos to better present its purpose. It also included a questionnaire requesting</p>

	<p>people to prioritize the proposed measurements. There were 15 posts and 66 answers of the questionnaire. The posts included interesting user's opinions and valuable proposed actions. The feedback of the dialogue, the priorities the users gave to their needs, will be used by the Region of Crete to prioritize for long term planning and future actions. Feedback received, was not in contrast to the planning, but the priorities the users gave to their needs can be used long term in order the Region of Crete to prioritize the future actions of the strategic planning of water management and protection (e.g. financial support for water saving etc). The strategic planning of water management and protection is a large collection of actions and measures that are going to be implemented by 2021 in order to improve the condition of water (quality and quantity) in Crete.</p>
<p>Environmental Impact study of existing hotel by the beach of Kavros, at the Municipality of Apokoronas, Regional Union of Chania</p>	<p>This dialogue was created in order to further open the consultation procedure of the Environmental Impact Study of an existing hotel at Chania. Two comments and twelve responds (questionnaire) were made in this dialogue. The first one expresses a positive opinion about the study, while the other one arises a general problem of the waste water treatment in the municipality. The outcome of the questionnaire was the result of 12 answers that showed that young people are worried about the waste water management of the hotel. The users' feedback was taken under consideration in the document sent to the Environmental Committee of the Region of Crete.</p>
<p>Environmental Impact study of the hotel RINELA BEACH at the location Konnini Chani, of the municipality of Chersonisos, Regional Union of Heraklio</p>	<p>This dialogue was created in order to further open the consultation procedure of the Environmental Impact Study for an existing hotel at Heraklio. Three comments and nineteen responses (questionnaire) were made in this dialogue, mainly addressing water consumption, energy footprint and coastal protection. The respondents of the questionnaire showed that young people are mostly worried about the waste water management of the hotel and the water consumption. The users' feedback was taken under consideration in the document sent to the Environmental Committee of the Region of Crete.</p>
<p>Environmental Impact study for the Hazardous Healthcare Waste Management Unit in the industrial area of Heraklion</p>	<p>This dialogue was created to further open the consultation procedure for the Environmental Impact Study for a Hazardous Waste Management Unit. Three comments were made in this dialogue, highlighting the usefulness of such units. Also, a notification about the wastewater treatment of the unit was made. The users' feedback was taken under consideration in the document sent to the Environmental Committee of the Region of Crete in order to express a positive or negative opinion about the</p>

	study.
Adaptation to climate change	This dialogue was created as an initial step to the legal obligation of the Region of Crete to develop a plan in order the better adaption in the climate change. So, a dialogue was created in order to record the thoughts of the citizens and the priorities they think should be given in this plan (study). A questionnaire was also used to record the user's thoughts. Thirty posts and 64 responses to the questionnaire received to this dialogue. Respondents' posts and questionnaire replies recorded the concerns of the citizens about the climate change, especially regarding the impact that those will have in Crete. Users think that the loss of biodiversity and the lack of water would be the main results of the climate change in Crete. A number of actions that could be implemented were suggested in order to prevent instead of later confronting those results. The results of this dialogue will be forwarded to the monitoring committee that will supervise and deliver the study about the adaptation to climate change that Region of Crete will compose.
Photography Contest "Crete-Environment"	The dialogue was an engagement dialogue to disseminate the platform. A contest was created, and young people were asked to upload a photograph of the natural environment of Crete and also to evaluate the posts of other users. The post with more "Likes" would win a smartphone. 24 posts were received, and the winning post received 61 likes. The winner earned a smartphone, provided by MLS.
Environmental Impact study for modification of the Chania airport	This dialogue was created aiming to further open the consultation procedure of the Environmental Impact Study of Chania Airport. The dialogue is supported by a questionnaire. So far 1 post and 8 questionanire responcees were received. The first respondents to the questionnaire highlighted noise and air pollution as the most important impacts of the airport operation. The results of this dialogue will be forwarded to the Environmental Committee of the Region of Crete in order to express a positive or negative opinion about the study.
Environmental Impact study for the establishment of a new dairy plant in Rethimno	This dialogue was created in order to further open the consultation procedure of the Environmental Impact Study of a diary in Rethimno. The user feedback will be will be forwarded to the Environmental Committee of the Region of Crete and taken into consideration during the Impact study consultation procedure.
Environmental protection and management of Kourna Lake	This dialogue was created aiming to increase public awareness of the current status and problems that Kourna Lake is facing. The dialogue provides information for the current conditions and the legal protection status of the lake and asks from the users'

suggestions and ideas on actions that can be performed to improve the lake conditions.

3.2.1.1 *The RoC pilot plan*

The gantt chart below presents the timeframe of the planned dialogues that were reported in D5.2 for the RoC. As we noted before additional dialogues were added in the RoC’s pilot plan. One of them was the “Accessibility to public space” which was initiated in order to give the chance to the young people who participated in the p_public festival to use the platform and be involved into an e-participation procedure. Two engagement dialogues were also used, so as to attract young people, and one of them included a photograph contest about the natural environment of Crete. The user, who uploaded a photo that collected the most “likes” was awarded with a mobile phone.

In order to increase the young citizens who participate in decision making the Region of Crete avoided to use scenarios, such as “Round table discussions” and “Conversations” and used scenarios, such as “Call for ideas” that were open to the general public. The dialogue for ecotourism was also not included in the pilot plan since there was not an environmental decision making procedure for this topic.

Planned & Implemented dialogues

Table 12 RoC Planned & Implemented dialogues

	May-17	Jun-17	Jul-17	Aug-17	Sep-17	Oct-17	Nov-17	Dec-17	Jan-18
Energy Conservation	Planned	Planned	Planned						
Natura protection	Planned	Planned	Planned	Planned	Planned	Planned			
Make your daily life greener	Planned								
Environmental and other impacts of uncontrolled urban land use	Planned	Planned	Planned	Planned	Planned	Planned			
Water Management actions		Planned	Planned	Planned					
Climate change				Planned	Planned	Planned	Planned		

Planned:
Actual:

Inclusion

In order to include young people with fewer opportunities, personal computers are available in the premises of each Regional Unit, which can be used by young people in order to access the platform. The activities performed by the ROC about the inclusion are mainly described in 5.2.

3.2.1.2 *Successful dialogue of the RoC Pilot & lessons learnt*

The most successful dialogue was that of the protection of the Caretta-Caretta (sea-turtle). This Dialogue seemed to be of interest to a wide range of Young People who mostly completed the questionnaire, some

participants also made posts to the Dialogue. Posts suggested actions such as: having people responsible for watching the sea turtle nesting sites; more educational and promotional activities about sea turtle protection; encouraging the boycotting of businesses who did not comply with current protection measures, for example playing loud music; and restricting the use of plastic on the beaches.

Figure 11 RoC STEP landing page highlighting the Caretta-Caretta dialogue

- Caretta Dialogue gave general information, combined with a lot of pictures and simple questions
- Remained opened for about four months.
- 90 questionnaire responses.
- 21 users posts to the dialogue.
- Social media search tool also revealed 24 posts.
- Mostly promoted by Facebook posts (reach: 1000) and invitations sent via the platform
- Engaged with NGO Archellon, but didn't achieve the expected results despite sharing via Facebook.)

Figure 12 – Facebook Page for RoC STEP showing Caretta caretta dialogue

Lessons learnt from RoC for Youth Engagement:

- The launch events taught us that we have to reach Young People carrying out their own activities.
- The main way we used to reach Young People was our presence in a number of events in order to inform them face to face.
- Dissemination material was widely sent by emails. The e-mailing list and the forum of the Technical University of Crete is viewed by 6500 Young People.
- Invitations to participate in the dialogues were sent to emails provided during the events.
- Frequent Facebook posts, Promotion of posts – 750 followers -Total reach of posts 47.250.

- Giving prizes as awards can enhance youth engagement; competition for most favorable photography of Crete landscape – Facebook posts reached up to 6.000 people, while the trip we granted for STEP’s final event to Berlin Facebook posts reached up to 5.000 people.

Figure 13 – RoC Dialogue Examples (a & b translated) c) STEP Social Media (Facebook) page d) Video about Water management.

The participation of Young People in the Pilots so far is not the expected:

- Fewer dialogues that stayed open for more time probably would have been better.
- There is a legal obligation to set Environmental Studies to public consultation. However, those dialogues had not the expected participation.
- Perhaps it would work better if “Yes” or “No” e-petitions were included.
- Young People were not convinced that e-Participation provides them a tool and it is not an obligation they have to fulfill.
- Public participation is already included in the decision-making procedure, so STEP was just another tool to further open the same procedure to younger people.
- STEP brought public officers closer to Young People and their way of thinking about environment and policy making
- STEP provided public officers with the opportunity to become familiar with strategies for reaching Young People
- Region of Crete mostly apply environmental policies rather than create new policies.

Proposals for the future:

- The project is in alignment with the overall effort of e-government targets of the Region of Crete.
- Planning further use for some chosen Environmental studies of more general interest.
- Further use for e-petitions. However, the Region of Crete mostly apply environmental policies rather than create new policies.
- Perhaps we could extent the platform to social related issues (not only environmental) increasing the flexibility of the Region of Crete.
- Use the platform as a tool in Environmental Education

3.2.2 Mollet del Vallés (MdV)

According to the deliverable D5.1:“Definition of STEP pilots and evaluation methodology”, the primary goal for Mollet del Valles was to use STEP as a complementary tool to their existing participatory model. The goal was successfully reached since the number of participants exceeded the anticipated target. Mollet del Valles (MdV) is a city that has already embraced the concept of civic participation and developed an engaged audience. The STEP platform was a needed component for the existing strategy, designed to strengthen specifically the youth participation in public consultation as it offered an interface design based on their needs and preferences. The citizens of Mollet del Valles were already aware of the participatory concept and familiar with digital tools since the city has been providing the majority of the public services online and employing the participatory budget process for the last few years. Key elements of this pilot’s success was on the one hand the user based design of the platform, making it attractive and interesting for young people and on the other hand the expertise and experience of the STEP platform administration team in working on similar projects.

A SWOT analysis follows with the basic characteristics of the internal and external environment of MdV’s pilot.

Table 13 SWOT Analysis of the MdV pilot

<p><u>Strengths</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Established Department for Public Participation • Highly skilled and committed administrators • Existing effective public participation process • Appropriate projects / topics for public consultation • Strong political will • Online public services • Excellent understanding of the civic participation process • Established children Council • Active youth organizations • Minimum bureaucracy (Administrator was responsible for content approval as well) 	<p><u>Weaknesses</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • City Scale: Limited number of available projects for public consultation
<p><u>Opportunities</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • STEP as a “team incubator” Keeping young people engaged and active. STEP can be used both as a tool for collecting ideas & raising awareness or as a team building tool. • STEP can be used as a complementary tool for already existing long participatory processes. For example, the 6-month preparation of the “Municipal Plan for Young People in Mollet” 	<p><u>Threats /Challenges</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensuring singular ID for platform users.

Strengths:

- For the last few years, the city of Mollet del Valles has managed to perform every civic procedure online, provide a digital signature for every citizen and establish a participatory budget process for short term implementable projects.

Weaknesses:

- The STEP platform is a tool that requires regular interaction with the participants in order to keep them active. The small scale of the city might limit the number of attractive/popular topics that could be directly implementable.

Opportunities:

- The STEP platform can be used as a “team incubator” aiming to keep young people engaged and active.
- The STEP platform can function as an e-Forum where young people have the opportunity to reach out to peers who share the same concerns or aspirations and by posting on the platform they can team up and implement their shared ideas.
- The STEP platform can be a complementary tool for the process of co-designing long term plans. (i.e. Municipal Plan for Young People in Mollet)

Threats:

- It is important to ensure a single ID for the platform users, especially when the STEP platform is used as a voting tool for participatory budget projects. However, requesting many personal details during the registration process might discourage citizens from joining the process. Moreover, it requires high security regulations since the platform administrators will have access to personal information.

In summary, the MdV pilot was extremely successful in terms of recruiting young people to use the STEP platform. This was achieved by a large amount of outreach activities and plenty of face to face contact with Young People at the types of events attended by them. MdV launched a total of 20 dialogues; three of them were reported in D5.2, while the rest of them are being reported in the current one. MdV has also used the STEP platform, in order to provide the citizens with information on the results of some dialogues. As one can see in the tables below, MdV opened three dialogues in order to disseminate the results of three dialogues that were uploaded on STEP.

Table 14 MdV Dialogues

Issue	Scenario	Type	Start	End	Questionnaire respondents	Total posts
Local Plan for Young People: experiences and activities	Innovation	Private	2/03/2017	31/12/2017 Open Dialogue	0	1
City Council	Call for ideas	Private	15/03/2017	31/01/2018 Open Dialogue	0	30
Let’s take a look to Mollet	Call for ideas	Public	16/03/2017	16/06/2017	0	6

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Electric vehicle in Mollet	Innovation	Public	8/05/2017	29/05/2017	0	2
Rumours prevention	E-petition and ideas	Public	14/05/2017	15/11/2017	0	31
Select a project; make your allocation of 100.000 euros of public investment. Participative budget.	Call for ideas	Private	22/05/2017	4/7/2017	1.043	350
Work Group to promote the Strategic Plan of Mollet. Evaluation 2016	E-petition and ideas		23/05/2017	23/07/2017	0	12
What would you improve from "Citizens Attention Office"?	E-petition and ideas	Public	16/06/2017	15/07/2017	58	2
Results of the dialogue "Decide 100.000 euros"	Call for ideas	Public	3/07/2017	28/07/2017	0	42
"Share the Summer City festival"	Call for ideas	Public	14/07/2017	6/9/2017	0	25
Results of the dialogue: "What would you improve from "Citizens Attention Office"?"	Call for ideas	Public	18/07/2017	31/07/2017	0	1
Artisans Fair. Do you like it?	Call for ideas	Private	5/09/2017	17/09/2017	96	35
Winners of the dialogue "Share the Summer City festival"	E-petition and ideas	Public	7/09/2017	13/09/2017	0	0
Consult the projects proposals for and by young people of Mollet del Vallès for 2017	E-petition and ideas	Public	11/09/2017	30/09/2017	0	11
Results of the participative meeting for the Waste Prevention Municipal Plan	E-petition and ideas	Public	14/09/2017	30/09/2017	0	10
Choose the initiatives/projects that you like the most!	Call for ideas	Public	18/09/2017	1/10/2017	645	7
Winners of the dialogue: "Artisans Fair. Do you like it?"	E-petition and ideas	Public	18/09/2017	30/10/2017	0	4

D5.3: Final Evaluation report

The table below presents the results of each dialogue that was uploaded in MdV pilot. It should also be noted that MdV used the STEP platform to upload two dialogues for participatory budgeting. These were the most successful ones in terms of citizens' participation, since the first one "Select a project; make your allocation of 100.000 euros of public investment" achieved over 1000 participants and the second one, an Open-call for Young People suggesting environmental projects, achieved a total of 645 participants. The reason for the success of these two dialogues was that participants could see that a direct action would arise as a result of their participation, the allocation of 100,000 Euros in the first instance to regenerate the chosen area, and 6 x 6,000 Euros for the projects achieving the highest number of votes for the latter. What needs to be noted though is that citizens in MdV have previous experience with such kinds of participatory budgeting public dialogues. The previous participatory budgeting public dialogues were implemented through a different e-participation platform under the name CONSENSUS. Since 2009, once a year MdV invited citizens to prioritize projects and actions to be implemented by the Municipality of Mollet. Based on this fact we can conclude that citizens in MdV have a participatory culture and are quite familiar with such kinds of tools for digital participation.

Table 15 Results of MdV' dialogues

Dialogue	Brief Description
Local Plan for Young People: experiences and activities	This dialogue was formatted to be utilised within the City Plan for Young People core group. The main objective behind this dialogue was to gather feedback and suggestions from the youths and core members of the "City Plan for Young People" group as well as to stimulate interaction between them.
City Council	City Council Members have created and used this dialogue to consult relevant documents and discuss issues during the council meetings (meetings agendas, pictures, etc.). Mainly the dialogue was utilised as an Intranet for the members of the City Council of Mollet del Vallès.
Let's take a look to Mollet	<p>This dialogue scope was to involve and enable citizens into city action planning. Citizens and youths were asked to propose actions to make Mollet more sustainable. Citizens and Youths were invited to send pictures, videos, comments of all the things-places - situations that require attention and suggestions on how they can be easily improved. Feedback received was focused on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sideways that should be wider -Public lighting that should be increased and repaired - Parks where we have to take care of mosquito plagues during the summer season. <p>All comments-suggestions were taken under consideration and were forwarded to the respective city departments to be addressed.</p> <p>Low participation in this dialogue was due to:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) lack of internal coordination b) a secondary application/software was already used for this purpose so confusion was created on the appropriateness of selection.
Electric vehicle in Mollet	The scope of this dialogue was two-fold: a) to inform citizens of the city planned actions to enhance electromobility and b) involve citizens and youths in a fruitful discussion about supplementary actions and incentives that could be given in order to achieve the goal. Participants were asked to join the dialogue and share they opinion / knowledge about electric vehicles. Given the low participation, the municipality

	<p>revised its tactic and concluded that measures and actions need to be implemented to attract citizens and youths to a meaningful and fruitful discussion, and that only the publication - initiation of a dialogue is not sufficient to bring the required results.</p>
<p>Rumours prevention</p>	<p>This dialogue was created to address rumours and fake news within the municipality. The leading role to this dialogue was given to a specific “working group” consisting of the City Council members and the Ombudsman. The scope of the working-group and the respective dialogue, was to evaluate the possibility of establishing the Antirumours network and reviewing whether there was need to upload information to tackle any fake rumours that may circulate across the city. The dialogue was fruitful and successful, since it enabled the City Council and it’s youth members to create a Manifesto against fake information in the city and to establish a procedure to be followed in order to address rumours in the city and respectively to run knowledge campaigns to tackle them.</p> <p>The dialogue was open to the public.</p>
<p>Select a project; make your allocation of 100.000 euros of public investment. Participative budget.</p>	<p>The purpose of this dialogue was to establish a participative process and enable citizens to take decisions about public investments in Mollet del Vallès. For more than one month all citizens were invited to choose their most preferred project from a specific list to invest 100.000 euros from the municipal budget. The most voted project would be implemented at the end of 2017.</p> <p>Citizens participated massively and proposed a great variation of projects to be implemented. The dialogue was very successful, and youths have been truly committed and happy to have the possibility to contribute to this money allocation.</p> <p>Further to the selected “winning” project the municipality has been committed to also take into account the rest of the projects proposed by the dialogue participants and potentially to implement them in the future.</p> <p>Conclusively, it has been a very useful and valuable dialogue, especially from the social dimension, where “3 community leaders” have been observed to work intensively while trying to convince citizens to vote for their initiatives.</p> <p>After the voting process, the difference in votes between the winner (first) and the second proposed project was so low, that the municipality decided to allocate an extra amount of 100.000 euros from the municipal budget to implement the second project in 2018.</p> <p>From the economic dimension it would not be sustainable or financially feasible, for the municipality to launch more than one similar dialogue per year.</p>
<p>Work Group to promote the Strategic Plan of Mollet. Evaluation 2016</p>	<p>This dialogue scope was to provide a common ground for the discussion and evaluation of the City Strategic Plan. Once a year the representatives of the three commissions (a) People b) rural-urban and c) economy & labour of the City Strategic Plan meet and evaluate the implementation of the plan during the previous years. This time a dialogue was created on STEP platform to host this discussion. The results of the dialogue will be shared with the members of the City Council and will be used to tune the City strategic plan for the following year. The feedback of utilising the STEP platform for this purpose, was positive.</p>
<p>What would you improve from “Citizens Attention Office”?</p>	<p>This dialogue was an open invitation on how the Citizens Attention Office, at the City Hall of Mollet del Vallès, can improve the quality of its services towards youths and citizens. Questionnaire respondents highlighted improvements could be performed on the following topics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Waiting time -Procedures - Behaviour of our officers -Others less relevant <p>From the questionnaire responses a report was formatted and sent alongside with</p>

	suggestions to the coordinators of the Citizens Attention Office to evaluate them and take actions if needed. The coordinators of the Citizens Attention Office contacted the core group for the coordination of STEP in the City Hall of Mollet, requesting to utilise STEP platform as a publicly available evaluation tool for their services.
Results of the dialogue “Decide 100.000 euros”	This dialogue was more on the communication side, aiming to inform about the results of the voting within the dialogue “Decide 100.000 euros” where participants had to vote 1 out of 9 possible projects to be funded and implemented. Given the high number of participants and the small difference in terms of votes between the first and the second project, the City decided to go forward with the 2 projects (the first and second) instead of only one.
Share the Summer City festival	This dialogue was formatted to enhance awareness of the STEP mobile app around the Summer City festival. Unfortunately, events (terrorist attacks) that took place during that time, restricted the dialogue from reaching as many youths and target audience as possible. Low response rate has been received to this dialogue.
Results of the dialogue: “What would you improve from “Citizens Attention Office?”	This dialogue scope was to communicate the results of the consultation, about the “Citizens Attention Office” quality of services and improvements. Also, the importance of Youths participation to the dialogue, was highlighted, even though a substantial amount of Youths uses the city electronic services for e-government.
Artisans Fair. Do you like it?	This dialogue aimed to involve citizens and youths to express their opinion and their suggestions on how to improve the Artisans Fair from Mollet del Vallès. A sufficient number of suggestions have been gathered, citizens evaluated several aspects of the fair. Feedback has been gathered and sent to the city culture department, which committed to take it into account for the next fair.
Winners of the dialogue “Share the Summer City festival”	This dialogue was more on the communication side, aiming to inform the Youths over the results of the raffle. It contained the announcement of the winner’s names for the trip to Berlin and for the Theatre yearly ticket.
Consult the projects proposals for and by young people of Mollet del Vallès for 2017	This dialogue was formatted to enable consultation and discussion with citizens and youths over the next city project. Mainly it was an informative dialogue about 8 projects that the city could possibly fund, by allocating 6.000 euros. It is important to take into account that previous to listing those 8 dialogues, the MdV young people department has arranged several meetings with youngsters. As a second step, youngsters were invited to edit a video, to communicate and engage other young people to submit their proposals. The youngsters submitted 12 projects in total and 8 of them were finally accepted. Those 8 projects were the ones that could be consulted in this dialogue.
Results of the participative meeting for the Waste Prevention Municipal Plan	This dialogue scope was two-fold: a) to present the waste reduction plan of Mollet del Vallès and b) inform and request propositions from citizens on actions that can be implemented to reduce the amount of waste in Mollet del Vallès. The citizens’ proposals, including a substantial amount from youths, had been included in the final document towards the next phase, 3rd phase consultation. The City plan alongside with the citizens and youths’ propositions will be further discussed and implemented.
Choose the initiatives/projects that you like the most!	This dialogue was formatted to enable youths to vote on their preferable project to be funded by the city. The available projects had been previously presented in the “Consult the projects proposals for and by young people of Mollet del Vallès for 2017” dialogue. The dialogue was very successful and out of the 8 suggested projects 6 were voted in favour and will be implemented.
Winners of the dialogue: “Artisans Fair. Do you like it?”	This dialogue was more on the communication side, aiming to inform the Youths over the results of the “Artisans Fair. Do you like it?” dialogue/voting results. It contained the announcement of the winner’s names to receive a basket of local organic products.

3.2.2.1 The MdV pilot plan

The gantt chart below presents the timeframe of the planned dialogues that were reported in D5.2 for MdV Municipality. One dialogue (Food policy) was cancelled at the end of the pilot due to the political instability that the Municipality experienced after the Proclamation of the Catalan Republic which has been cancelled by the Spanish Government and the whole process will finish in a regional election that will take place on the 21st of December. Additional dialogues were added in MdV pilot plan, which are presented in the table above.

Planned & Implemented dialogues

Table 16 MdV Planned & Implemented dialogues

	May-17	Jun-17	Jul-17	Aug-17	Sep-17	Oct-17	Nov-17	Dec-17	Jan-18
Artisan's fair					Planned	Planned			
					Actual				
Share the Summer City festival				Planned					
			Actual	Actual	Actual				

Planned: Actual:

As it is indicated by the pilot manager: "At the beginning of the pilot we thought that users will appear in an easier way if we launch topics strictly related to environment. However, we experienced great difficulties in real engagement and this is the reason why we also tried other fields. Despite this we have also launch several dialogues strictly related to sustainability like the Urban Garden, Gallecs and Mollet parks, organic and local food, etc. All in all, we believe that all these new dialogues that we have been adding are the output of two reasons:

- We have achieved a truly political commitment that smoothed a good dissemination of the STEP pilot at internal level. We reached many departments that have taken the decision to pilot dialogues in STEP like the environmental department, young people department, culture department, commerce department, participation department, ect
- The fact of creating a core group of officers from several departments aiming to coordinate the dialogues (content, timeline, etc) has also modified significantly our previous proposal that has been prepared without having the opportunity to have many hours of ongoing work on the dialogues. Our first proposal was the result of a truly political will to open our decision making processes to young citizens but the topics of number of dialogues have been tuned by officers from several departments as well as some social and political circumstances as the terrorist attack in las Ramblas or the Proclamation of the Catalan Republic.

Figure 14– Landing page of Mollet del Vallés, Success Stories of the MdV Pilot

Inclusion:

MdV Municipality was in close collaboration with colleagues from more than 10 civic and cultural centers network, who offered the possibility to young citizens to participate in every STEP dialogue using the public computers, as well as using free access to public wifi. Roll-ups were also placed in all the centers halls, while youngsters who were at risk of social exclusion to participate in the project were specially informed by the Municipality workers.

3.2.2.2 *Successful dialogue of the MdV Pilot & lessons learnt*

According to MdV Municipality, there were two very successful dialogues in the MdV's pilot, which are presented below

Decide on regeneration plan using 100.000 Euros to make Mollet more sustainable: 1,043 users

Goal: Open call for proposals to make our public space more sustainable: 600 submitted.

- 9 proposals were finally outlined, that aligned with the MAP and the city territory.
- The municipality produced a video showing the 9 spots.
- Voting process (via STEP).
- Winning proposal was selected: re-urbanization of a public square to promote pedestrian mobility.
- Exhibition at the city hall and public library.
- Visit to the spot with citizens and officers.
- Possibility for some on-site decisions.
- Arrange a public tender for private companies willing to develop the project.
- Project development.
- Intense communication campaign during the whole process.

Open call for proposals: projects/initiatives for and by Young People: 645 users

Goal: the municipality plans to offer the possibility for Young People to decide on and run their own activities.

- Meetings with young people and invitation to edit a video.
- Communication campaign: social media accounts, website for Young People, etc.
- Allocation of 6,000 euros.
- Dialogue set-up and period for projects submission.
- 12 proposals were submitted and 8 were finally accepted.
- The municipality invites the Young People of Mollet to choose 6 proposals.
- Meetings between the municipality and the 6 winners aiming to allocate the money aligned with the number of votes and the characteristics of the projects.
- Project development (from December 2017).

Lessons Learned regarding Youth Engagement:

- Invested a lot of resources in our summer city festival with no result. It is better to link open dialogues to smaller activities in which the dialogue can have an important role.
- All dialogues have been launched by the municipality and despite this we haven't succeeded in convincing our local associations to lead one, we believe that stakeholders leadership would ensure greater success.
- Despite having a new channel via STEP, in some dialogues it has still been crucial to have a person doing face-to-face interactions.

Overall Lessons Learned MdV:

- The App: from a flagship element to a weakness: Today a youngster's mobile is a "jungle of apps" where only the most appreciated ones are allowed to remain. - Need of wifi connection.
- Several errors during the piloting period.
- Prizes are not the solution.
- Against all odds we've learned that a good prize does not always increase the number of users.
- The best kept secret: to contribute to a real change.
- Mollet has reached success with STEP when citizens were invited to take decision that will have a major/clear impact in the city.

Advice to other municipalities from MdV:

- First - Find a new name for the platform – it should be more meaningful. STEP is also very hard to search for.
- Then - Run dialogues with a direct impact - the only way to make it efficient.
- Keep Dialogues Simple.
- Keep in mind using the tool to disseminate the work you are doing. Don't focus only on the number of users.

3.2.3 Valdemoro

According to the deliverable D5.1: "Definition of STEP pilots and evaluation methodology", the primary goal for Valdemoro's pilot was to create the city's public participation framework and establish a communication channel between youth and the Municipality. Although the participation of young citizens was not the

expected one, it is fair to acknowledge that the dialogues on the STEP platform managed to raise awareness on environmental issues. As it has been made clear from the STEP experience, but also as it is noted by the Municipality workers, Valdemoro is a city with lack of youth participation. Young people don't feel close to politicians and there is lack of trust. This is a result of political instability that citizens experience during the last years. Most probably this is why the number of the users is not the expected one. The fact that the Mayor of Valdemoro changed during the STEP's open pilot is also a fact that most probably affected the progress of STEP. Additionally, one of the basic members of the STEP team in Valdemoro had to leave the team and take a long-term leave. This was a great loss for Valdemoro's pilot since this person was actively involved in the implementation of STEP.

The table below presents Valdemoro's pilot SWOT analysis

Table 17 SWOT Analysis of Valdemoro's Municipality pilot

<p>Strengths</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bridged communication gap between different local stakeholders (politicians, technicians, teachers, youth, associations, NGOs, etc) • Interdepartmental STEP administration team • Minimum bureaucracy (Administrator was responsible for content approval as well) 	<p>Weaknesses</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understaffed Department responsible to initiate and support participatory processes • Weak understanding of the participatory process (insufficient training) • Communication • Lack of previous experience in interactive participatory processes with youth • Lack of short term implementable projects
<p>Opportunities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Youth Community Centers can become the centers for young people to meet, discuss, collaborate and participate • Integrate the Youth Council/ Mayor to the participatory process 	<p>Threats /Challenges</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Youth engagement • Lack of existing framework for participatory processes • Political will

Strengths:

- New communication channels were established because of the STEP pilot testing phase between different local stakeholders.
- The interdepartmental editorial team provided a variety of dialogue topics.
- The STEP administrative team was responsible for both creating the dialogue content and approving it, reducing significantly the required bureaucracy for publishing the dialogue.

Weaknesses:

- The STEP platform was the first e-participation platform that was used by the Municipality of Valdemoro, therefore the targeted audience was not familiar with neither the concept of participating in the decision making process or using a digital tool to communicate with the Municipality.
- Due to lack of previous experience and expertise in participatory processes the planning of the project was not that strong. It required more time than anticipated from the STEP administrative team to approach young people, build strong partnerships and create the right dialogue content to successfully engage the local youth.

Opportunities:

- The STEP platform could potentially be the appropriate tool to empower the already established Youth Council/ Youth Mayor to advocate for the priorities of young people.

Threats:

- The lack of an existing legal framework that sets the guidelines for a proper civic participation process can be a significant drawback in any effort towards implementing meaningful public consultations on major issues that affect the citizen’s daily life.
- Successful civic participation is largely relied on the short term impact of the taken decisions. It is crucial to have strong and committed political will that will eventually ensure immediate implementation.

In summary, the Valdemoro pilot had many challenges to overcome in order to successfully use the STEP platform. However, it managed to create a precedent of youth engagement and thus this STEP pilot testing period set the starting point for the city to create the missing mechanism for actively involving youth into the local decision making process. It is important to highlight that new communication channels were created between the Municipality and local stakeholders as well as promising partnerships for implementing a broader and more successful campaign to increase youth engagement and participation in the coming future.

Figure 15– Valdemoro Landing page

The monitoring of Valdemoro’s pilot was quite intensive and there was a period during which DRAXIS team, that was responsible for the monitoring of the pilots, had weekly skype calls with the pilot administrator. During the calls DRAXIS team and the pilot administrator were discussing take the corrective actions that were needed in order to promote the STEP platform. It should be noted that all the available from the Municipality tools were used for the promotion of STEP. A large number of people were reached through events, activities and workshops but the participation in the platform was not the expected one.

The table below presents the dialogues that were uploaded on the STEP platform.

Table 18 Valdemoro Dialogues

Issue	Scenario	Type	Start	End	Questionnaire respondents	Total posts
Let's take care of our parks	Call for ideas	Public	18/1/2017	31/08/2017	0	26
Ideas for a new cycling route in Valdemoro	Call for ideas	Public	1/3/2017	31/09/2017	34	12
Urban gardens; Responsible and healthy cultivation	E-petition	Public	15/05/2017	31/07/2017	0	11
Keeping the streets clean from dog feces	Call for ideas	Public	15/05/2017	30/09/2017	0	9
Environment in Images	Call for ideas	Public	12/6/2017	30/11/2017	0	73
Saving Water!	Call for ideas	Public	12/7/2017	30/11/2017	0	17
Eco-transport	Call for ideas	Public	12/9/2017	30/11/2017	0	87

The Municipality of Valdemoro brought under public participation 8 dialogues in total; 1 was reported in D5.2, while the other 7 dialogues are reported in the current deliverable. The feedback that was gathered by all dialogues was promoted to the respective departments.

Table 19 Results of Valdemoro's dialogues

Dialogue	Brief Description
Let's take care of our parks	The scope of creating this dialogue was trifold: a) to inform and motivate the citizens in retaining the city parks clean and b) to increase citizens awareness of the city park flora and fauna and c) involve citizens and youths in a fruitful discussion about supplementary actions and incentives that could be given in order to retain city parks clean and valuable to all. 26 posts received by citizens were forwarded to the Department of the Environment that will discuss these proposals and relative actions within the local government.
Ideas for a new cycling route in Valdemoro	The scope of creating this dialogue was to design a new cycling route and parking place in Valdemoro. The creative power of youths that participated to the dialogue resulted in several ideas of new cycling routes in Valdemoro. Feedback received will be forwarded to the municipality respective dept., empowering Valdemoro to be included in a project of the Community of Madrid, called "Cicla Madrid".
Urban gardens; Responsible and healthy cultivation	The scope of creating this dialogue was bifold: a) to inform the citizens about the urban gardens and their advantages b) to assess the citizens demand for urban gardens. Participants to this dialogue supported the idea of urban gardens in their municipality as well as of the significant and positive impact that such actions may have in schools, especially regarding the change in consumer behaviour. All participants underlined the significance of having healthy habits and of consuming sustainable products.
Keeping the streets clean from dog feces	The scope of creating this dialogue was to increase awareness and consult youths over the current situation with regards to dog feces in Valdemoro. Participants to the dialogue expressed their opinions and their suggestions over

	<p>the current situation and how it can be improved. Main issues raised are: it is a big problem to walk the dirty streets with feces, although there are sandboxes, dispensers of bags and posters, the owners of the dogs are not acting responsibly. It was suggested that issuing fines to those that do not comply with relative legislation, could be an initial solution to the problem. No actions were taken further because a motion of censure, within the local government, stopped all activities. Conclusions were forwarded to the respective municipality dept. to support the creation and allocation of space for urban gardens.</p>
<p>Environment in Images</p>	<p>The scope of creating this dialogue was to raise awareness about the environment in Valdemoro and in general. Youths were requested to upload images and post their comments, expressing their vision about environment. Some images reflected positive aspects and other images contained aspects that require attention to be improved. All feedback will be reviewed and will be forwarded to the respective municipality department for further actions.</p>
<p>Saving Water!</p>	<p>The scope of creating this dialogue was to consult young citizens on every day and city water saving actions and about their thoughts on the necessity (or not) of developing a water treatment plant. Respondents to this dialogue suggested a number of actions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) use a rain collection system for the maintenance of parks and gardens; b) control the time of the sprinklers in the parks; c) plant trees that do not need much water; d) save water in homes; e) install flow reducers in taps and cisterns; f) showering instead of bathing, etc. <p>All feedback received will be reviewed and will be forwarded to the respective municipality department for further actions. The results of this dialogue will also be communicated in the upcoming Valdemoro event entitled "Educating City".</p>
<p>Eco-transport</p>	<p>The scope of creating this dialogue was to consult young citizens on ways that public transportation can be improved in Valdemoro e.g. Ecological transport; use of bikes, Segway, go-car, etc; improve infrastructures in buses, train and roads.</p> <p>This is a major topic for the Valdemoro municipality because there are many citizens who use public transport to get around Valdemoro and the nearby cities.</p> <p>Participants to this dialogue suggested a number of actions: to get non-polluting means of transport and better services; hybrid buses, use bikes and Segway's, sharing private cars, transport card in the mobile phone, more trains at some times, bus shelters to protect them from the rain, electronic signs for the bus schedule etc.</p> <p>All feedback received will be reviewed and will be forwarded to the respective municipality department for further actions. This dialogue was also used for the selection of Valdemoro youths that will participate in the STEP final event in Berlin.</p>

3.2.3.1 *The Valdemoro pilot plan*

The gantt chart below presents the timeframe of the planned dialogues that were reported in D5.2 for Valdemoro Municipality. Generally, there were no deviations from the initial and the updated pilot plans. The Municipality of Valdemoro added only one new dialogue in the pilot, which was: Environment in Images.

Planned & Implemented dialogues

Table 20 Valdemoro Planned & Implemented dialogues

	May-17	Jun-17	Jul-17	Aug-17	Sep-17	Oct-17	Nov-17	Dec-17	Jan-18
Ask where to locate new green spaces and park areas in the Valdemoro city	Planned	Planned	Planned	Planned					
Ask young people where to build a path for bike lane in Valdemoro city.	Planned	Planned	Actual	Actual	Actual				
Present how the collection of dog excrement on the streets works and consult young people on new ideas for collection.	Planned	Planned	Planned	Planned	Planned				
Request for more urban orchards; cultivate our healthy foods	Planned	Planned	Planned						
Request to young people of images that represent their environmental concerns		Planned	Planned	Planned	Planned	Planned	Actual		
Consult young citizens on water savings, combined with the development of a water treatment plant.			Planned	Planned	Planned	Planned	Actual		
Ask young citizens to reorganize the urban transport network by giving them the chance to place bus stops					Planned	Planned	Actual		
Ideas for a new cycling route in Valdemoro	Actual	Actual	Planned	Planned	Planned				
	Planned:		Actual:						

Inclusion:

Valdemoro's pilot plan has included initiatives focused on groups of disabled citizens and people at social risk, giving them the opportunity to participate in STEP events and activities, as well as participate in STEP platform dialogues.

3.2.3.2 Successful dialogue of the Valdemoro Pilot & lessons learnt

According to the Municipality, the most successful dialogue from Valdemoro was the “Environment in images” dialogue which achieved a total of 73 participants. Despite the difficulties with regards to the lack of

youth participation, the policy makers involved agreed that their involvement in the project has helped to enhance the awareness of environmental issues in Valdemoro.

The City Council of Valdemoro achieved the following items as a STEP pilot:

- Give prominence to environmental issues.
- Make evident the problem of youth participation.
- Reconcile the City Council with environmental associations.
- Involve of all politicians in the project.
- Create an Advisory Board on environmental issues.
- Create a STEP Web page, and Facebook and Instagram accounts.

The Municipality of Valdemoro as a STEP pilot has achieved the following:

- Create a communication channel between the City Council and stakeholders.
- Become a link between stakeholders and Young People interested in the environmental issues.
- Create a communication channel for Young People to get involved in local environmental decisions.
- Organize public participation procedures to receive feedback on local environmental issues

Youth Engagement Activities:

- Organization of events and activities: Waste collection in the Parque.Bolitas del Airón; Reforestation activities at Castle Hill.
- Promotion of STEP through web and Facebook account of STEP Valdemoro, and social media account of Valdemoro City Council.
- Presentation of the dialogues to Young People in various workshops.
- Involvement of stakeholders directly linked to the issue of this dialogue to promote and participate in the STEP.
- Collaboration of young volunteers.

It is fair to conclude that of all of the Pilots in STEP, Valdemoro achieved a low engagement of Young People participating in the platform. This was partly due to unfortunate circumstances with a key staff member becoming seriously ill part-way through the project. Given the amount of time taken for Public Officers that was required to achieve engagement with STEP, this undoubtedly had an impact on the overall success of the Valdemoro Pilot and the numbers of Young People that the rest of the staff were able to reach. The interviews revealed that many of the dialogue topics did not really resonate all that well with the interests of Young People, which could also contribute to the low level of e-Participation achieved in the municipality of Valdemoro.

3.2.4 Hatay Metropolitan Municipality

One of the largest cities in Southern Turkey, located on the Mediterranean coast, Hatay has recently become a Metropolitan Municipality. Of all of the Pilot partners involved in the STEP pilot activities, Hatay has the largest population of young people; the region also has a very high percentage of refugees due to the recent crisis in Syria which shares a border with Hatay.

The primary goal for the Hatay pilot was to create the opportunity for young people to speak up and influence the decisions that directly affect them. Although initially the goal was to facilitate the communication between the local youth and the Municipality, it's worth to mention that two STEP dialogues resulted in direct implementation of projects that young people highlighted as their priorities.

The SWOT analysis below, presents the internal and the external environment of Hatay's pilot case.

Table 21 SWOT Analysis of Haty's pilot

<p>Strengths</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interdepartmental editorial team for STEP dialogues • Variety in dialogue subjects • Minimum bureaucracy (Administrator was responsible for content approval as well) • Interdisciplinary partnerships with local stakeholders (Educational sector, Environmental sector) 	<p>Weaknesses</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not inclusive audience • Lack of short term implementable projects • Lack of previous experience in digital tools • Basic understanding of the civic participation process (insufficient training)
<p>Opportunities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of STEP as a campaign tool for the upcoming HATAY EXPO 2021 • Promote youth leadership through the newly established partnerships with local stakeholders (politically neutral) 	<p>Threats /Challenges</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Committed Youth engagement • Political will

Strengths:

- The interdepartmental editorial team provided both a wide variety of dialogue topics and a successful horizontal collaboration between the different Municipal Departments, which otherwise wouldn't have been communicating with each other. (siloes processes)
- The STEP administrative team was responsible for both creating the dialogue content and approving it, reducing significantly the required bureaucracy for publishing the dialogue.
- The STEP administrative team had a fair understanding of the participatory process and thus managed to partner from the beginning with the appropriate stakeholders in order to increase the engagement and participation to the platform.

Weaknesses:

- Due to the lack of independent youth organizations an issue of inclusiveness occurred among the STEP young audience. Currently, the only active youth organizations are the ones coordinated and strongly influenced by the political parties.
- Dialogues with more specific and implementable projects could have enhanced the engagement of the young citizens.
- The STEP platform was the first e-participation platform that was used by the Municipality of Hatay, therefore the targeted audience was not familiar with neither the concept of participating in the decision making process or using a digital tool to communicate with the Municipality.

Opportunities:

- The pilot testing phase of STEP platform created a precedent for a digital tool not only for civic participation but also for communication between the local youth and the Municipality. Therefore, STEP offers the possibility to spread the message among the youth for future plans of events coordinated by the Municipality such as the HATAY EXPO 2020.

- The partnerships that emerged during the STEP pilot testing phase between the Municipality, NGOs and educational institutions created the appropriate ecosystem for more youth organizations to flourish, especially independent organizations focused on environmental issues.

Threats / challenges:

- Fostering youth participation in the local decision making and establishing a communication channel between youth and the Municipality is a long term process that requires time and commitment from both sides. It is crucial to have strong and committed political will that will eventually ensure immediate implementation. Nowadays, due to the existing mistrust between authorities and citizens, initiating public dialogues with vague themes or timeframes might result in low engagement and broaden the communication gap even more.

The Hatay pilot managed to reach a high percentage of youth participation while at the same time achieved to prioritize the implementation of projects which were proposed on STEP platform by the young participants. During the pilot, a total of 3.701 participants (3.146 of them are between 16-30 years old) used the platform and 14 unique dialogues were released. The participation was quite high, but there is a number of reasons that Hatay’s pilot could not achieve the initial goal of 3.500 users:

- STEP.green tool was the first tool for digital participation used in Hatay. The young people didn’t have the experience and therefore a significant amount of time was needed to explain what step.green is and how it works. According to the experiences gained, face to face promotion is necessary to persuade young people to use such kinds of tools and this is a quite time demanding and expensive procedure.
- The tool is adequate for its purpose but the youngsters want more active and dynamic tool.
- The lack of interest in policy making and the lack of trust in the government was an important subject as well.
- There is a lack of Young society organizations in Hatay and due to circumstances in Turkey even the young citizens are not courageous enough to express their opinions freely.

The high number of participants is a result of Hatay’s intensive communication and dissemination strategy, which focused in engaging young people in the STEP platform using dialogues that would attract their interest. The dialogues achieving the greatest level of participation were the Expo 2021, the dialogue for new Cycle Lanes and the dialogue for a Greener Hatay (see Success stories for more details later). Many other dialogues also attracted large numbers of participants. The table below presents the dialogues that were uploaded onto the STEP platform.

Table 22 Hatay Dialogues

Issue	Scenario	Type	Start	End	Questionnaire respondents	Total posts
Priority Green for Hatay	Call for ideas	Public	3/03/2017	10/11/2017	0	250
Young create their own parks...	Consultation	Public	31/03/2017	30/06/2017	83	72
EXPO 2021 Hatay... Share your ideas	Call for ideas	Public	2/05/2017	10/10/2017	125	387
What will happen if the green (areas) runs out?	Call for ideas	Public	19/05/2017	21/05/2017	0	133
Mustafa Kemal University graduates	Call for ideas	Public	9/06/2017	11/6/2017	0	105

Choose your bicycle road and win your bicycle....!	Call for ideas	Public	13/06/2017	9/9/2017	75	425
Asi River	Call for ideas	Public	23/06/2017	23/07/2017	0	229
For a Cleaner Hatay	Call for ideas	Public	2/08/2017	15/09/2017	0	8
Let's determine the most beautiful 3 flowers who are growing in Hatay.	Call for ideas	Public	5/10/2017	30/11/2017	0	15
Protecting Living Things & the Environment!	Call for ideas	Public	5/10/2017	30/11/2017	0	2
Step Green evaluation survey	Call for ideas	Public	12/10/2017	24/10/2017	0	2
Step to Berlin.....!!	Call for ideas	Public	7/11/2017	20/11/2017	0	36
Give a voice when you are a volunteer!	Call for ideas	Public	5/12/2017	31/01/2018 Open Dialogue	-	29

Step was a new subject for the Municipality of Hatay and an experience that taught a lot on the topic of digital and generally citizens' participation. At the beginning or the pilot, the dialogues were created by the Municipality and this was not so attractive for the young people. As the open pilot was moving forward, the Municipality of Hatay decided to further involve the youngsters into the preparation of the dialogues. The added value of having an interdepartmental editorial team for the dialogue content was the diversity and flexibility of topics addressed on the STEP Platform. The dialogue variety led to quick wins and provided a broader understanding of the e-participation concept. It should be noted that some of the dialogues that were added in Hatay's pilot plan derived from the users posts in other dialogues. This was quite significant for the engagement of the users, since it was an evidence that the Municipality actually took into consideration the opinions expressed from citizens onto the STEP platform. The table below briefly describes and presents the results of each dialogue.

Table 23 Results of Hatay's Dialogues

Dialogue	Brief Description
Priority Green for Hatay	The main goal of this dialogue was to involve and engage the youngsters around the topic: "what is your idea for a greener and environmental friendly Hatay". The youths participated highly in this dialogue, probably because it contained a simple topic about the city and everyone could express an opinion and get participate. Young citizens that participated highlighted the lack of green space in the city and their wish for an expansion of the green areas. Posts and feedback received have been forwarded to the respective city department for evaluation and relevant actions. Furthermore, a sufficient number of Youths posted complaints about the University road condition and the large amount of garbage all over the city. Due the complains received the Municipality decided to bring forward the plans initially foreseen to be undertaken the following months and initiated several actions to reduce waste and maintenance work

	in several roads especially near the University.
Young create their own parks...	The main goal of this dialogue was to involve and engage the youngsters around the topic of “designing their own neighbourhood parks”. Young citizens that participated highlighted the lack of green space in the city and their wish that those green areas be expanded. Several suggestions were made with regards to parks infrastructure to support different activities. Posts and feedback received has been forwarded to the respective city department for evaluation and relevant actions. Although it can be considered that the dialogue requires “special knowledge” around the topic of green area design, the dialogue received a high number of responses.
EXPO 2021 Hatay... Share your ideas	The main goal of this dialogue was to involve and engage the youngsters around the topic of EXPO 2021 Hatay. The dialogue questions were aiming to reach youngsters for their ideas and opinions about the EXPO event. Posts and feedback received were sent for examination to the relevant departments and will be evaluated from the Experts. The promising ideas will be implemented on the EXPO event.
What will happen If the green (areas) runs out?	This dialogue was created to raise youths’ awareness for the environment and engage them in fruitful discussions within STEP. The dialogue was open during the Book fair in Hatay, where a stand was placed in order to communicate the dialogue and the project. Several participants of the fair showed interest both to the project and to the STEP platform. Following the fair, a draw was performed, and 3 lucky participants were given a number of books.
Mustafa Kemal University graduates	The main goal of this dialogue was to involve and engage the youngsters into the STEP platform. The dialogue was created for the participants of the Mustafa Kemal Universities Graduate Party. The University organized a party with a famous singer. Following a draw, 3 lucky participants won the entrance fee .
Choose your bicycle road and win your bicycle....!	This dialogue was created based on Step participants comments in previous dialogues, where the youngsters were complaining about the lack of Bicycle roads in the city. The dialogue’s main question was “In which part of the city we need the bicycle road at most”. This Dialogue was a remarkable success in terms of getting posts/comment and participation, mainly because the idea derived from the youngsters. Posts and feedback received has been forwarded to the respective city department for evaluation and relevant actions. Furthermore, a drawn was performed following the dialogue and 5 lucky participants won new bikes.
Asi River	The main goal of this dialogue was to involve and engage youngsters in discussion around the Asi river. Asi river comes from Lebanon, pass through the city of Hatay and ends in Mediterranean Sea. The pollution of the river is a big problem for several years now. Posts and feedback received has been forwarded to the respective city department for evaluation and relevant actions.
For a Cleaner Hatay	The main goal of this dialogue was to receive youngsters Ideas for a cleaner and liveable Hatay. Posts and feedback received has

	been forwarded to the respective city department for evaluation and relevant actions.
Let's determine the most beautiful 3 flowers who are growing in Hatay.	This dialogue was created in order to raise the awareness in horticulture sector among youngsters in Hatay. Youngsters were invited to express their opinion and preference to specific species present or not in the parks. According to the posts the parks and gardens Dept. in Hatay Municipality will be more focused on these flowers for the next years.
Protecting Living Things & the Environment!	This dialogue was created aiming to involve youths in a more sustainable living concept and ideas on "how to protect living things (beings) in the city & the Environment". Ideas received had been forwarded to the respective Municipality Dept.
Step Green evaluation survey	This dialogue was created aiming to assist the process of performing the STEP Evaluation Survey.
Step to Berlin.....!!	This dialogue was created aiming to increase awareness and engage youngsters with the "Nature Beauty" in Hatay. Youngsters were asked to locate and capture the natural beauty in a picture and then upload it on the Step platform. Furthermore, participants in the dialogue, following a draw, would be in position to win and participate in the STEP final event in Berlin.
Give a voice when you are a volunteer!	This dialogue was created aiming to raise awareness for volunteer actions at the city and the volunteer's day. The dialogue main question was "what kind of volunteering would you like to contribute in the city". The dialogue is ongoing, and all feedback received by youths will be evaluated. The main idea behind the dialogue is to format groups of Youth Volunteers and enable the spirit of volunteering in city events e.g. EXPOHatay, festivals etc.

3.2.4.1 *The Hatay Metropolitan Municipality pilot plan*

The gantt chart below presents the timeframe of the planned dialogues that were reported in D5.2 from the Municipality of Hatay. As it can be seen in the dialogue tables above, additional dialogues were brought under public participation according to the needs of the pilot.

Planned & Implemented dialogues

Table 24 Hatay Planned & Implemented dialogues

	May-17	Jun-17	Jul-17	Aug-17	Sep-17	Oct-17	Nov-17	Dec-17	Jan-18
Priority for Green Hatay	Planned								
Bicycle road planning	Planned								
Asi river cleaning concepts	Planned								
Let's determine the 3 most beautiful flowers that are growing in Hatay.	Planned								

Planned: Actual:

Inclusion:

The Municipality created alliances with some Environmental NGOs, Political Youth parliaments and Volunteers in Hatay, like “Genc Thema Hatay” and “Hatay Defne tıbbi aromatic bitkiler doğaya dönüş derneği”. The Municipality also tried to include the Refugees in the project but it proved to be very difficult to get them interested in e-democracy or the environment. The limited access to internet, the lack of smartphones, and the lack of funding were major problems that couldn’t be tackled.

3.2.4.2 Successful dialogue of the Hatay Metropolitan Municipality Pilot & lessons learnt

Several dialogues had a large number of participants, the three most successful were the ‘Expo 2021’, a dialogue on new Cycle Lanes and the ‘Greener Hatay’ dialogue. The success of the greener Hatay dialogue was attributed to the fact that it was a simple topic, it was easy for Young People to participate as everybody has an opinion about what improvements could be made. Hatay will be the host of the International Expo in 2021, which is a prestigious event for the city to hold, this dialogue has been successful in attracting a lot of interest from Young People. A lot of effort was made by Hatay to carry out outreach activities with young people at the places that young people are found, they particularly targeted Universities to promote the STEP platform, and also attended various events in the city.

Figure 16 Screenshots of the Green Hatay & Bicycle Lane dialogues

Lessons learned from the Hatay Pilot process:

- It’s a good idea conducting e-Participation in the Municipality, it works, but to fully implement such a new tool will take time.
- The Digital community, smart city, digital municipality do not exist in Hatay for now. Therefore digital e-Participation is under-estimated for the time being.

- For some departments (eg. parks and garden) STEP is a good tool, for others it need more time to understand and implement.
- It raised the awareness for a greener city
- The success depends on interdepartmental cooperation of Public Officers and decision implementation.
- This software must be more dynamic and interactive.
- Less One sided dialogues.
- The topics should be more general.
- To participate with Young People you need to think like a young person and attract their attention via methodologies such as gamification.
- Core Team understood during the Project that it takes time to engage all the youth of Hatay.

Future plans:

- Municipality planning to use the e-Participation again.
- We want to implement such an e-Participation for EXPO2021 HATAY.
- Not for only Young People, but for everybody to create local and relevant Big Data.
- Use as a tool for the smart city.

3.2.5 Association of Municipalities of Locride Area

The Locride area is one of the most peripheral and isolated territories of southern Italy and STEP represents the first case of promoting e-Participation for Young People. Before STEP, in the entire metropolitan city of Reggio Calabria, there has never been a project that promoted initiatives of e-Participation or e-democracy involving Young People. Now, thanks to STEP, hundreds of young people living in the Locride area can participate in public dialogues on environmental issues through the online platform and social media channel. STEP was an exciting challenge not only in terms of broadening the youth participation in decision making processes about environmental issues, but also for promoting innovative tools for e-Participation in a poorly developed region.

The SWOT analysis below presents the special characteristics for Locride’s pilot case.

Table 25 SWOT Analysis of Locride’s pilot

<p>Strengths</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Established collaboration with local schools • Experience in working with youth (creative activities - treasure hunt) • Political Endorsement (Deputy Mayor responded through the STEP Platform) • Strong local press coverage • Minimum bureaucracy (Administrator was responsible for content approval as well) • Fair understanding of the civic participation process 	<p>Weaknesses</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of experience in digital tools • Lack of short term implementation projects
<p>Opportunities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Existing legal framework • Establishing an e-participation process is a priority goal for the Area • Existing public participation processes (petitions) 	<p>Threats /Challenges</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Socio- economic Conditions of the local society • Provision of equal access to digital tools for everyone • Committed Political will • Create a unified civic e - participation strategy for all

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Established Youth Councils in 7 out of 42 Municipalities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> the 42 Municipalities Internal communication
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Strengths:

- The established collaboration with the local schools provided an easy and direct access to young people. More specifically, the STEP administrators were authorized to enter the classroom and have sufficient time to work together with the students during the school hours.
- The STEP administrative team was responsible for both creating the dialogue content and approving it, reducing significantly the required bureaucracy for publishing the dialogue.
- The STEP administrative team had a fair understanding of the participatory process and thus managed to achieve high level of participation by coordinating creative activities to spark the interest of young people and by partnering with the appropriate stakeholders.

Weaknesses:

- The targeted audience was not familiar with using a digital tool since the STEP platform was the first e-participation tool that was used by the Sant'Agata Municipality (Locride Area)
- Dialogues with short term implementable projects might have resulted in higher engagement of young citizens, since it could help the participants to comprehend the importance of participating and staying active in the dialogue.

Opportunities:

- Building upon the existing citizen petition process and the recent institutionalization of lowering the age limit to 16 years old for participating in the petition process, the STEP platform could potentially be the appropriate tool to empower further the already established Youth Councils to advocate for their priorities. A successful example of an active Youth Council is very likely to set the foundation for the establishment of similar Councils in the rest of the Municipalities in the Locride area.

Threats:

- The socio-economic conditions of the area limit the access of a broad audience to the use of digital tools. Citizens of lower income might not be able to own a smartphone or a computer, therefore, alternative options should be provisioned by the local authority ensuring equal access to the digital processes and digitally shared information for everyone.

In summary, the Locride pilot is considered to be a successful example for using the STEP platform, as not only they reached the anticipated young participants involved but they managed to create a major success story. Therefore, within the framework of STEP, the Municipality of Sant'Agata del Bianco actually changed its statute to recognize the possibility for Young People to submit e-petitions; the Municipality has officially lowered the age limit from 18 to 16 years old and additionally managed to simplify the e-petition process by reducing the number of signatures needed in order to submit a petition as a citizen. Moreover, the Locride pilot managed to influence the policy makers on a local transportation issue and raise awareness on important environmental issues.

The table below presents the dialogues of Locride's pilot.

Table 26 Locride Dialogues

Issue	Scenario	Type	Start	End	Questionnaire respondents	Total posts
Recycling in Locride area	Call for ideas and e-petitions	Public	2/02/2017	31/08/2017	-	24
New green areas in the Locride	Call for ideas and e-petitions	Public	23/03/2017	31/08/2017	-	24
Waste water treatment: Keep the sea clean in Locride Area	Call for ideas	Public	3/05/2017	31/08/2017	-	34
Separate collection of waste and recycling: no waste landfills	Call for ideas & E-petitions	Public	3/05/2017	31/08/2017	-	11
Road traffic in the city of Siderno	Call for ideas and e-petitions	Public	3/5/2017	21/01/2018	-	15
Promoting the use of spring water	Call for ideas and e-petitions	Public	23/06/2017	21/01/2018	-	14
Landfills and waste management in the Locride area	Call for ideas and e-petitions	Public	31/08/2017	21/01/2018	-	35
Urban park in Marina di Sant' Ilario dello Jonio	Call for ideas	Public	31/08/2017	21/01/2018	-	20

The Association of Municipalities of Locride Area has uploaded 7 dialogues in total on the STEP platform. All the dialogues are reported in the current deliverable. The table below presents the results of each dialogue.

Table 27 Results of Locride's Dialogues

Dialogue	Brief Description
Recycling in Locride area	Recycling is an important issue in Locride area due to the lack of a serious recycling plan. This dialogue was created to investigate citizens' approach, ideas and propositions on how to improve recycling in the area. Participants to the dialogue highlighted several aspects and shared interesting ideas in order to enhance the "recycling attitude" in Locride area. All interesting ideas and proposals gathered were evaluated and forwarded to the local decision makers. The end-purpose is to invite local decision-makers to place the proposals, which emerged in the dialogue, in the political agenda.
New green areas in the Locride	The city of Locri needs more green areas and a child-friendly approach of the city planning. This was exactly the base upon which this dialogue was created. Locri's young people participating in the platform promoted the idea to ask citizens to share their ideas and suggestions, starting from which places could be more suitable to build new public gardens. The ultimate goal of this dialogue was to collect ideas and suggestions from the youths and

	forward them to the Locri public administration to be included in the city planning.
Waste water treatment: Keep the sea clean in Locride Area	This dialogue was formatted to increase awareness and engage citizens for one of the most important environmental issues in Locride Area, and concerns the waste water treatment and the pollution of the sea. Pollution caused by the poor functioning of the plants on the waste water treatment situated on the coast and the fact that the little municipalities situated on interior of the Locride area (in the mountains and hills) discharge into rivers untreated waste waters. Consultation with citizens was very fruitful and an interesting solution proposed by the youth environmental associations was for the development of a constructed wetland (CW) of treating the municipal wastewater of the little communities. This new approach could be promoted throw a citizen’s debate in order to invite local decision-makers to put this new environmental approach in the political agenda. All interesting ideas and proposals gathered were evaluated and forwarded to the local decision makers. The end-purpose is to invite local decision-makers to place the proposals, which emerged in the dialogue, in the political agenda.
Separate collection of waste and recycling: no waste landfills	Calabria region approved in 2016 the “No landfills “plan to recycle all waste. Citizens need clear and detailed information about it and above all they need an efficient waste collection and management plan to be implemented from local administrations. Thus, the dialogue was created to involve and engage citizens while at the same time request their feedback, comments and suggestions. All feedback received will be dispatched to the local decision makers, highlighting the daily problems that citizens face with the collecting of waste.
Road traffic in the city of Siderno	This dialogue was formatted following the encouragement of a student’s group coming from the city of Siderno. The old highway 106 (the most important street in Locride area) is inadequate and causes often traffic congestion. It is necessary to redesign an alternative traffic plan for the city. Within this dialogue we ask the youth citizens to share ideas and proposals to improve the road network conditions. Following initial comments and feedback received, the Municipality of Siderno (a few days after the beginning of this dialogue) released a statement, announcing new solutions for improving the road conditions of the city. As a result, some youngsters criticized in their comments the functionality of the city bike lane and the bad attitude of some drivers. Given that this dialogue is very fruitful, the Locride team decided to keep the dialogue open and enhance the dialogue among the municipality and the young citizens in order to collaboratively improve any issues.
Promoting the use of spring water	Although our territory is rich in pure water springs, most of the people still buy bottled water, leading to negative consequences for the environment. The aforementioned statement was the initiative based upon this dialogue was formatted. Further given that the water springs of the region are rarely connected with an efficient water distribution network, it is necessary to raise awareness among decision-makers and people about the advantages of distributing and consuming mineral water from natural springs. The most interesting ideas and proposals will be collected and will be forwarded to the local decision makers. The purpose is to invite local decision-makers to place the proposals, which emerged in the dialogue, in the political agenda.
Landfills and waste management in the Locride area	This dialogue was created as a response to the young people and citizens of the Locri area, that call for a strategic change in the management of waste. A territory inundated with waste alongside the main roads and public

	<p>squares, cannot plan its future, especially for tourist development. At the same time, it needs to solve the problem of the many uncontaminated, disused and not secured landfills. The aim of this dialogue is to push decision-makers for a change in the waste management plan. Participation is so far high, mainly because the topic influences the daily life of all citizens in Locride area as well as because of the dialogue award, participation to the Step final event in Berlin's was an important incentive to reach more young participants.</p> <p>Several interesting ideas and suggestions were provided through posted comments, pictures, links about some recent situations in their cities concerning the waste collection etc. At this dialogue there was significant participation from youngsters who wanted to communicate their worries for the current environmental problems in their region and to share proposals in order to solve it. The feedback that will be received will be evaluated and then forwarded to the respective city department for further evaluation and actions. The ultimate purpose is to invite local decision-makers to place the proposals, which emerged in the dialogue, in the political agenda.</p>
<p>Urban park in Marina di Sant' Ilario dello Jonio</p>	<p>The Municipality of Sant' Ilario dello Jonio is planning to create an urban park. The Municipality shared information about the new project with the through the STEP platform and asked for citizens' suggestions and proposals. The dialogue was open to youngsters of Sant'Ilario but also to citizens living in other municipalities as well. They shared their experiences and proposals from similar projects in other cities of Locride Area. The dialogue is still open. The most interesting ideas and proposals will be gathered in order to prepare short reports (newsletters and press releases) for the local decision makers. The purpose is to invite local decision-makers to place the proposals, which emerged from the dialogue, in the political agenda.</p>

3.2.5.1 *The Association of Municipalities of Locride Area pilot plan*

There were not many deviations in the Association of Municipalities of Locride Area pilot plan. The gantt chart below presents the timeframe of the pilot plan.

Planned & Implemented dialogues

Table 28 Locride Planned & Implemented dialogues

	May-17	Jun-17	Jul-17	Aug-17	Sep-17	Oct-17	Nov-17	Dec-17	Jan-18
Separate collection of waste and recycling: no waste landfills	Planned	Planned	Planned	Planned	Planned				
New green areas in the Locride	Planned	Planned	Planned	Planned	Planned				
Promote the consumption of water coming from springs.		Planned	Planned	Planned	Planned	Actual	Actual	Actual	Actual
New project for Urban Green Park in Sant'Ilario dello Jonio.	Planned	Planned	Planned	Planned	Planned				
	Planned:		Actual:						

Inclusion

Informative meetings and activities in different municipalities, in public spaces, schools and universities were held for the inclusion of young citizens. Additional activities with info kiosks were organized in cooperation with peer youth leaders, who contacted various youth groups and invited them to participate in STEP dialogues.

Figure 17 Locride’s Landing Page

3.2.5.2 Successful dialogue of the Association of Municipalities of Locride Area Pilot & lessons learnt

The “Landfills and waste management in the Locride area” was the most successful dialogue in the Step Platform in terms of the quality of posts and interaction among users, since the young people of the Locri area and many more citizens call for a strategic change in the management of waste. The dialogue was successful because the topic influences the daily life of all citizens in Locride Area.

Success Story of the Pilot:

The most successful story of the Locride pilot was the change of the statute of the Municipality of Sant’Agata del Bianco, with reference to online petitions. Its goal was to extend and will facilitate the participation of Young People in decision making processes.

On 28th April 2017, the Municipality Assembly deliberated to reduce the number of signatures necessary to propose a petition, which can be presented also online. The minimum age for subscribing a petition was also lowered from 18 to 16 years old.

Future Use of STEP / advice to others:

The promotion of any kind of cooperation between Young People and policy makers through e-Participation is a big challenge today because of the lack of trust in politicians and politics by most Young People. In our

experience, to achieve e-Participation, it was important to involve the local youth leaders, and this is the approach taken to advance the platform and achieve greater levels of participation.

3.2.6 Resilient Thessaloniki

The Municipality of Thessaloniki is an additional pilot in the STEP project, not initially foreseen in the DoA. According to the deliverable D5.1: “Definition of STEP pilots and evaluation methodology”, the primary goal for the “Resilient Thessaloniki” pilot was to use the STEP platform during the early implementation phase of the city’s “Strategy for Urban Resilience -Thessaloniki 2030” aiming to introduce the concept of e-participation into the local decision making and provide the opportunity for young people to speak up for their priorities and aspirations. The goal was partially successful as the delivered outcomes of the two dialogues led to successful ideas implementation (quick wins), however, the impact was limited due to the lack of authority (political endorsement).

The table below presents a SWOT analysis of Thessaloniki’s pilot.

Table 29 SWOT Analysis of Thessaloniki’s pilot

<p>Strengths</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Appropriate projects / topics for public consultation ● Interdisciplinary portfolio ● Skilled Administration team 	<p>Weaknesses</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Lack of administrator’s authority ● Lack of city’s agenda for Youth ● Limited access to young audience ● Communication ● Conflict with similar digital platforms owned by the Municipality (all in pilot phases)
<p>Opportunities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Existing legal framework ● Existing vision for a stronger regional e-governance model, Promoting E-participation 	<p>Threats /Challenges</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Youth Engagement ● Political will ● Bureaucracy ● Internal communication

Strengths:

- Through the program “Resilient Thessaloniki”, the Municipality of Thessaloniki has been testing out new urban governance methods and piloting a variety of innovative urban projects. The majority of them were appropriate for public consultation. (i.e. the recently designed public space for co-creation policy).

Weaknesses:

- The Resilient Thessaloniki pilot was administered by the Resilient Thessaloniki team, which is a team of external partners of the Municipality. The lack of authority of the administrative team limited significantly the number of the published dialogues.
- Currently, the Municipality of Thessaloniki, has a variety of digital platforms with overlapping functions, such as public consultation features. Although, the Municipality has just recently released

the city’s digital strategy, it was still very confusing even to the civic employees which are the available tools that can be used for certain digital functions.

- The Municipality of Thessaloniki lacks of a structured Agenda for Youth. The portfolio for youth is fragmented between different Municipal Departments and responsibilities of more than 3 Deputy Mayors. Therefore, an established communication channel between the youth and the local administration does not exist and usually Departments refuse to lead Action Plans regarding responsibilities that are not entirely relied on them.

Opportunities:

- The pilot testing of the STEP platform within the frame of pilot public space projects showcased the added value of citizen participation in collaborating and decision making. Therefore, as soon as a specific Department is appointed to be responsible for the Youth Agenda, the Municipality team could co- design together with the Resilient Thessaloniki program a campaign that will encourage and empower young people to participate in public consultations.
- The existing national legal framework for civic participation in the local decision making alongside with the vision of the Resilient Thessaloniki Strategy (“Thessaloniki 2030”) for a more participatory governance model that fosters youth participation, are paving the path for tools like the STEP platform to be institutionalized and integrated to optimize and advance the existing civic procedures.

Threats:

- The political endorsement is a key element for impactful civic participation. It is crucial to have strong and committed political will that will eventually ensure immediate project implementation. Nowadays, due to the existing mistrust between authorities and citizens, initiating public dialogues with vague themes or timeframes will not only result low engagement but it is rather likely to broaden the communication gap even more.

Even though the Municipality initiated only two dialogues, they managed to attract the interest of 213 users in total, 126 of which estimated to be less than 30 years old. The tables below present the dialogues and the results derived from each one.

Table 30 Resilient Thessaloniki dialogues

Issue	Scenario	Type	Start	End	Questionnaire respondents	Total posts
Take action at your neighbourhood park. Voting for ideas.	e-petition	public	25/05/2017	31/08/2017	60	33
Community Gardens as a tool for strengthening the Urban Resilience	Call for ideas	Public	12/10/2017	12/12/2017	N/A	50

Table 31 Resilient Thessaloniki dialogue results

Dialogue	Brief Description
Take action at your neighborhood park. Voting for ideas.	The Municipality coordinated a pilot placemaking project aiming to reactivate a neighborhood park. The ideas posted on STEP were the outcome of participatory neighborhood workshops. The main goal of this dialogue was to open up this discussion to a broader audience by asking the citizens to vote the suggested concepts ideas of their preference. The number of the

	<p>respondents of the questionnaire was 60, while 30 posts were uploaded on the platform. The outcome of this dialogue was the selected idea-concept that was implemented at the neighborhood park. Resilient Thessaloniki announced the results to the participants through Social Media Posts, Press releases and interview at the local radio.</p>
<p>Community Gardens as a tool for strengthening the Urban Resilience</p>	<p>The subject was derived from the outcomes of the “Youth Resilience Challenge” Workshop, where young people shared their aspirations, ideas and concerns for Thessaloniki. Since Urban Farming was set as a priority during this workshop, the Municipality saw the opportunity to educate, train and engage the young people who were interested in the subject. We created this dialogue to be developed in two phases. The goal was to collect ideas and inquiries from the young people regarding urban gardening and community gardens in order to:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Phase 1: coordinate an onsite workshop/training seminar based on the inquiries/interests of the participants. The workshop took place at the 1st community garden of the city “kipos3” which is co- owned by the Municipality and the local residents. 2. Phase 2: Keep the discussion ongoing after the workshop, aiming to enable peer-to-peer exchange of knowledge and insights. <p>Participants feedback included several Inquiries regarding:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Plantation and Crop. - Potential challenges in developing a community garden (social, financial, environmental). - Ideas regarding additional programs/projects that could be organized and implemented within the frame of a community garden project. <p>Municipality’s short term plan is to keep this emerging e-community group active by coordinating meetings and training seminars as the Municipality is at the moment seeking funding for the construction of another two community gardens. The ambition is that this group that emerged from STEP will eventually become the ambassadors and initiators of the next community gardens.</p>

According to the initial plan, the Municipality of Thessaloniki aimed to use STEP as a tool for enabling structured dialogue between the local youth and the Municipality. The plan was to integrate the STEP platform to the ongoing Action Plan "Youth Resilience Challenge", in order to collect youth-driven data and insights through a service that corresponds to the current youth culture.

The City of Thessaloniki is collaborating with local youth organizations and initiatives to coordinate a year-long program regarding the youth inclusion in local decision-making processes. The main objective is to empower the youth to become ambassadors of urban resilience and ensure their meaningful contribution in the implementation of Thessaloniki’s Resilient Strategy. The program includes workshops and meetings with young people in the local and national level regarding a broad range of subjects regarding environmental, economic and social challenges.

While the Municipality has a specific partner for this Action Plan for communication, the youth organization "United Societies of Balkans", the absence of a specific Municipal Department that is responsible for Youth weakened their position in this partnership since for reaching out to the young people they were obliged to rely to this partner. This limitation resulted in very low engagement to the STEP Platform as the city didn't promote it.

Additionally, the citizens of Thessaloniki are not familiar with participation into the local decision making process in any format, not only digitally. Although, public deliberation is often requested as a requirement by law for the approval of certain decisions taken by the city's administration, the deliberation process is obsolete and elusive.

The first dialogue of Thessaloniki's pilot:

The next plan of the Municipality to use STEP was for a public space pilot project they coordinated aiming to empower the young people of the neighborhood to take action and activate the neighborhood's public spaces. In this context the Municipality uploaded the dialogue "Take action at your neighborhood park. Voting for ideas." The pilot project was coordinated in order to test the newly designed policy they have created within the Municipality that simplifies the permit process, which citizens need to apply for in order to use public spaces for the purpose of an event or a small scale intervention. There were two basic issues with this dialogue:

- Conflicts between various digital platforms the Municipality owns (none of them are in use, however, the Department of e-governance was confused)
- Limited access to the youth audience (communication boundary), Municipality's partner (Tópio) that was in charge of creating a communication channel between the Municipality and youth for this project, responded that the STEP application (mobile application) was complicated to use and too large for the mobile phone memory, so none of the students downloaded it on their phones.

However, the responders to the questionnaire (registration not needed) were 65. The outcome of this dialogue led to the planning of the next participatory workshop regarding the coordination of the public space pilot project.

Dialogues that weren't implemented:

Additionally, the Municipality was planning to initiate dialogues for raising awareness regarding environmental issues (ex. such as the use of plastic bags) but again due to the lack of a specific department responsible for Youth they didn't have political commitment. The Local administration (Deputy Mayors) were hesitant to endorse those dialogues, because they couldn't identify the owner of the dialogue (in an effort to avoid any misunderstanding that the Municipality is committed to execute the ideas/proposals posted on STEP platform by participants).

Future use of STEP:

Although, the pilot period of STEP platform is over, they Municipality is still interested in using the STEP tool and more specific a very special feature of STEP , the round table discussion. Following the Public Space pilot project ideas dialogue, now a month after the implementation of the pilot project, they are seeking ways to keep in touch with the participants of the pilot and also initiate a discussion for overcoming the challenges they faced while implementing the project and deciding on the next steps. They believe that the "Round Table feature" will be the perfect tool for this, since coordinating community meetings in a regular basis is not always successful due to everyone's busy daily schedule. Moreover, since this is an ongoing project with a small group of participants (8) that are already committed and genuinely interested in the progress of this discussion they anticipate high engagement.

Another potential upcoming dialogue for the Municipality of Thessaloniki is the one below: Citizen Consultation on the Thessaloniki's bike routes Plan conducted by the Department of Mobility, Municipality of Thessaloniki. The Municipality is still in discussions about this dialogue.

Figure 18 Screenshot showing posts to Thessaloniki Dialogue: Ideas for Urban Gardens (translated)

3.2.7 EU Pilot

One of the main goals of the STEP consortium was to fully exploit the platform and use it at Pan-European level, in the framework of a general European pilot test, which will invite young people to voice their opinions on general issues concerning the environment. The initial goal was to raise awareness on major environmental issues that are nowadays priorities of the Global Urban Agenda, such as climate change and air quality.

In this framework, DRAXIS and YEE set up the first EU dialogue, which went public in July 2017. The topic of the first EU dialogue was about the 17 Global Sustainable Development Goals (SDG's). Another two dialogues followed; EU pilot was actively supported by Epaminondas Christofilopoulos, member of STEP's Advisory Board. EU pilot managed to gather users from different European countries, such as Czech Republic, Germany, Spain, Greece, Italy, Australia, Belgium, Romania, Hungary, Albania, Slovakia, Switzerland, Ukraine, etc. EU pilot was promoted through online activities, such as facebook campaigns, social media, newsletters, etc, as well as offline, such as presentation at events, at meetings with organizations, etc.

The table below presents a SWOT analysis of EU's pilot.

Table 32 SWOT Analysis EU pilot

<p><u>Strengths</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Crosscountry dialogues • Excellent STEP platform Translation Feature • Inclusive audience 	<p><u>Weaknesses</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of administrator’s authority • Limited access to young people in different countries
<p><u>Opportunities</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • STEP can be used as a communication tool / e-forum between european youth organizations • STEP can be used as an awareness campaign tool 	<p><u>Threats /Challenges</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bureaucracy • Committed Partnerships

Strengths:

- Through the translation feature of the STEP platform, cross-country dialogues can emerge between not only European authorities and young citizens but among young people as well.

Weaknesses:

- In order to successfully engage young people from different countries and sustain this communication channel, it is important to establish local partnerships and ideally identify key people who can play the role of the liaison between the European organizations and local youth organizations.

Opportunities:

- The STEP platform can function as an e-forum where young people among different countries, with shared concerns and aspirations can discuss and ideally collaborate with each other.
- The STEP platform can be used also as a campaign tool for youth policy making organizations, providing them the opportunity to conduct short-term surveys in order to receive feedback when designing new policies.

Threats:

- The complex and lengthy bureaucratic procedures of the European Union might become a drawback for implementing ideas that have emerged from the STEP dialogues limiting the impact of the STEP Platform to simply exchanging knowledge among the participants.

In summary, the EU Step pilot can be considered as a successful first attempt to initiate crosscountry dialogues on important global challenges among European youth. Acknowledging the global impact of the environmental issues addressed on the STEP platform, such as the air quality and the climate change, the concept of the EU Pilot was to take the discussion from the local to the European level. Key element for this attempt was the STEP platform translation feature, which provided the opportunity to reach out to a broader and more inclusive audience by tackling the language barriers.

The tables below present the three dialogues of the EU pilot. Regardless the number of participants that were engaged in those dialogues, the fact that a multi-language dialogue on a common concern was initiated, is quite important for the STEP team.

Table 33 EU dialogues

Issue	Scenario	Type	Start	End	Questionnaire respondents	Total posts
17 Global Sustainable Development Goals. Which are more important to you?	Call for Ideas	Public	01/07/2017	31/08/2017	182	-
Tackling Climate Change	Call for Ideas	Public	01/09/2017	20/10/2017	108	-
Air Quality	Call for Ideas	Public	06/11/2017	31/12/2017 <i>Open Dialogue</i>	-	29

Table 34 Results of EU dialogues

Dialogue	Brief Description
17 Global Sustainable Development Goals. Which are more important to you?	<p>The dialogue was formatted to engage and increase Youths awareness of the 17 Global Sustainable goals. Participants were asked to select and prioritise the implementation of the goals based on their community and living area. Participation to the dialogue was significant and several interesting conclusions were made. Young people seem to be interested to share their opinions regarding the SDGs; however, some of them were not familiar with the 17 SDGs per se, but rather with the topics on which the goals are focusing. In this context, we believe that young people could and should have an important role in addressing the completion of the SDGs until 2030.</p> <p>The respective dialogue report results have been communicated widely through STEP and YEE social media and circulated to a number of selected stakeholders (EC, UN SG etc) as well as to the Network of Interest (NOI) members.</p> <p>(The dialogue report is available at the present deliverable Appendix D)</p>
Tackling Climate Change	<p>The dialogue was formatted to engage and increase Youths awareness of Climate Change as well as to obtain information about youths' perception of climate change and how they suggest that it can be tackled. Participation to the dialogue was high and several interesting conclusions were made. Young people seem to be interested to share their opinions regarding ways to efficiently tackle Climate Change. The majority of the youths identified Human activities as the main cause of Climate change and almost half of them are worried about the effects and implications of Climate Change in their everyday life. More than half of the Youth respondents consider that it is a bit late to totally reverse the effects of climate change, but our actions can assist to slow down the effects. More than half of the Youths consider that actions shall be coordinated and implemented mainly by the national governments. Most of the respondents try to reduce their activity effects by using public transport, by avoiding the use of plastic bags and plastic by-products etc. Youth respondents also highlighted the need for more dissemination and communication of the actual and practical results of Climate Change from Scientists and Environmental organizations. Scientists</p>

	<p>and Environmental are considered as trustworthy sources of information. The respective dialogue report results are currently analysed by the STEP team and will be communicated widely through STEP and partners social media and will be circulated to a number of selected stakeholders as well as to the NOI members.</p> <p>The dialogue report is available at the present deliverable Appendix D)</p>
<p>Air Quality</p>	<p>The dialogue was formatted to engage and increase Youths awareness on the topic of Air Quality, as well as to obtain information about youths’ perception on the topic and how they suggest that it shall be addressed.</p> <p>The dialogue contains an informative video about “Air Pollution” and Is posing four main questions to youths:</p> <p>How do you think air pollution affects us?</p> <p>How would you/do you help reducing air pollution in your community?</p> <p>Which small steps we could take towards cleaner air?</p> <p>Are you interested to help your city in air quality monitoring?</p> <p>The intention of the questions, is to enable youths to express their opinion and engage them in the dialogue.</p> <p>The dialogue is open until 31/12/2017.</p> <p>Following the dialogue completion, the STEP team will analyse the users posts and draft the respective dialogue report. The dialogue results will be communicated widely through STEP and partners social media and will be circulated to a number of selected stakeholders as well as to the NOI members.</p>

The “Air Quality dialogue” of the EU pilot dialogue, attracted significant attention from users originating in different countries. In contrast to previous dialogues (where all responses and language used in the posts was English) within the “Air Quality” dialogue a substantial number of users responded in their mother language (Spanish, Catalan Italian etc.). Attempting to “analyze” the user’s behavior we could conclude two points: a) the “translation” function within the Step platform is fully functional and assists users to engage and respond in their mother language and b) the “translation” function of STEP provides to dialogue administrators a wider base of users, since they are not required to restrict the dialogue language to English or to their mother language solely. By allowing users to express themselves in the language they feel comfortable, the STEP platform represents an even friendlier e-Participation platform. Furthermore, all participating users are enabled to understand fully the dialogue postings and interact indifferent of their language. We expect that the STEP “translation function” can be a valuable asset for cross-country dialogues, especially if we consider that the “environmental subjects” under discussion in STEP represent global challenges and require to be addressed with an equal global participation.

The two major challenges of this pilot were the access to young people in different countries and the commitment regarding the dialogue outcomes, since the administrators of STEP EU pilot were not european policy makers. However, the remarkable benefit of this pilot was that it showcases the need for a “common space”, an e-forum where young people among different countries, sharing same concerns and aspirations can discuss and ideally collaborate with each other.

3.3 Risk Management

The monitoring of the work progress was a key process for the successful implementation of the STEP project, since it kept the STEP team alerted and allowed tracing any risks, rescheduling and planning additional future activities. DRAXIS was responsible for the monitoring of the STEP pilots. A comprehensive plan was created for the monitoring of the pilots. In order to ensure the timely and smooth implementation of the pilot operation DRAXIS team was in close communication with all the pilot partners via emails, while online meetings were taking place every month, or every week when it was needed. The number of the online meetings was defined by the needs and the riskiness of each pilot. During the calls DRAXIS was monitoring the performance and the progress of each pilot, discussed the monthly action plan with each pilot partner, discussed any problems encountered, etc. The table below presents the risks that occurred during the pilot phase and the measures taken by the STEP team.

Table 35 Risk Monitoring

Risks	Measures
A key staff member of Valdemoro Municipality team became seriously ill part-way through the project, so the human resources reduced in Valdemoro's STEP team	DRAXIS was informed about the issue and sent an official letter to the Mayor. Unfortunately, there was not a replacement with new personel, however, the work foreseen was carried out by the existing members of the team.
RoC's, Valdemoro's and Locride's pilots were in risk of not reaching one of the success indicators: Number of young people involved in the pilot	Once DRAXIS recognized the problem, official letters were sent to the pilot administrators in order to stress the risk and ask them to deploy a new strategy, intensify the dissemination activities and the promotion of the STEP platform. Additionally, DRAXIS arranged for weekly calls with each pilot administrator separately in order to monitor the progress and further support the pilots. DRAXIS team also traveled to Crete in order to meet the STEP team of RoC, discuss the problem and come up with an updated strategy. It should be noted that RoC contracted two external experts to support the team with the implementation of the pilot.
The public authorities did not fully grasp the functionality of the STEP platform	Apart from the initially planned workshops, additional webinars took place, while a 2 days training workshop dedicated to the pilot partners was organized in Mollet del Valles. During the workshop, the technical team had a training session with each pilot separately.
The Mayor was unexpectedly changed in the Municipality of Valemoro during the implementation of the open pilot	The STEP team was informed about the incident and sent an official letter to the new Mayor in order to inform him about the STEP project and to stress that additional support is needed for the successful implementation of the pilot.
The Catalan independence referendum that was held on the 1 st of October 2017 in the Spanish autonomous community of Catalonia	The pilot administrator informed DRAXIS team about the situation in Catalonia from the very beginning. DRAXIS team was kept updated on the topic. Pilot activities continued as planned, although their impact during the period of political tension was limited.

4 Interview Results

After having seen a number of issues associated with the piloting activities, in the following sections we present the results of qualitative interviews conducted for the evaluation of the STEP platform. We have also included in this section any relevant free text answers given in response to the survey. We start by presenting the Public Officers/Policy Makers interviews and then follow with the Young People interviews. These interviews have given a number of relevant insights on what has worked well and less well in the piloting and offer a deep overview of the perspective of relevant actors who took part to the e-Participation process.

4.1 Policy Makers / Public Officers

Here we highlight some of the main issues that arose in the interviews with Policy Makers / Public Officers by theme. We will also connect these results to the results of the questionnaires where applicable, in order to offer greater clarity on the evaluation aspects of the project.

The Usefulness of the Platform for e-Participation

The Public Officers/Policy Makers who we spoke to about STEP all agreed that despite a few minor issues the platform was valuable and useful for them to gather the opinions of Young People on environmental issues. Public Officers mentioned that the scope of their work had been increased since using the platform and that it had been very beneficial in being able to bring together more isolated regions where perhaps little attention had been paid previously:

“The contribution STEP has made to our municipality – the tool has helped us to widen our scope. Before STEP we were much more concrete, for example we used to have a focus on the municipality budget, but that was it. Now we have shared several dialogues with absolutely different topics, and this is quite new for us. It has given us more participants, and a much wider focus.” MDV PO¹⁵

“Each municipality should have this kind of tool.” MDV PO

The main difficulty in effectively using STEP had been to inform and attract users to the platform and in the amount of time and effort involved in keeping the platform vibrant with new content so that users would want to return to it and further engage with the content. Public Officers said that more people were needed to ensure this happened:

“Platform is really useful but the key thing is that we need more than one person to control it effectively. Main difficulty is in keeping it going.” Hatay PO

“One of the ways to solve local problems is to participate with other towns, but it had never happened before in Calabria. STEP has been very, very positive in this respect. Without the platform it would have been impossible to speak to those in more remote regions.” Locride PM¹⁶

“The STEP Platform is putting more focus on these more remote areas, areas where perhaps people are less aware of the importance of the environment.” Locride PM

¹⁵ PO – Public Officer

¹⁶ PM – Policy Maker

The interviewees mentioned that the platform was helping them to be more aligned with the expectations of Young People with regards to how they communicate, and that this made them seem both more modern and more approachable. Being able to use the Social Media Mining Tool (SMMT) to track the reaction of citizens to specific campaigns was also mentioned as being useful by ROC POs:

“The platform will be a modernization of the local administration in the Young People’s eyes. The dialogue they can now have with us is the same type of communication they have with pop groups, football clubs, their friends etc. It’s one more channel that they have in their lives.” MDV PO

“The only way to inform people previously was via tv or newspapers. A few seconds perhaps, or short paragraph. Now we don’t need to depend only on these channels”. Locride PM.

“Useful? Absolutely – it was not possible to do these 15 events previously. Every time we used the STEP platform, then Young People had the opportunity to find out about the project”. Locride PM.

“I Used the SMMT when I had to present STEP in a national conference. I logged in as administrator, and was able to present information about how people reacted to the material we had published.” ROC PO

One PO from Hatay shared how he thought the platform could be utilised for education and learning about green issues from other countries. He strongly believed that the platform should offer greater opportunities for learning. He also wanted to make more use of the leaderboard and gamification aspects to assign greater admin rights to those Young People who were acting in a leadership capacity on the STEP platform, allowing them to be able to open their own dialogue once a certain level is reached:

“For example, let’s say I’m a volunteer for greening the city, please give me the 10 best practices, 10 cities in the world that have done this, give me an example, where the Young People have done green actions, what have they done? Why they have done it? I want to know how they have done it in Chicago, London, why they have done it. What do they have to do, they don’t know. We must teach the guys what they have to look for. Where are the fish, are they hunting in the right place. Steer them in the right way.” Hatay PO

“It must be more dynamic, the users must control the platform as well. We must give some awards to the influencers, and to the experts - so they can open a dialogue or something” Hatay PO

Usability / Issues with the platform

Interviews with the Public Officers indicated that there did not appear to be any major usability issues with the platform. Most said that they had no difficulty in using the platform. Overall, the general opinion was that the platform worked well and was relatively easy to use. The operating speed of the platform was however, reported as being an issue (especially in Hatay):

“I am ok with the platform. Not so much usability problems. The main issue was that it’s really slow. Sometimes I have to wait too long for it to load. The App is generally faster than the website” Hatay PO

“I used both ways (app & web). Admin site for the website was easier.” Hatay PO

“I didn’t need to watch the (help) videos. I Didn’t need to seek support. Biggest problem was to recruit the users.” ROC PO

“Speed. Everything seems OK, but it should work faster.” Hatay PO

“Must be able to enter the site more easily” Hatay PO

One PO from Crete mentioned that the interface changed over the course of the Pilot, resulting in a **lack of consistency**, which caused her some confusion:

“Every time I open the application I find a new screen, I couldn’t find the things I needed easily. STEP was changing a lot.” ROC PO

The PO from Hatay mentioned in the free text options for the Survey that it would be useful to be able to associate various media in the voting process and also a preference for having the comments visible before voting rather than after.

“It would be nice if you can associate a document, video or image in voting processes with options in each option.”

“Possibility of comments being visible before voting processes and not when you just voted.” Hatay PO

Increasing Trust between Young People and Policy Makers

After interviewing a number of Policy Makers from the different Pilot regions, it was apparent that **Trust was not something that could be built quickly**, although the STEP platform was a step in the right direction, **more actions** would need to be made (and Young People would need to see these actions being made) before Trust would increase to any degree.

“To speak about increasing trust – it’s really too early. The platform can help us ease communication between the administration and the Young People, it will probably take a lot of time to build trust though.” MDV PO

“Does it help relations to grow? Because they are so young they have problems to see the usefulness of the administration. It’s not that they think it’s absolutely useless, but I mean they don’t see the relevance. It comes with age.” MDV PO

Most POs/PMs shared the opinion that the platform had **helped them to communicate more effectively** with Young People, and that as a result of this they became **more approachable**.

“Not that sure that any increase in trust yet between YP & politicians has been achieved. However, they trust these new issues more than have been put in front of them.” Locride PM.

“Definitely, before they didn’t trust politicians or politics at all. Politicians were also happy to have youngsters excluded. Before STEP, the mayor was seen as very far away from youngsters – now thanks to the platform and his interest in environmental issues, they have approached him.” Locride PM.

“Trust – yes I think STEP is helping. The Young People are very happy that they have been asked their opinion. The fact that it is open and transparent is good. Needs time and some examples of success. It will probably take a bit of time” Hatay PO

“STEP makes us seem more approachable. They will know that they are heard and that their opinion is valuable.” ROC PO

Engaging Young People / Maintaining Interest

All of the Pilots involved in STEP expressed how much time and effort needed to be put in to engage Young People with the dialogues and the STEP platform. In the early phase, a lot of time and effort is required to promote STEP to the relevant demographic. Having the platform targeted at 16-29 year olds also proved to add to the difficulties in promoting the platform to Young People. The general opinion of all the Pilot partners was that younger school age children (around 13-16yrs) are often more receptive to new ideas, such as the STEP platform, and that a lot of outreach in promoting the platform could have been achieved with the support of the local schools if this age group was included:

“It’s difficult that we can only promote to over 16’s – this restricts us. We promoted via Universities”
Hatay PO

Having enough staff to spend time on the platform and to engage with the dialogues was also important, the time and energy needed was considerable. Having new content to encourage return visits was mentioned by several PO’s and the fact that other sites are (such as Twitter and Facebook) are much more familiar to them:

“Main difficulty is to get them engaged. We now have more than 2800 users – but to engage them to use it is difficult. We need to have more than one person working on this, our social media team, is more than 6 people who work for the municipality, and you also need a lot of volunteers to actually help run the platform well” Hatay PO.

“We need to put in a lot of effort in to keep the Young People involved in the platform and to keep them interested. You have to add something every day, to have new content in the dialogue.” Hatay PO

“I think it is because Twitter and Facebook are much more familiar (describing earlier, low participation rates).” ROC PO

The dialogue topic is of crucial importance. As reported in the Youth Engagement deliverables (D 4.1 & 4.2) the topic should be of relevance to the lives of Young People. Participation rates varied widely between the different dialogues, both between the different pilots and within individual pilots, suggesting other forces than purely demographic ones were important. ROC released a lot of technical Environmental Impact Assessments (EIAs), which received little participation, the interviews held revealed that these highly technical documents were not very accessible to Young People (they were supplied to download as PDF files and contained very technical language), Young People felt that they were not relevant to them:

“They (YP¹⁷) are more interested in the issues put on debate than on the EIA they are technical things, containing terms that most YP do not understand, it’s hard for them to express an opinion. They are more interested in things about everyday stuff, things that they can do themselves ” ROC PO

“I think that the YP who find it most useful and interesting are those with an environmental background. Hard to get the others interested” ROC PO

“I think overall then the dialogues that we ran were mostly the right ones, if you want to test something then you have to do as many different dialogues as you can. I think maybe with a much bigger city everything would be different. The bigger the city the easier it should be.” MDV PO

In many instances, Pilots had resorted to using prizes as incentives for Young People to engage with the platform. The success of this strategy has been very mixed though, it helped in some Pilots, but for MdV in particular, the prize of a trip did not have a positive effect on numbers of people engaging in the dialogue:

¹⁷ YP – Young People

“The trip to Berlin didn’t make a change it was less than 10 people participating, it was a disaster. We had communication tools, everything, and still only 10 people. They were not interested. There were like around 5000/6000 summer city programmes that we printed with the information of the whole of the summer city festival but also with a dialogue with these huge banners and we printed the debate and through all the media, Facebook. It’s like ‘if the topic is not relevant they are not going to participate’.” MDV PO

“We learned that people participate more when they think that their contribution will have a direct impact. Our other dialogues had 50, 60, 80, 10, 12,9 participants and then suddenly 1000. It’s because it (regeneration dialogue) really had an impact on their everyday life, in their everyday public space. MDV PO

Celebrity Endorsements

Having a celebrity, or at least someone recognisable to Young People use the STEP platform may have been helpful in attracting them to use the platform (considered by the pilots to be the most difficult issue to tackle). The Young People we interviewed agreed with this, and some suggestions are provided under the relevant section of the Young People interviews (section 4.2.1.3).

“Maybe we need to have someone famous (or minor celebrities). Just someone that they recognize. For example Anna Simon (a journalist on Spanish TV). Might be better to pay them to participate, rather than spend the money on banners. It needs to be someone on the TV that they can recognize – doesn’t matter if they are knowledgeable about the environment. Maybe if she had said something we would have had thousands of participants.” MDV PO.

4.1.1 Key Points Young European Citizen Interviews

In what follows we present some key aspects of the interviews conducted with Young People in the STEP pilots. Like before, the interviews give in-depth insights in what has worked well and less well during the piloting activities. We have also included in this section any free text answers given in response to the survey, as these are qualitative results and fit better with this discussion.

4.1.1.1 The concept of STEP – Young People engaging in e-Participation

From the interviews it was apparent that overall, the Young People really appreciated the concept of the STEP e-Participation platform. One young person from the ROC eloquently expressed how the platform was likely to increase her engagement with environmental policy making:

“If you suggested to me that tonight, I should go to an exhibition about climate change I wouldn’t go, I prefer to stay on my couch, but if I have an application about e-Participation, where I can just type my opinion, and I can interact with others and from other regions then this is appealing.” ROC YP¹⁸

One young Spanish person mentioned that the platform was a great idea as politicians would be better able to see what Young People (who are the future) think and need:

¹⁸ YP – Young Person/Young People

“I really liked the idea of a platform dedicated to Young People and the idea of relating Young People with the politicians, and them seeing what we think and what we think we need, because we are like the future you know. So it was a great idea.” Valdemoro YP

Young People mentioned that having the STEP platform made things much more convenient if they wanted to share their opinions on environmental issues, both with other Young People and with Policy Makers at the regional / municipality level. Not having to physically be at a certain place and being able to use the tool in their own time made participation more appealing:

“The best thing is to be able to easily share our opinion.” Locride YP

“I think STEP will help, because although obviously we can go to the door (Town Hall) and say ‘listen to me’ the fact is no-one will, and the platform is going to help us in this way, so I think it is good. Also everyone nowadays is on social media.” Valdemoro YP

“I participated in the dialogue about economical / social aspects. If more people are informed & engaged in environmental issues, then all ages of people from young to old become educated. I believe that the application is really very effective.” ROC YP

“For people not already interested, it will make them more conscious about the environment” Hatay YP

“The STEP Platform is helping because it (environmental knowledge) gets into the citizens and they teach it to the little kids and when they grow up, then they are gonna be aware about it.” Valdemoro YP

The free text answers given in response to the further comments on using STEP also gave an indication that the concept of STEP and e-Participation was appreciated, the following comments were given by Young People :

“I hope this project will spread throughout the country and that the dialogues will be active.” Hatay YP

“In terms of environment then Young People had a great influence in having a say, thanks to everyone.” Hatay YP

“STEP Platform is giving more importance to Young People’s ideas” Hatay YP

“It is undoubtedly an innovative application that, if widely used by the public, will help to raise awareness of environmental issues, while addressing some of the current problems.” ROC YP

“My experience has been good at finding out about environmental information” Valdemoro YP

“It is a useful application and I think it must continue to exist and contribute in its own way” ROC YP

4.1.1.2 Young People being considered by Regional Government

During the interviews, YP were asked if, prior to STEP, that the opinions of YP had ever been considered where they lived. They also discussed in their opinion, if and how STEP had contributed to this process.

“Difficult to say – there was not much effort previously, specifically on environmental issues, they deal with Young People just as a group, and not with specific issues. It’s not common for Young People to

be considered other than maybe Young People and employment, but not for the environment.” MDV YP

“They tend to lump everything together for ‘Young People’. They do make some effort, but not on specific things.” ROC YP

“I find it very interesting that the Municipality is trying to manage this platform and that it is something that belongs to the city of MDV and I think that by participating actively I will now spread the tool amongst other citizens and make it known.” MDV YP

“I'm happy to be able to give my idea and know that someone with a charge of power and influence is going to read it.” Free text Survey Response, Valdemoro YP

4.2 Usability and Issues with the platform

Most Young People interviewed found the website easy to use, but some fine-tuning of the usability is still needed to increase the overall capacity of STEP. There were some comments stating that perhaps the purpose of the platform could be more obvious from the initial interaction with the first pages, but overall it was usable. Some Young People commented that it was not simple enough, comparing the usability to Apps such as Instagram (needing just one click). Comments provided in the survey responses mentioned that the interface had become more user-friendly over time.

“The Interface seems to be changing, making it simpler and more user-friendly” ROC YP

Getting Started

The majority of usability issues seemed to relate to early interactions with STEP, Young People did not like having to provide a lot of information to register on the platform, and actually finding the STEP website or App and getting registered on the platform was problematic. The password recovery process was mentioned as being a barrier to using the platform, in the free text options of the survey.

“At the beginning, I felt that the platform was asking for too much information – too quickly.” ROC YP

“Found some things that didn't go so well - eg. how to register a new user. Resolved this, but we had to close the page and reload to do it.” Locride YP.

“Posts – I uploaded a photo. This was OK, posting text also worked well. However, I couldn't understand how to comment with the photo or video. It's not that clear.” Locride YP

“I thinks that it is a very easy platform, that it is easy to use it” MDV YP

“Functionality was good, just the interface was a bit confusing” Locride YP

“It's a bit confusing - I use instagram a lot and it's super simple. STEP is more confusing. I get a bit lost to be honest - I gave up. Instagram is one click and you see it. You have a lot of clicks on the STEP platform” Valdemoro YP

“The use will be increased if the site is made easier to use” Free text survey response

Searching for STEP

Several Young People mentioned the difficulty that they had in finding out the details of the website and STEP platform form by searching on Google. There are so many other ‘STEP’ sites and this makes it difficult, people described how they moved the search to STEP EU to find the website. This issue had been identified in the intermediate evaluation process, although it was difficult to easily rectify. Having a more meaningful and less commonly used name would have helped, but as the project had begun to use the name and web links, it would have been difficult to change it without causing further confusion:

“I Googled STEP, but it was very difficult to find – there are a thousand other things, I then Googled Step EU, I found it eventually, but couldn’t to begin with. I found the website through the STEP EU link, but then I couldn’t find the Crete website, I had to go back to the regional website and find it. I’m not expecting for it to be the first thing to come up when I Google STEP, but I think it’s a bit of a problem that it is so difficult. If you try to go another way, i.e. other than using the direct link, then it’s a problem.” ROC YP

“Takes a lot of time to learn to use it. It’s a bit confusing. Have to learn how to use it. Computer version was better than the app. Too much info on the screen.” Locride YP

Sharing Issues

Some Young People reported during the interview that they had encountered problems with sharing material from STEP via their social media accounts:

“I shared my idea on STEP and then I shared this on my FB wall – but it was not showing my whole idea, not my whole comment. I strongly believe that these technical problems are not the thing that stops people getting involved though.” ROC YP

“Generally it worked well – but I had some issues about sharing, I could share, but on Facebook wall my friends couldn’t see the content I shared.” Locride YP

Interacting with other posts

Some Young People mentioned that adding a comment to an existing post was more confusing than adding a new post. An interesting comment was made by a young person from the ROC, she explained the observation that little interaction was taking place between the Young People on specific posts, stating that the **younger generation are happy to share their ideas**, but when it comes to creating a dialogue with others they are more reluctant:

“I was talking alone, I didn’t see any other messages, I added 2 specific ideas to the dialogue but I didn’t see any reaction.” ROC YP

*“I saw one or two people adding comments, but we didn’t communicate. I think the young generation are happy to express our opinions, but not so good at creating a dialogue. Maybe it’s our ego. I think we need more questions posted, **we are not good at developing this dialogue with others** – but better at posting ideas.”* ROC YP

Others comments suggested that this low response to other posts may be due to more technical or usability issues, rather than the shyness of Young People to speak with each other:

“I noticed you could do it (leave comments on other posts), but it was a little bit confusing. Easier to write directly a new comment than to comment on the existing post.” Locride YP

Speed and lack of user feedback

The speed of the platform was reported to be too slow, this was mentioned by Young People in Hatay and MdV. Not having sufficient user feedback whilst uploading images was mentioned to be problematic, sometimes resulting in the user uploading the image more than once:

“The platform loads too slowly - of course, people lose interest” Hatay YP

“When I uploaded the picture and wrote the message, I could not see that this was uploaded, so I had to wait a little bit, so I ended up uploading it several times because I wasn’t sure whether the picture was uploaded or not. Maybe faster feedback like ‘thanks your photo has been uploaded’.” MDV YP

Attractiveness of the Platform

There was a mixed reaction to the attractiveness of the platform from the Young People we interviewed, it varied by region with Young People in Spain and Greece rating it mostly positively and Italy and Turkey being more critical. Some Young People liked it a lot commenting positively on the interface, others remarked it was ‘old fashioned’ or that there was too much information on the screen.

“I really like the Interface and I really liked the Design of the platform. Of course in Greece, unfortunately, for most public websites, there is not much effort into making sure they are pretty.” ROC YP

“The platform is very well set up, the graphics are very modern and the interface is nice, but it could maybe be a little clearer in the beginning regarding the purpose.” ROC YP

“In my opinion - the platform was not that attractive, it has an older user interface. I think that that there were too many things together on the platform. It’s easy to get confused.” Locride YP

“Worst thing is the interface” Locride YP

“It’s not attractive enough to attract as many people as we would like” Hatay YP

“Nothing else to add I liked it a lot, it is intuitive and I would like my opinion to be useful and to improve this situation” Valdemoro YP (free text survey response)

4.2.1.1 Importance of the Dialogue Topic

From the interviews, and when considering the usage data of the platform across the various dialogues released by the Pilots it is very clear that the Dialogue topic is of major importance in engaging Young People to contribute to the e-Participation process. The topics chosen were wide ranging, but the Young People interviewed gave some indication of why some proved to be much more popular than others.

Young People mentioned that they **should have some knowledge** about the topic being discussed. Having the dialogue about a topic that is already quite controversial (such as Wind Farms) was also suggested as a way to increase participation:

“So the dialogues about Climate Change and Water Management in Crete, or the Caretta Caretta, these are things that people know about and can form an opinion about and express it. There is a lot more chance that they will express their opinion ” ROC YP

“I think the EIA’s were very local, all the environmental perceptions are more limited about projects which are quite local and it’s maybe better if there would be something else to have a discussion about..” ROC YP

Young People also mentioned that the topic had to appeal to them and not be too technical:

“I participated in the dialogue on Climate Change. The thing about the EIA, it’s not very appealing. It sounds very technical, the people who would be willing to engage would only be the people who may be directly affected, the response would not be very positive. Most EAI’s are very local” ROC YP.

“There was actually a huge discussion in Crete the last year about wind farms. There were quite a few protests about it and I think that is something that became a political issue, so that would be something that most people would participate in. “ ROC YP.

“When it comes to EIAs, for example, the one about the hotel being built, well, people think ‘OK - It’s not my job to know about this’ “ ROC YP.

“On being asked if the dialogues in Valdemoro were relevant to Young People: “I’m not sure to be honest, because sometimes I read some of them and was like ‘ok that’s kind of like not calling me to participate’ it didn’t grab my attention enough you know, I was like OK.” Valdemoro YP

Young People told us that the topic issue is easier to discuss if it is about something tangible:

“When you transform the issue into something tangible, then it’s easier to talk about it. So for example Water Management is easier to discuss than CO2 emissions and global warming. “ ROC YP

4.2.1.2 Framing the Dialogue to resonate more with Young People

An interesting interview took place with one Greek young person who was interested in politics and international policy-making. He commented on how simply re-framing a question can have a significant impact on how people become engaged with an issue.

“I saw an interesting discussion on how they successfully shifted the debate in the US on gay marriages from no to yes. Originally they were framing this on equal rights, so the basic argument from the pro side was ‘people deserve equal rights’ and it was like everyone was like yes but it didn’t really work out. And then, they shifted the narrative towards love and how ‘we all have the right to love whomever we choose’. That resonated much more with people in a sentimental way because you have the right to marry and to love whomever you like. And it actually helps with the debate.” ROC YP

Framing the dialogues in a way to really engage Young People is very important, but it will be a skill that each Pilot has to develop over time and is likely to be very contextual to each region. We offer some guidance in section 4 of our WP5 document *A Roadmap for the delivery of e-Participation: lessons learned from the STEP project*.

4.2.1.3 *Problems of catching YP's attention and maintaining interest*

The issue of Youth Engagement is of major importance to the success of the STEP platform. In addition to making the Dialogues relevant to Young People, the project has understood the need to **lower the barriers to e-Participation**, making it as quick and easy as possible and to allow Young People to interact with the platform while they are available (making the phone app appealing). The interview responses from the Young People involved in the Pilot's highlights some of the difficulties with gaining the (often already overloaded) attention of Young People and of maintaining interest over a sustained period. Young People mentioned that their attitude was sometimes not at all focused on environmental issues, and that they just wanted to be young and carefree:

"Sometimes, the Young People are like, 'I'm young and I don't care about what is happening, I'm gonna just live the crazy life!' you know and I feel it (STEP) will help us to know a little more about what is happening here." MDV YP

"Sometimes the attitude is - I'm young – I don't care what's happening." Valdemoro YP

Some Young People stated that participation should begin via schools, thus capturing interest at a younger age and in an environment where participation could be supported by the relevant environmental education. The overwhelming amount of information available to Young People means that they tend to move onto the next topic very quickly:

"Engagement with the environment should start young, the whole participation should be part of the course at the school (not so voluntary). There is too much information, always the next thing and the next thing, so people don't focus on the topic. They move onto the next thing." ROC YP

Several Young People mentioned the issue of gaining visibility for the platform and having an active community participating and making new posts to the platform, not having a large or active community meant that they had little reason to go back and visit the platform.

"It's difficult to maintain this enthusiasm, people come and then lose interest and move away. I put comments and then I didn't see any more posts - so I stopped looking." ROC YP

"In this city we couldn't attract enough people – the platform was not active enough. We found it was not enough to keep people interested. We were keen to attract more people" Hatay YP (Environmental Activists)

"Something to look at everyday would help – plus the topic should be more personal. Maybe not always my interest, if it was more personalised, not by region, but by way of approach." ROC YP

Celebrity endorsements and influencers

Having 'influencers' or local celebrities using the platform was discussed with some of the Young People we interviewed, their opinion was that this would help a lot – especially in attracting people to the platform in the first instance:

"Of course this would help. If it's a perfume and a celebrity uses it then Young People will use it. It would be the same for this platform. Even representatives from institutions. If an artist makes a post on social media then it would attract all their followers. Need someone with a lot of followers, my suggestion is to have a 'celebrity' for each target group (eg University professor for University students) a political person and environmental associations. Need to define the target groups and

then for each target group, you need a representative that will bring their own target group / followers. And this would be needed for each region. “ ROC YP

4.2.1.4 *Building Trust & Seeing Positive Actions resulting from the Dialogues*

Young People were of the opinion that although they appreciated being asked their opinion, **more feedback and actions from the Dialogues was needed**. Some also mentioned that they would have liked more interaction between the Pilots to encourage learning from others in different areas. Young People said it is better to have clear outcomes presented, enabling them to know what would happen after the dialogue ends otherwise they are not keen to participate. They would have liked to have been invited to participate in further face-to-face interactions with the policy makers after the online dialogue had ended:

“So when you have just an open discussion, with no real goal, without stating what’s going to come after, then what’s going to come out of this, it doesn’t motivate people. That’s the problem.” ROC YP

“No I don’t think there has been enough feedback actually. But that’s the thing, wouldn’t it be better if you had all the dialogues and then at some point you really have a feedback and you organise a meeting with the people that participated and they discuss live those things.” ROC YP

“I think it was like, ok they (municipality) are trying to help.” Valdemoro YP

“So I really liked this (STEP) - I do wish that there was more interaction between the pilots though, I think that this is very important. We can learn from the experiences of each other.” ROC YP

“Would have liked more information about what was happening in the other pilot areas” Locride YP

*“It would be nice to create your own group, that is to say, with related contacts to learn more about those new projects.”*MDV YP - Free text survey response

4.2.1.5 *Gamification Aspects*

We asked Young People what their opinion was on the gamification aspects of the STEP platform. Some admitted to not noticing features such as the leaderboard, whereas others thought that the features would encourage engagement with the platform. There were some comments on not knowing how the points were assigned which they would have preferred to know more about, this uncertainty tended to decrease their liking of these features.

“I saw the leaderboard – but didn’t know how it worked. Didn’t like the leaderboard – because it was not understandable, it frustrated me a lot to be honest” Valdemoro YP

“Leaderboard – could be useful but the notification system was a bit confused. Couldn’t understand the notification system” Valdemoro YP

“Leaderboard; We noticed the points. Can be Useful – encourages people to post more, Clear how it worked? It’s clear but too slow.” Hatay YP

5 Evaluation Questionnaires

As discussed in particular in D5.1, one of the core instruments for the evaluation of STEP has been an online questionnaire. The methodology and the rationale behind the conduction of the questionnaire have been described elsewhere, including the aforementioned deliverable and these aspects will not be repeated here. This section of the deliverable indeed focuses entirely on the presentation of the core results of the questionnaire. As anticipated in D5.1, two questionnaires were prepared for the STEP evaluation:

- A Public Officers Questionnaire (POQ)
- A Young People Questionnaire (YPQ)

Both questionnaires have been released and completed during the month of October 2017 in the respective national languages to the 6 pilots, in the final phase of the project. The data has subsequently been cleaned and it has been analysed with custom written python scripts. We will present the results of each questionnaire in turn, starting from the Public Officer Questionnaire.

A further consideration is required before discussing the analysis. The Objectives table of the project (which can be seen in the project proposal as well as in D5.1) reported various targets (i.e. 60%, 70%) including often targets of 100%. This last, is a figure which in itself is unlikely to be achievable through questionnaires, where indeed even a small number of negative responses can be expected. Therefore, the targets of 100% have to be considered as whole, where other measures of impact will need to be included, as available and discussed in other deliverables, but also in the qualitative section of this deliverable where analysis of in-depth interviews with core stakeholders in the pilots are presented. Responses to the questionnaires show however STEP achieving often **nearly 70% or above positive responses**, and in any case consistently above 60%, thus, bringing overall a very positive picture in relation to the evaluation as captured by the questionnaire. We will signal in the presentation of data (yellow cells in tables) when an indicator falls significantly below the 60% threshold for a 100% target, or anyway when an indicator is distant from the target. We will also signal (green cell in tables) when an indicator is well above the target. In what follows we will report the targets as presented in the Objective table and where reasonable we discuss how close STEP has been in achieving the figure.

5.1 Public Officers Questionnaire

From the POQ we have gathered 19 responses across all the pilots. It was expected that the POQ would not result in large number of responses and that would not allow much comparison across pilots. Therefore the data from all POQs have been merged in a unique dataset from which an analysis has then been conducted. The POQ also resulted in a minimal amount of missing data and particularly the question number 4 (associated with the device used during STEP) was affected in a couple of pilots. In this case we used the neutral answer (used devices on equal amount) to build for the missing data in order to maintain the structure of the dataset across the pilot responses. The question 13e was missing in one of the questionnaires (probably due to the process of translating from English to National language), also in this case the answer has been set as the neutral answer, again with the goal to keep intact the structure of data. What follows are frequency tables which show more details about the measured demographics aspects of the POQ.

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Table 36 POQ Gender Demographics

Gender	Frequency	%
Male	11	58
Female	8	42
Tot.	19	100

Table 37 POQ Position Demographics

Position	Frequency	%
Elected Politician	2	11
Local Government Worker	12	63
Other	5	26
Tot.	19	100

Table 38 POQ Age Demographics

Age	Frequency	%
25-24	4	21
35-44	11	58
45-54	3	16
55-64	1	5
Tot.	19	100

Table 39 POQ Gender (Female)-Age Demographics

Age/Female	Frequency	%
25-24	3	38
35-44	4	50
45-54	1	12
Tot.	8	100

Table 40 POQ Gender (Male)-Age Demographics

Age/Male	Frequency	%
25-24	1	9
35-44	7	64
45-54	2	18
55-64	1	1
Tot.	11	100

From these simple demographics we get a first picture of the Public Officers involved in the STEP e-Participation during the piloting activities. There is a reasonable balance between Males (11 – 58%) and Females (8 – 42%). In terms of their respective position in the pilots, much of POs were employees of their organisation (12 – 63%) with only 2 participants being actual elected politicians (11%). The point to this consideration is that the actual managements of e-Participation activities within STEP has been conducted by what in D5.1 are called Pilot Leaders, Platform administrators, Responsible for communication etc., people from the Public Authority to whom elected politicians have delegated the task of managing the e-Participation process, after having set the political-participation agenda for the pilot. The age distribution of respondents shows that involved POs are largely from the age band 35-44 (11 – 58%) and this prevalence is present also across the different genders surveyed. By a larger extent POs participating in the piloting of STEP were relatively young and we could assume reasonably well accustomed with using new technologies. In terms of devices used to access the platforms. There has been a quite limited exclusive use of Tablets, with essentially no POs saying they have used only or mainly this device. Overall 8 POs said they have used only or mainly the computer and 3 PO shave said they have used mainly the smart phone. 8 POs’ have used devices equally however with also 2 POs saying they have used equally computer and phone.

In what follows we structure the presentation of results according to the STEP objectives as described in Table 3.

5.1.1 O1: To enable public authorities to quickly open their decision making processes to Young People

In relation to Objective 1 of STEP the POQ did focus on measuring the sub-objective c (O1c): Increased understanding of opinion of Young People. Four questions of the POQ were prepared to measure this and the questions are reported in the following table, for greater clarity and for allowing readers a better understanding of the produced graphs and analysis. This approach will be used throughout the presentation of the results. Tables with questions are not numbered in the deliverable.

Objective	Questions Number	Questions Text
O1c	8b, d, e	The STEP platform improves my ability to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • b: Reach a wider audience of Young People • d: Obtain feedback from Young People more easily compared to old method

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> e: Understand the general opinion of Young People on Environmental Issues
	13b	Understand the general opinion of Young People on environmental issues

Table 41 presents the results for each question for both Positive (Strongly Agree and Agree, SA+A) and Non-negative (including also the Neutral, N), for O1c.

Table 41 O1C: Results against the target

Questions	Frequency (n=19) (SA+A)	Frequency (n=19) (SA+A+N)	% (SA+A)	% (SA+A+N)
8b	13	16	68	84
8d	13	14	68	73
8e	15	16	79	84
13b	12	17	63	89
TARGET			70%	

What follows are graphs associated with questions 8b, 8d and 8e.

8. The STEP platform improves my ability to Reach a wider audience of young people

8. The STEP platform improves my ability to Obtain feedback from young people more easily

8. The STEP platform improves my ability to Understand the general opinion of YP on environmental issues

Figure 19 – General graphs for questions 8b, 8d, 8e

The following are the graph and frequency table associated with question 13b.

Table 42 Q13b Frequency table

Q13b	Frequency	%
Strongly Disagree	1	5
Disagree	1	5
Neutral	5	26
Agree	11	58
Strongly Agree	1	5
Tot.	19	100

Figure 20 – General graph for question 13b

Overall, looking at the results we could conclude that STEP has done well toward the achievement of an increased understanding of opinion of Young People from the perspective of POs. Most respondents do Agree or Strongly Agree with the questions, with hence a good level of positive responses. Only in relation to the subject of the question 13b some improvements may be foreseeable for the future as for example 5 out 19 respondents remain Neutral as to the capacity of STEP to increase their understanding of Young People. The project target for O1c, overall, has been achieved.

5.1.2 O2: To enable young citizens to participate in decision-making on issues with environmental impact

In relation to Objective 2 of STEP the POQ did focus on measuring the following sub-objectives:

- O2a: Increased understanding of opinion of Young People.
- O2b: Increased trust of young citizens in political activities
- O2d: Relevance of content presented to the user through social media mining tool

- O2e: Accuracy of automatically translated content

We will consider each of these sub-objectives in turn.

5.1.2.1 *O2a: Increased understanding of Young People opinion*

The sub-objective O2a was measured with the following questions.

Objective	Questions Number	Questions Text
O2a	8b	The STEP platform improves my ability to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reach a wider audience of Young People
	10	I feel that the STEP platform was appropriate for engaging the target participants and is likely to increase the participation of Young People
	13c	The STEP platform allows policy makers to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engage Young People with environmental policy making

The following table presents the results for O2a.

Table 43 O2a: Results against the target

Question	Frequency (n=19) (SA+A)	Frequency (n=19) (SA+A+N)	% (SA+A)	% (SA+A+N)
8b	13	16	68	84
10	14	18	73	94
13c	13	17	68	90
TARGET			100%	

We have already seen the responses to question 8b. We will report here on questions 10 and 13c.

Table 44 Q10 Frequency table

Q10	Frequency	%
Strongly Disagree	1	5
Neutral	4	21
Agree	9	47
Strongly Agree	5	26
Tot.	19	100

10. The STEP platform was appropriate for engaging participants

Figure 21 – General graph for question 10

Table 45 Q13c Frequency table

Q13c	Frequency	%
Strongly Disagree	1	5
Disagree	1	5
Neutral	4	21
Agree	11	58
Strongly Agree	2	11
Tot.	19	100

13. The STEP platform allows policy makers to Engage young people with environmental policy making

Figure 22 – General graph for question 13c

Most respondents do Agree or Strongly Agree with the four questions. The objective on whether there has been an increased understanding of opinion of Young People (from the perspective of POs) has seen circa 70% of Positive responses. By including also the Neutral responses, we have nearly 90% of Non-negative responses. For the future e-Participation campaigns, it may be suggested to increase the capacity of the platform for reaching a wider audience (question 8b).

5.1.2.2 O2b: Increased trust of young citizens in political activities

The sub-objective O2b was measured with the following questions.

Objective	Questions Number	Questions Text
O2b	13a	The STEP platform allows policy makers to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Conduct a participation process in an unbiased way
	20	Do you think that the STEP platform is likely to increase trust between Young People and policy makers

The following is the results table for O2b.

Table 46 O2b: Results against the target

Questions	Frequency (n=19) (SA+A)	Frequency (n=19) (SA+A+N)	% (SA+A)	% (SA+A+N)
13a	12	17	63	90
20	13	18	68	94
TARGET			100%	

What follows are the graphs and frequency tables for questions 13a and 20.

Table 47 Q13a Frequency table

Q13a	Frequency	%
Strongly Disagree	1	5
Disagree	1	5
Neutral	5	26
Agree	10	53
Strongly Agree	2	11
Tot.	19	100

Figure 23 – General graph for question 13a

Table 48 Q20 Frequency table

Q20	Frequency	%
Disagree	1	5
Neutral	5	26
Agree	8	42
Strongly Agree	5	26
Tot.	19	100

20. STEP increases trust between YP and policy makers

Figure 24 – General graph for question 20

Earlier in the project, we spent a substantial amount of time discussing the issue of Trust, as many respondents to our interviews (especially Young People during the requirements phase) expressed clearly that Trust was a major issue. This was in particular an issue with Young People who generally said they did not trust politicians and their motives and it was clear that there was a gap between Policy Makers and Young People. The objective on whether there has been an increased trust of young citizens in political activities (from the perspective of POs), has also been reasonably reached. Most respondents do Agree or Strongly Agree with the questions, as seen in the frequency tables presented, with figures slightly below 70%. Again if we include in the calculation also the Neutral responses, we can see an overly Non-negative picture (above 90%). It should be remarked that achieving 100% target on this topic remains very difficult in the light of earlier findings from the project but also from the general knowledge we have about people’s mistrust toward politics and politicians (see D4.1 for a discussion). Achieving nearly 70% in this area is quite a positive result for STEP.

5.1.2.3 O2d: Relevance of content presented to the user through social media mining tool

The following question was used to measure the sub-objective O2d.

Objective	Questions Number	Questions Text
O2d	9a	I found that the following STEP platform features were useful: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social Media Mining Tool

The following table presents the results for O2d.

Table 49 O2d: Results against the target

Questions	Frequency (n=16 ¹⁹) (SA+A)	Frequency (n=16) (SA+A+N)	% (SA+A)	% (SA+A+N)
9a	12	15	63	93
TARGET			100%	

9. I found that the following STEP platform features were useful
Social Media Mining Tool

Figure 25 General graph for question 9a

An ad-hoc evaluation on the Social Media Mining Tool (SMMT) is conducted independently as part of WP4. The questionnaire for D5.3 measured the usefulness of the tool with one question. The question design had a “not applicable” field, which means that some of the POs did not use the tool for their activities (n=3). Taking away this figure (n=16), only 1 person out of 16 disagrees with the usefulness of the SMMT. This leads to Non-negative perspective of the POs (by including also the Neutral responses) on the usefulness of the tool (above 90%), as the following table shows. If we limit to SA+A, the Positive response is 63%.

5.1.2.4 O2e: Accuracy of automatically translated content

The following question was used to measure the sub-objective O2e.

Objective	Questions Number	Questions Text
O2e	15	The language translation functionality worked well and was accurate

¹⁹ The 3 non applicable have been removed from the calculation, thus n=16

The following table presents the results for O2e.

Table 50 O2e: Results against the target

Questions	Frequency (n=19) (SA+A)/19	Frequency (n=19) (SA+A+N)/19	% (SA+A)	% (SA+A+N)
15	10	19	52	100
TARGET			80%	

15. The language translation functionality was accurate

Figure 26 – General graph for question 15

The question associated with the language translation tool sees no Negative responses and a little less than half of respondents remaining Neutral. It may be that these Neutral respondents have not used the translation feature directly. Overall, (considering also the Neutral responses) there is no disagreement on the accuracy of translations on the STEP platform (100%) and we have slightly more than half (52%) positive responses.

5.1.3 O4: To pilot test the services in an operational environment in terms of technical, organisational and legal feasibility, with the participation of end users

In relation to the Objective 4, the following sub-objectives have been considered by the questionnaire:

- O4c: Acceptance of the STEP platform
- O4d: Involved representatives from all participating and effected social levels (Social Map)

5.1.3.1 O4c: Acceptance of the STEP platform

The following questions were used to measure the sub-objective O4c.

Objective	Questions Number	Questions Text
O4c	17	I would recommend the STEP platform to other people in a similar position to myself
	18	I would use the STEP platform the next time I need to engage Young People with environmental policy making

The following is the table with the results for objective O4c.

Table 51 O4c: Results against the target

Question	Frequency (n=19) (SA+A)	Frequency (n=19) (SA+A+N)	% (SA+A)	% (SA+A+N)
17	16	17	84	89
18	17	18	89	95
TARGET			70%	

In what follows we present the graphs and frequency tables for questions 17 and 18.

17. I would recommend the STEP platform to other people

Table 52 Q17 Frequency table

Q17	Frequency	%
Strongly Disagree	1	5
Disagree	1	5
Neutral	1	5
Agree	10	53
Strongly Agree	6	32
Tot.	19	100

Figure 27 – General graph for question 17

Table 53 Q18 Frequency table

Q18	Frequency	%
Strongly Disagree	1	5
Neutral	1	5
Agree	9	47
Strongly Agree	8	42
Tot.	19	100

18. I would use the STEP platform for policy making the next time

Figure 28 – General graph for question 18

The objective on whether or not there has been acceptance of the STEP platform has been substantially reached. SA+A Positive responses are well above 80% (against a target of 70%). With the inclusion of Neutral the result changes only marginally, but overall is above 90%. Respondents thus, we could conclude, have used STEP with satisfaction and would indeed be ready and willing to use it again for their participatory policy-making.

5.1.3.2 O4d. Involved representatives from all participating and affected social levels (Social Map)

The following questions were used to measure the sub-objective O4d.

Objective	Questions Number	Questions Text
O4d	8a	The STEP platform improves my ability to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reach a wider audience of Young People
	10	I feel that the STEP platform was appropriate for engaging the target participants and is likely to increase the participation of Young People
	11	I feel that the platform was appropriate and able to reach all sectors of the target audience (including the 'hard to reach')
	12	I feel that the Young People participating via STEP were representative of the Young Population as a whole

Following is the table with the results of objective O4d.

Table 54 – O4d: Results against the target

Questions	Frequency (n=19) (SA+A)	Frequency (n=19) (SA+A+N)	% (SA+A)	% (SA+A+N)
8b	13	16	68	84
10	14	18	73	94
11	13	16	68	84
12	14	18	73	94
TARGET			10%	

For this objective the results of questions 8b and 10 were presented before. Here we present the results of questions 11 (left) and 12 (right).

11. The platform was able to reach all sectors of the target audience

12. Participants were representative of the Young Population

Figure 29 – General graphs for question 11 and 12

Overall POs feel that the objective of involving a wider audience, especially “hard to reach” Young People and also being representative of the Young Population as a whole has been widely achieved. Against a potential target of 10%, the survey has delivered (for SA+A) results which overall are around 70%. However this is clearly the perception of POs. POs thus felt that STEP played an important role in achieving participation, having facilitated the involvement of all the sectors of the Young People population in the pilots.

5.1.4 O5: To assess the usability, effectiveness and impact of the project in embedding open engagement in public sector processes, and to identify the key barriers for wide scale deployment

In relation to the Objective 5, the following sub-objectives have been considered by the questionnaire:

- O5a: Stakeholder satisfaction with organisations’ performance in meeting its charter
- O5b: Utility level of the STEP solution
- O5c: Legal and Ethical Compliance

Furthermore the sub-objective b was further broken down in order to get a better granular evaluation of a certain usability aspects:

- O5b1: Utility of STEP
- O5b2: Accessibility of STEP (overlaps entirely with O5b1, through questions 6 and 7)
- O5b3: Effectiveness of STEP
- O5b4: Barriers for using STEP (measured with qualitative answer in the survey)

Objective O5b2 overlaps entirely with O5b1, through questions 6 and 7 in the POQ, thus there will not be a specific subsection for this. Objective O5b4 was measured with qualitative questions (free text) in the POQ and therefore observations about this objective are included in the qualitative section of the deliverable. Here therefore we focus on O5b1 and O5b3.

5.1.4.1 *O5a: Stakeholder satisfaction with organisations’ performance in meeting its charter*

The following questions were used to measure the sub-objective O5a.

Objective	Questions Number	Questions Text
O5a	13d	The STEP platform allows policy makers to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inform Young People about local initiatives and events
	16	I feel that the results of the e-Participation processes carried out via STEP had a genuine impact on the decision and policies made by the Municipality

What follows is the table with the results for objective O5a.

Table 55 O5a: Results against the target

Question	Frequency (n=19) (SA+A)	Frequency (n=19) (SA+A+N)	% (SA+A)	% (SA+A+N)
13d	16	16	84	84
16	11	17	58	89
TARGET			60%	

What follows are the results from question 13d.

Table 56 Q13d Frequency table

Q13d	Frequency	%
Strongly Disagree	1	5
Disagree	2	10
Agree	15	79
Strongly Agree	1	5
Tot.	19	100

13. The STEP platform allows policy makers to Inform young people about local initiatives and events

Figure 30 – General graph for question 13d

What follows are the results from question 16.

16. The e-participation had a genuine impact on decision and policies

Figure 31 – General graph for question 16

In relation to question 16, overall POs felt that STEP has helped them achieve their goal, with the e-Participation process having a clear impact on the respective decision making processes and on the formulation of policies. Against a target of 60%, we have 58% of POs stating that they Agree and Strongly Agree. By including also the Neutral responses the figure goes to nearly 90%. In relation to question 13d, results also are very Positive with 84% of respondents feeling that STEP helped them in promoting environmental issues at local level and achieving the goals of the respective Public Authority. Thus on this specific point, STEP went well beyond achieving the target showing (in the POs eyes) capacity to be an effective tool for policy making around environmental issues.

5.1.4.2 *O5b: Utility level of the STEP solution*

As stated above, this objective has been further broken down into smaller sub-objectives to allow for a better evaluation of Usability via the questionnaire. We will consider each sub-item in turn.

5.1.4.2.1 *O5b1: Utility of STEP*

The following questions were used to measure the sub-objective O5b1.

Objective	Questions Number	Questions Text
O5b1	5	<p>How did you use the STEP online platform during the Pilot Study</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> To Set up a consultation process <input type="radio"/> To get ideas from Young People via idea sharing features <input type="radio"/> To view topics being discussed on social media <input type="radio"/> To carry out a timeline poll <input type="radio"/> To have a conversation with Young People
	6	<p>I found that the STEP platform was</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> a: intuitive <input type="radio"/> b: enjoyable to use <input type="radio"/> c: attractive <input type="radio"/> d: appropriate for the target audience <input type="radio"/> e: confusing
	7	<p>Did you need to access any Help Settings whilst using STEP</p>
	8	<p>The STEP platform improves my ability to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> a: Disseminate information quickly <input type="radio"/> b: Reach a wider audience of Young People <input type="radio"/> c: Present clear environmental initiative <input type="radio"/> d: Obtain feedback from Young People more easily compared to the old method <input type="radio"/> e: Understand the general opinion of Young People on environmental issues
	13a, b, c	<p>The STEP platform allows policy makers to</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> a: Conduct a participation process in an unbiased way <input type="radio"/> b: Gain a better understanding of the views of Young People <input type="radio"/> c: Engage Young People with environmental policy making

	14	Is there any feature you think would have been useful that was not available?
	19	Is there anything about the STEP platform that would stop you from using it again

The table with the results for this objective is presented at the end of the section, due to its length and to facilitate readability of the text. Of the above, questions 14 and 19 were open questions and are not considered here directly (some considerations are made in the section of this deliverable related with qualitative interviews). We have seen already, in previous sections, the following questions: 8b, d, e, 13a, 13b and 13c. We will therefore concentrate on the remaining questions.

Figure 32 – General graph for question 5

Question number 5 was a checkbox where respondents could choose multiple options. The number of responses received was 39. The question focuses on gathering information about which features of STEP were used by POs. It is clear that in prevalence POs have used STEP with the goal to get ideas from Young People using the idea sharing feature of the platform (n=16). This is followed by setting up a consultation process (n=10) and then to view topics being discussed via Social Media by Young People (n=8). The other two features appear far behind with only 2 POs having used the poll (n=2) and only 3 to have a direct dialogue with Young People (n=3). Therefore ideas generation and consultation do appear the core set of features that POs used during the piloting activities.

Question number 7 asked about the help features of STEP and in if POs have used the help feature and if indeed this helped them achieve what they needed to do. The graph for this question is not included. Overall only 1 respondent did use the help but still could not do what he/she needed. In addition 3 respondents did not use the help also struggling to use the platform. Generally we can conclude that the Help Features has been of good support among those who have used it (8 respondents, 42%) and that a relative majority (11 respondents, 58%) did find the use of STEP straightforward, without the need to consult the help.

What follows are the responses to question number 6 and associated sub-questions.

Figure 33 – General graphs for question 6

Overall from this question there are mixed responses and this appears to be the one area in which STEP will need some further work in the future. In the first 3 questions, 4 POs (21%) disagree as to STEP being intuitive, enjoyable and attractive. This still brings these question responses at around 80% non-negative (including Neutral). However the number of Neutrals equals that of those who agree with the first question (intuitive). For the other two questions, it is clear that POs see STEP as an appropriate instrument for reaching Young People. The last question, asking whether STEP is confusing, must be read in reverse order. There are 4 POs that Agree or Strongly Agree that STEP is confusing, thus overall we have 9 POs that Disagree or Strongly Disagree of STEP being confusing (hence Positive responses).

The remaining results to be seen are associated with question: 8a and 8c. Overall in the case of information dissemination (8a) POs appear reasonably satisfied with only 3 (about 16%) which Disagree and thence with 84% Non-negative responses. Question 8c presents exactly the same dynamics and frequencies, where POs feel satisfied that STEP can present environmental initiatives clearly.

Table 57 Q8a Frequency table

Q8a	Frequency	%
Disagree	3	16
Neutral	4	21
Agree	10	53
Strongly Agree	2	11
Tot.	19	100

Figure 34 – General graph for question 8a

Table 58 Q8c Frequency table

Q8c	Frequency	%
Disagree	3	16
Neutral	3	16
Agree	11	58
Strongly Agree	2	11
Tot.	19	100

Figure 35 – General graph for question 8c

To summarise, both questions 5 and 7 (seen at the beginning of this section) do not yield calculable frequencies that can be compared against a numerical target. However they show aspects of the usability, with, in particular question 7, showing that the help feature has been overall a good support instrument when used and that a relative majority of POs did see the use of STEP as being straightforward, without the need to access the help features. For all the other questions, the following tables shows the overall frequencies (SA+A as well as SA+A+N) and associated percentages, against the target. Overall in the areas associated with question 6 (for Positive responses), some actions need to be recommended for the future in order to improve the overall usability (cells in yellow in the table) and to improve in particular how the platform is enjoyable to use (6b) and its attractiveness (6c). It must be said however that considering the Neutral responses also, however, the non-negative results of question 6 are consistently at around 80% or above. This very well shows that STEP already has a good level of usability and supports well the end-users (e.g. POs). It is perhaps the case that usability requires some fine-tuning, in order to make STEP jump to the next level of capacity.

Table 59 O5b1: Results against the target

Questions	Frequency (n=19) (SA+A)	Frequency (n=19) (SA+A+N)	% (SA+A)	% (SA+A+N)
6a	10	15	52	79
6b	7	15	37	79
6c	9	15	47	79
6d	11	17	58	89
6e ²⁰	9	15	47	79
8a	12	16	64	85
8b	13	16	68	84
8c	13	16	68	84
8d	13	14	68	73
8e	15	16	79	84
13a	12	17	63	90
13b	12	17	63	89
TARGET			100%	

5.1.4.2.2 O5b3: Effectiveness of STEP

The following question has been used to measure the sub-objective O5b3.

Objective	Questions Number	Questions Text
		I found that the following STEP platform features were

²⁰ Due to the nature of question 6e, we are counting here frequencies of Strongly Disagree and Disagree

O5b3	9	<p>useful</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● a: Social Media Mining Tool ● b: Language Translation ● c: Idea sharing ● d: E-petitions ● e: Formal consultation ● f: Admin features ● g: Help
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The table with the results is presented at the end of the section. The effectiveness of STEP is measured by questions 8 (all sub-questions analysis discussed in previous sections) and 9. This latter will be considered here in full.

- Entire Dataset - N=19

9. I found that the following STEP platform features were useful
Social Media Mining Tool

- Entire Dataset - N=19

9. I found that the following STEP platform features were useful
Language Translation feature

- Entire Dataset - N=19

9. I found that the following STEP platform features were useful
Idea Sharing features

- Entire Dataset - N=19

9. I found that the following STEP platform features were useful
e-Petitions

Figure 36 – General graphs for question 9

Overall the Effectiveness of STEP appears very solid with consistent Positive responses from the POs. The following table summarises the results (the non-applicable responses, have been removed and we adjusted the value of n). By including the Neutral responses some items reach 100% and the others are consistently above 90%. By considering only Positive responses, we see question 9h (help features) scoring below 60%. However, as we noted before for question 7, a relative majority of respondents did not use the help feature at all, hence the Neutral responses. We see that only questions 9a, 9b and 9e presents a single Negative response and that all the other questions do have Non-negative responses.

Table 60 O5bc: Results against the target

Questions	Frequency (SA+A)	Frequency (SA+A+N)	% (SA+A)	% (SA+A+N)
9a (n=16)	12	15	75	93

9b (n=18)	14	17	78	94
9c (n=19)	18	19	95	100
9d (n=18)	13	18	72	100
9e (n=18)	12	17	67	94
9f (n=19)	11	19	58	100
9g (n=18)	9	18	50	100
TARGET	13	16	100	

5.1.5 O5c: Legal and Ethical Compliance

The following question has been used to measure the sub-objective O5c.

Objective	Questions Number	Questions Text
O5c	13e	The STEP platform allows policy makers to <input checked="" type="radio"/> Comply with legal and ethical requirements

13. The STEP platform allows policy makers to Comply with legal and ethical requirements

Figure 37 – General graph for question 13e

Table 61 Q13e Frequency table

Q13e	Frequency	%
Disagree	1	5
Neutral	8	42
Agree	8	42
Strongly Agree	2	11
Tot.	19	100

The target for this objective was a Yes over a Yes/No set of options. Overall, as it can be seen in the frequency table, only 1 respondent disagrees, bringing generally a high level of perceived compliance (roughly 95% of respondents considering SA+A+N). We should remember also that this question was missing in one of the pilots where we then used Neutral on the missing data.

5.2 POQ Summary

Overall the POQ evaluation has produced generally positive results with some indicators being very close to the original project targets and quite a good number of them surpassing the target as detailed in previous sections. As we noted, perhaps only around the subject of Usability of the platform and in relation to question 6, some improvements may need to be undertaken in the future in order to improve how the platform can be more enjoyable to use and in part more attractive for POs. However we also noted that on this objective the number of Non-negative response were still very high (at around 80-90%) and for this the recommendation to improve the Usability is in fact a problem of better fine-tuning of the platform, something which will take STEP the next level of tis capacity. Indeed what comes out from this questionnaire is that POs have a strong positive perspective on the capacity of STEP to support their policy making around environmental issues (Objective O4c) and that overall, they are likely to use STEP again for this (84% of positive responses against an original target of 70%) and that they would recommend STEP to other policy makers (89% against a target of 70%).

5.3 Young People Questionnaire

From the YPQ we have gathered 270 responses across all the pilots. It was expected that the YPQ would result in more responses than the POQ and that this would support some comparison across pilots. In what follows we will therefore present both an analysis of a merged unique dataset as well as (where possible) analysis for each individual pilot dataset. The YPQ has resulted in minimal missing data: two free text questions in the Locride pilot and two sub-questions (5c and 8e) in the Hatay questionnaire, these latter have been included with all responses as neutral and the questions will be flagged up in the analysis. This has been done in order to keep the structure of the data identical across pilot responses. As this was an open questionnaire, which was received by all potential participants in the STEP activities, this also has resulted in a number of responses (n=89) from people of age 30+, and thus outside the specific target group of the project (16-29, n=181). In the analysis thus we will filter out the 30+ responses and mainly concentrate on Young People responses. However the 30+ responses afford an interesting opportunity for some comparisons with Young People and where meaningful we will propose some considerations. Some additional notes regarding responses in some pilots are needed. In the case of Mollet del Vallés (MdV thereafter) we have received a comparable low responses rate²¹. The Thessaloniki pilot was an additional pilot (not part of the original project) run by STEP and there we received a low response rate from Young People. It will not be possible to draw meaningful comparisons with these two specific pilots and the others, although on many occasions during the analysis we will present the relative graphs for completeness.

Table 62 16-29 and 30+ responses for each pilot

Pilot	16-29 ²²	30+
Crete	27	13
Locride	31	30
Valdemoro	55	2
MdV	6	10
Hatay	55	16
Thessaloniki	7	18
Tot.	181	89

What follows are frequency tables for each pilot as well as for the entire dataset, for the respondents 16-29.

Table 63 YPQ Gender Demographics 16-29

Gender	Crete		Locride		Valdemoro		MdV		Hatay		Thessaloniki		TOTAL	
	Fr.	%	Fr.	%	Fr.	%	Fr.	%	Fr.	%	Fr.	%	Freq.	%
Female	18	67	14	45	8	15	3	50	39	71	3	43	85	47
Male	9	33	17	55	46	83	3	50	16	29	4	57	95	52.5
PFNS ²³	-	-	-	-	1	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	0.5

²¹ This evaluation survey was run in October 2017 in a moment in which there was particular political turmoil in the Catalunya region and we believe this has impacted on the responses substantially as likely the attention of Young People was on regional politics.

²² Includes also "prefer not to say" responses related with the age question (n=3)

²³ Prefer not to say

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Tot.	27	100	31	100	55	100	6	100	55	100	7	100	181	
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Table 64 YPQ Age Demographics 16-29

Age	Crete		Locride		Valdemoro		MdV		Hatay		Thessaloniki		TOTAL	
	Fr.	%	Fr.	%	Fr.	%	Fr.	%	Fr.	%	Fr.	%	Freq.	%
16-20	5	19	8	26	47	85	2	33	9	16	-	-	71	39
21-24	6	22	6	19	4	7	-		34	62	2	29	52	29
25-29	16	59	17	55	2	4	3	50	12	22	5	71	55	30
PFNS	-	-	-	-	2	4	1	17	-	-	-	-	3	2
Tot.	27	100	31	100	55	100		100	55	100	7	100	181	100

Table 65 YPQ Occupation Demographics 16-29

Occupation	Crete		Locride		Valdemoro		MdV		Hatay		Thessaloniki		TOTAL	
	Fr.	%	Fr.	%	Fr.	%	Fr.	%	Fr.	%	Fr.	%	Freq.	%
Full-time student	6	22	9	29	44	80	2	33	23	42	-	-	84	46
Full-time worker	4	15	3	10	1	2	2	33	19	35	6	86	35	19
Part-time student	3	11	6	19	5	9	-	-	5	9	-	-	19	10
Part-time worker	4	15	6	19	3	5	2	33	-		1	14	16	9
PNTS	1	4	-	-	2	4	-	-	-		-	-	3	1.5
Carer	1	4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		-	-	1	0.5
Not student or worker	3	11	4	13	-	-	-	-	4	9	-	-	11	6
Other	5	19	3	10	-	-	-	-	4	9	-	-	12	9
Tot.	27	100	31	100	55	100	6	100	55	100	7	100	181	100

Overall there is a reasonably balanced distribution among Females (47%) and Males (52.5%²⁴), although there are some imbalances intra-pilot where for example from the Valdemoro questionnaire we have 83% of male respondents and in Hatay 71% Female respondents and 67% in Crete. Also the relevant age-bands considered in the questionnaire (16-20, 21-24, 25-29) are well represented with the larger group being the youngest 16-20 with 39% of observations and the other two accounting for 29% and 30% respectively. The age band 16-20 is over represented in Valdemoro with 85% of observations and the age band 20-24 accounts for 62% of observations in Hatay. In the questionnaire we also asked the occupation of

²⁴ The missing 0.5% refers to "other" genders

participants with the students, both full and part-time, being the largest represented group with 56% of observations, followed by workers (full & part-time) with 27% of observations. In the Valdemoro questionnaire 80% of observations come from full-time students. This seems to reflect the outreach activities carried out by the pilots (ie schools or universities).

5.3.1 O1: To enable public authorities to quickly open their decision making processes to Young People

In relation to Objective 1 of STEP the YPQ did focus on measuring the sub-objective c (O1c): Increased understanding of opinion of Young People.

Objective	Questions Number	Questions Text
O1c	8	8. I feel that the STEP platform was effective in allowing me to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="radio"/> a: Find out what is happening regarding my local environment <input type="radio"/> b: Chat to other interested Young People <input type="radio"/> c: Voice my views / concerns to the relevant policy makers <input type="radio"/> d: Get other Young People interested in important environmental issues <input type="radio"/> e: Participate in environmental policy making compared to the old method <input type="radio"/> f: Filter information of interest from content in social media and web streams <input type="radio"/> g: View content from other countries in my own language <input type="radio"/> h: Find out new things regarding the environmental topics discussed <input type="radio"/> i: Access information in an accessible way
	11	I felt that the contributions made to the STEP platform by Young People were of high quality

We will consider the above two questions in turn, focusing on selected sub-questions. The frequencies (for SA+A=Positive and SA+A+N=Non-negative) are presented in the following results table.

Table 66 O1C: Results against the target

Questions	Frequency (n=181) (SA+A)	Frequency (n=181) (SA+A+N)	% (SA+A)	% (SA+A+N)
8a	128	164	71	91

8b	107	157	59	87
8c	103	160	57	88
8d	110	165	60	90
8e ²⁵ (excl. Hatay n=126)	66	113	53	90
8f	83	161	46	89
8g	112	160	62	89
8h	127	167	70	92
8i	122	162	68	90
11	120	168	66	93
TARGET			70%	

For question 8 we will present some comparison across pilots as there are interesting differences to note, we focus here on questions 8c and 8h, while other items of question 8 will be explored later in relation to other objectives. We will see question 8f when we will discuss the Social Media aspect of STEP in relation to Objective O2d. This is the question that diverges mostly from the actual target (46%). Question 8c in particular was the one with highest Positive responses (Strongly Disagree + Disagree, n=21, 11%). Although we can still see an overall Non-negative outcome (81%), pilots have had a different views. Overall, questions associated in a very explicit way with policy makers do seem to suffer still from a degree of lack of trust (see objective O2b) as for example question 8e presents a similar pattern. This is an aspect that has been discussed multiple times in STEP deliverables and something that emerged very early in the project (already during requirement gathering and later on in other phases of research) and it appears the most difficult gap to fill.

8. I feel that the STEP platform was effective in allowing me to:
Voice my views / concerns to the relevant policy makers

²⁵ Missing data from Hatay

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Figure 38 General and pilot graphs for question 8c

We see in relative terms that 22% of respondents (n=12) from Hatay Disagree or Strongly Disagree with the question (more than 1/2 of the total overall) and that there is a marked difference in Negative responses with other pilots, especially Valdemoro, Crete and Locride. MdV and Thessaloniki, as said, have a low response rate and it is hence difficult to compare (although Thessaloniki appears to have the same pattern with n=2),

but the graphs are still presented for completeness. The issue associated with the question – namely whether Young People were able to voice their concerns to policy makers - thus may not be widespread across pilots and related directly with the STEP platform, and it may actually constitute an issue associated with trust toward the local policy making in the specific pilot mostly. We see that in Crete and Valdemoro the negative response percentage is lower and in Locride there are no Negative response at all. Overall however the Hatay pilot presents a stronger Positive response (SA+A) than some other pilots, indeed it is also noticeable how in the Valdemoro pilot there is a large chunk of neutral responses (45%) and that Hatay fares also better than Crete in Positive responses. As we will see later, the high neutral response rate in the Valdemoro pilot is a pattern emerging in nearly all questions and it may be associated with the relatively low success of the piloting activities in Valdemoro.

It is further interesting to see that for example this question does present limited differences in Negative responses when seen from an age-band or gender perspective, as the following graphs show. Although Positive responses (SA+A) do very clearly increase as the age grows, with the youngest group (16-20) showing 48% SA+A responses, far less than the other two groups of Young People. We can see also the results for 30+ where the Negative responses are even lower.

Figure 39 – Graphs for question 8c, age

From a gender perspective, Negative responses (SD+D) appear much more pronounced for Females (around 15%) than for Males (around 8%), although Females respondents do show more pronounced Positive responses (SA+A).

Figure 40 Graphs for question 8c, gender

The following are the gender graphs for the Hatay pilot, where we clearly see that in relative terms it is actually the Female group who has the largest Negative attitude toward the subject of the question 8c.

Figure 41 Graphs for question 8c, Hatay and gender

Question 8h has shown a strong performance in positive responses, where Young People feel that STEP has helped them with finding new information about the environmental topics discussed on the platform. The following is the graph for the entire dataset.

8. I feel that the STEP platform was effective in allowing me to:
Find out new things regarding the environmental topics discussed

Figure 42 General graph for question 8h

The following are the graphs for the pilots. It is quite noticeable the strong Positive response (SA+A) in Locride, Crete as well as Hatay (again MdV and Thessaloniki are presented for completeness). On the other hand it is noticeable that Positive responses are far lower in Valdemoro, where there is a large chunk of Neutral responses.

8. I feel that the STEP platform was effective in allowing me to:
Find out new things regarding the environmental topics discussed

8. I feel that the STEP platform was effective in allowing me to:
Find out new things regarding the environmental topics discussed

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Figure 43 Pilot graphs for question 8h

The following is the general graph for question 11, asking about the quality of contributions of Young People and further following are the graphs for each of the 6 pilots (again with caution on the analysis for Mollet del Vallés and Thessaloniki)

11. The contributions made to the STEP platform were of high quality

Figure 44 General and pilots graphs for question 11

What is evident about the cross-pilot comparison is that while all the pilots present relative strong Positive (SA+A) responses, Valdemoro does have a quite large chunk of Neutral responses. This is a pattern which thus far, in the questions presented, Valdemoro has displayed consistently and, as said, it is very likely due to the relatively low success of the piloting activities in this municipality. In any case, the overall figure of Positive responses (66%) for the question is very close to the actual target of 70%.

5.3.2 O2: To enable young citizens to participate in decision-making on issues with environmental impact

In relation to Objective 1 of STEP the YPQ did focus on measuring the following **sub-objectives**:

- O2a: Increased understanding of opinion of Young People.
- O2b: Increased trust of young citizens in political activities
- O2d: Relevance of content presented to the user through social media mining tool
- O2e: Accuracy of automatically translated content

We will consider each of these sub-objectives in turn.

5.3.2.1 O2a: Increased understanding of opinion of Young People.

The sub-objective O2a was measured with the following question.

Objective	Questions Number	Questions Text
O2a	14	STEP is likely to increase the number of Young People taking part in Policy Making

The following table presents the results for O2a.

Table 67 O2a: Results against the target

Question	Frequency (n=181) (SA+A)	Frequency (n=181) (SA+A+N)	% (SA+A)	% (SA+A+N)
14	119	161	66	89
TARGET			100%	

The question shows a relatively positive scenario where Young People do generally agree that STEP can indeed increase the participation of Young People to policy making. Positive responses are at 66% and Non-negative at 89%, against a 100% target. It is interesting however to analyse the responses further to unveil some pilots dynamics as we did before. What follows is the general graph for question 14 and following are the pilot graphs. What seems to be clear in particular is that majority of the overall Negative responses (13 out of 20) comes from the Valdemoro pilot. In this pilot we also have nearly half of the Neutral responses (19 out of 42) also. There may be thus some pilot dynamics associated with how people see the capacity of the platform to increase Young People participation. We see indeed strong positive answers in the three other pilots of Hatay, Crete and Locride with also very low number of negative responses. We may perhaps hypothesise that the Valdemoro relatively Negative results may be associated with the piloting activities, perhaps some relative obstacles in accessing or participating. A gap this that may need to be filled in the

future at the municipality level, should this authority continue relying on e-Participation as a method of involvement of Young People.

14. STEP is likely to increase YP participation in Policy Making

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14. STEP is likely to increase YP participation in Policy Making

Figure 45 – General and pilot graphs for question 14

Upon observations, results for this question also do not differ extremely for genders and ages (graphs are not presented here). It is also not possible to observe demographics differences especially in the Valdemoro pilot data due to the unbalanced responses as discussed earlier (prevalence of males, 16-20 and students).

5.3.2.2 O2b: Increased trust of young citizens in political activities

The sub-objective O2b was measured with the following questions.

Objective	Questions Number	Questions Text
O2b	5d, e	Participating in Environmental Policy Making via STEP: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • d: made policy makers seem more in touch with younger people • e: Increased the transparency of the decision making process
	6g	. The STEP Platform: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Is trustworthy
	12	After using STEP I feel more able to trust local policy makers

The following is the table with the results for objective O2b.

Table 68 O2b: Results against the target

Questions	Frequency (n=181) (SA+A)	Frequency (n=181) (SA+A+N)	% (SA+A)	% (SA+A+N)
5d	89	136	49	75
5e	92	153	50	84
6g	124	163	68	90
12	88	152	49	84
TARGET			100%	

As it has been noted multiple times in other deliverables (for example D2.2 and D4.1) the issue of Young People’s trust toward politicians is a rather delicate issue where – especially from qualitative interviews – it emerged as a general distrust toward the actions but also the motives of policymakers in enacting participatory policy formulation processes. Here we concentrate the analysis on questions 5d and 12, and to a lesser extent 6g. If we look at the results for question 5d, we can clearly see that there is a perceived trust gap between Young People and policy makers. Overall the positive responses outweigh the negative ones, however these latter amount to 25% (n=45) of the total.

5. Participating in Environmental Policy Making via STEP
Made policy makers seem more in touch with younger people

Figure 46 General graph for question 5d

There are some cross-pilots differences related to the observations just made, which is further interesting to pinpoint (we limit here to the four pilots with the largest responses). It is clear indeed that Locride and Crete show strong Positive responses, with a reasonably good level of trust. In Hatay although circa 24% have provided negative responses we still have a majority of Positive ones. Valdemoro however clearly shows the largest chunk of Negatives (nearly 42%) and Positives amount to less than 30% only. This again may confirm what we noted when discussing the previous objective: this pilot may need extra activities in order to fill the trust gap via e-Participation.

Figure 47 Pilot graphs for question 5d

It is interesting to see responses to this question from an age perspective (although as a caution we need to remember that on this weigh the demographics of the Valdemoro pilot). We include here also responses received from 30+. We can clearly see that Negative responses decrease with the increase of age, where thus a correlation may be hypothesised that as age increases the perceived negative trust attitude toward policy makers then decreases. However positive responses appear very strong for respondents in the age band 21-24.

Figure 48 Graphs for question 5d, age

The following is the general graph for question 6g. The question clearly did focus on the platform – rather than directly on policy makers – but it aimed at understanding how the “medium is the message”, in other word how the policy making message as delivered through STEP can increase trust. We can clearly see strong Positive responses (a little less than 70%) with limited Negative ones (amounting to exactly 10%). Thus STEP, could be concluded, has in fact the capacity to increase trust and it is seen by Young People as a trustworthy instrument for e-Participation (e.g. if we compare for example with 5d results), so long that the focus is not directly on the figure of policy makers but with a strong focus on the policy making message.

Figure 49 General graph for question 6g

Question 12 was also directly focused on the figure of policy makers but with a clear accent on the local ones. More than on the general results – that although clearly present a high number of Neutral responses - it is hence interesting to consider the pilots results.

Figure 50 General graph for question 12

We can see that Hatay and Locride present strong Positive results (in both cases 60% circa), with the latter not presenting even a single negative response. This latter about Locride is also a pattern which (as we will see) has emerged often in the questionnaire. Crete and Valdemoro present relatively less Positives (in both cases slightly above 30%), however the second has a much larger chunk of Negatives (above 30%, n=18)

which amounts for more than half of the Negative responses for the entire dataset. We have noted previously this pattern emerging from this specific pilot and the focus of question 12 on “local policy makers” perhaps confirms the presence of some specific pilot dynamics associated with negative results.

Figure 51 – Pilot graphs for question 12

5.3.2.3 O2d: Relevance of content presented to the user through social media mining tool

The following question was used to measure the sub-objective O2d.

Objective	Questions Number	Questions Text
O2d	7d	STEP Platform features: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social Media Mining tool allowed me to find posts of interest to me
	8f	I feel that the STEP platform was effective in allowing me to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Filter information of interest from content in social media and web streams

The following is the table with the results for objective O2d.

Table 69 O2d: Results against the target

Questions	Frequency (SA+A)	Frequency (SA+A+N)	% (SA+A)	% (SA+A+N)
7d (n=151 ²⁶)	84	136	56	90
8f (n=181)	83	161	46	89
TARGET			100%	

Question 8f, as seen in the results table, presents a 46% positive responses, which appear relatively far from the 100% target. This is largely due, in fact to Neutral responses, as indeed for this question the Non-negative response is at 89%, pretty much in line with all the other sub-questions of question 8 (see O1c) and with thence the same level of negative responses. The Neutral responses also do come from all the pilots, this time more or less in similar proportions. It may very well be that respondents while seeing the usefulness of filtering Social Media information from STEP, remain neutral toward the relevance of this information for the participatory policy making process.

²⁶ Responses for “not used” have been removed

8. I feel that the STEP platform was effective in allowing me to:
Filter information of interest from social media and web streams

Figure 52 General graph for question 8f

Question 7d presents pretty similar dynamics of the previous question. In this case we have a number of responses from people who have not used the feature (n=30). The number of Positive responses however outweigh the Neutral ones and overall this bring a mild Positive (SA+D) perspective on the capacity of the Social Media tools to filter relevant information. By including also the Non-negative neutral responses, the figure goes to 90% not very far from the original target.

7. STEP Platform features
Social Media Mining tool allowed me to find posts of interest to me

Figure 53 General graph for question 7d (including not used, n=30)

5.3.2.4 O2e: Accuracy of automatically translated content

The following questions were used to measure the sub-objective O2e.

Objective	Questions Number	Questions Text
O2e	7c	STEP Platform features: <input checked="" type="radio"/> Language translation was accurate
	8g	I feel that the STEP platform was effective in allowing me to: <input checked="" type="radio"/> View content from other countries in my own language

What follows is the results table for the objective O2e.

Table 70 O2e: Results against the target

Questions	Frequency (SA+A)	Frequency (SA+A+N)	% (SA+A)	% (SA+A+N)
7c (n=164 ²⁷)	106	149	65	90
8g (n=181)	112	160	62	89
TARGET			80%	

- Entire Dataset - N=181

7. STEP Platform features
Language translation was accurate

Figure 54 General graph for question 7c (including not used, n=17)

²⁷ Responses for “not used” have been removed

As we can see from the table, both questions present similar dynamics, above 60% for Positive responses and 90% for Non-negative. Before is the main graph for figure 7c where we can clearly see strong Positive responses, well above the Neutral ones. Overall, the language translation feature does seem capable to offer the translation functionalities that are relevant for participatory policy making across borders.

5.3.3 O4: To pilot test the services in an operational environment in terms of technical, organisational and legal feasibility, with the participation of end users

In relation to the Objective 4, the following sub-objectives have been considered by the questionnaire:

- O4c: Acceptance of the STEP platform
- O4d: Involved representatives from all participating and effected social levels (Social Map)

5.3.3.1 O4c: Acceptance of the STEP platform

The following questions were used to measure the sub-objective O4c.

Objective	Questions Number	Questions Text
O4c	6	The STEP Platform: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • a: is Intuitive to use • b: is Engaging • c: is Enjoyable to use • d: Has an attractive interface • e: Provides information that was relevant to me • f: Provides politically unbiased information • g: is trustworthy • h: Gave me enough information regarding data protection issue
	7	STEP Platform features: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • a: Help features were useful • b: Online chat / forums were enjoyable to use • c: Language translation was accurate • d: Social Media Mining tool allowed me to find posts of interest • e: to me Idea sharing features were interesting
	13	I feel that the feedback given of how Young People's contributions have been considered was adequate
	14	STEP is likely to increase the number of Young People taking part in Policy Making
	15	I would recommend the STEP platform to other Young People

Results of question 7 are presented in a separate table for simplicity, as the question had the “non-used” option and thus usable frequencies vary across sub-questions (once non-used are taken away). All the scores for Positive responses are not far away from the target figure of 70% and if we include Non-negative, scores are all well above the target. Overall we can conclude that STEP has achieved a reasonable level of acceptance and that the target has been met satisfactorily. In what follows we discuss some questions while some have already been discussed. For example, question 14 was discussed also in relation to objective O2a. After the table, we present and discuss in particular the graphs related with questions 13, 15 and 6f.

Table 71 O4c: Results against the target

Question	Frequency (n=181) (SA+A)	Frequency (n=181) (SA+A+N)	% (SA+A)	% (SA+A+N)
6a	110	152	60	83
6b	96	163	53	90
6c	106	156	59	87
6d	98	160	54	88
6e	124	168	69	93
6f	115	166	63	91
6g	124	163	68	90
6h	113	170	62	93
13	90	158	50	88
14	119	161	66	89
15	139	177	77	98
TARGET			70%	

Table 72 O4c: Results against the target for question 7

Question ²⁸	Frequencies (SA+A)	Frequencies (SA+A+N)	% (SA+A)	% (SA+A+N)
7a (n=161)	104	144	65	89
7b (n=148)	85	136	57	92
7c (n=164)	106	149	65	90
7d	84	136	56	90

²⁸ Responses for “not used” have been removed

(n=151)				
7e (n=165)	105	153	63	93
TARGET			70%	

Question 13 is the one which presents the lowest positive score. However as we can see also from the graph this appears to be due to the presence of a large component of neutral responses. The question asked about the feedback that Young People had received on their contribution to the participatory policy making process via STEP. It is thus not so much the case that Young People were not satisfied with the level of feedback received, but that the feedback was adequate (Neutral) for a large chunk of them. If we split again the data across pilots we can observe some interesting dynamics. First of all, Neutral responses appear strongly across all pilots (we observed before that one particular pilot often had the most neutral observations). We can see in particular Valdemoro and Crete having nearly the same percentages of Neutral responses (49% - 44%), with Hatay and Locride also having the same figures (around 30% for each). Interestingly we can also see that Hatay presents the largest set of Strongly Disagree responses (n=6) in fact amounting to 75% of all Strongly Disagree. It therefore looks like that particularly in Hatay, some Young People did not feel the feedback received was adequate in relation to their contribution to the participation in policy making.

13. Adequate feedback of how YP contributions have been considered

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Figure 55 General and pilot graphs for question 13

We can also look at the dynamics of this question in relation to the age demographics, where there are clearly marked differences. We clearly see that there is a potential correlation between increasing age and reduced negative responses, where then the oldest group 25-29 (among Young People) appear less in disagreement with the fact that the feedback received was adequate. Like we have seen before however, the strongest Positive responses belong to the group 21-24. We do not report the 30+ as the question was directly asking about Young People.

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Figure 56 Graphs for question 13, age

Question 15 has seen very strong Positive responses from Young People. We can clearly see the largest set of responses in the Strongly Agree, with very limited negative ones (n=4 <3%). In fact, the overall Positives reach 77%, well above the target, showing that on this aspect there is a very strong acceptance of STEP as a policy making tool and that Young People would recommend STEP to their peers for this purpose. All the pilots thus show strong Positive responses, with however the Valdemoro pilot having 40% Neutral responses.

15. I would recommend the STEP platform to other young people

Figure 57 General graph for question 15

Question 6f presents a different dynamic, with far less Neutral responses and a far stronger set of Positive responses. The question asked whether Young People felt that the information provided through STEP was politically unbiased. From the individual pilot graphs we see that particularly in the Locride pilot there is a strong Positive response (83%) and a similar figure is present also in the Crete pilot (75%). The Valdemoro pilot presents the dynamic we have observed also earlier, with a relatively large number of Neutral responses. Hatay and Crete both present the largest set of Strongly Agree responses (27% and 33% respectively), whereas Valdemoro has the lowest (approx. 13%). Clearly, thus there are some pilot dynamics associated with the responses to this question. Although the STEP platform is generally seen as an online venue where information is provided with limited or absent political bias, there may be local differences related with piloting as to how Young People perceive this specific aspect. In the Valdemoro pilot there has been consistently some milder scepticism toward the participatory policy making.

6. The STEP Platform (System Evaluation) Provides politically unbiased information

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Figure 58 General and pilot graphs for question 6f

5.3.4 O5: To assess the usability, effectiveness and impact of the project in embedding open engagement in public sector processes, and to identify the key barriers for wide scale deployment

In relation to the Objective 5, the following sub-objectives have been considered by the YPQ:

- O5a: Stakeholder satisfaction with organisations’ performance in meeting its charter
- O5b: Utility level of the STEP solution
- O5c: Legal and Ethical Compliance

Furthermore the sub-objective b was further broken down in order to get a better granular evaluation of a certain usability aspects:

- O5b1: Utility of STEP
- O5b2: Accessibility of STEP
- O5b3: Effectiveness of STEP
- O5b4: Barriers for using STEP (measured with free text questions, results are discussed in the section about qualitative interviews)

5.3.4.1 O5a: Stakeholder satisfaction with organisations' performance in meeting its charter

Objective	Questions Number	Questions Text
O5a	5f	Participating in Environmental Policy Making via STEP: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Had a genuine impact on the decision and policies made by the local municipality
	8a	I feel that the STEP platform was effective in allowing me to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a: Find out what is happening regarding my local environment

The following is the result table for objective O5a. We will discuss both questions in turn.

Table 73 O5a: Results against the target

Question	Frequency (n=19) (SA+A)	Frequency (n=19) (SA+A+N)	% (SA+A)	% (SA+A+N)
5f	76	149	42	82
8a	128	164	71	91
TARGET			60%	

Question 5f appears to have a large majority of Neutral responses which is clearly visible also from the graph, there is indeed a clear discrepancy between Positive (SA+A) responses (42%) and Non-negative (82%). Looking at the pilot graphs, are particularly visible the 70% neutral responses from the Crete pilot and the circa 23% of negative responses in the Valdemoro pilot. This high level of Neutral responses is possibly due to the length of time needed by Policy Makers to analyse the results of eParticipation response and to formulate a response. Many of the Pilots had yet to give feedback on many of the dialogues. The qualitative interviews revealed that YP prefer and expect more immediate results which conflicts with the slower methodologies of local Policy Makers.

5. Participating in Environmental Policy Making via STEP
Had a genuine impact on the local municipality

Figure 59 General graph for question 5f

Figure 60 Pilot graphs for question 5f

We can perhaps read the results of the previous question in the light of question 8a, asking if STEP has helped Young People knowing better about environmental initiatives. We clearly see strong positive responses overall (71%) well above the 60% target.

8. I feel that the STEP platform was effective in allowing me to:
Find out what is happening regarding my local environment

Figure 61 General graph for question 8a

For example, the Crete pilot (which in 5f had 70% Neutral) has a very strong positive response (85%). The Valdemoro pilot which throughout the questionnaire has shown substantial Neutral, brings about more than half of the overall Neutral responses while at the same time displaying a 51% positive not far from the actual target of 60%. Overall one could conclude that STEP has been very effective in letting people know more about environmental initiatives in the local area (8a), however the actual impact on the local municipality/region (5f) has perhaps not yet been delivered in full during the project lifetime. It may also be a question of timing associated with the implementation of policies, which indeed require some time before actual concrete results could be seen by citizens.

Table 74 Q8a Frequency Table Crete

Q8a	Frequency	%
Strongly Disagree	1	4
Disagree	1	4
Neutral	2	7
Agree	14	14
Strongly Agree	9	29
Tot.	27	100

8. I feel that the STEP platform was effective in allowing me to:
Find out what is happening regarding my local environment

Figure 62 Graph for question 8a, Crete

Table 75 Q8a Frequency Table
Vademoro

Q8a	Frequency	%
Strongly Disagree	2	4
Disagree	3	5
Neutral	22	40
Agree	22	40
Strongly Agree	6	11
Tot.	55	100

8. I feel that the STEP platform was effective in allowing me to:
Find out what is happening regarding my local environment

Figure 63 Graph for question 8a, Vademoro

5.3.4.2 O5b: Utility level of the STEP solution

As stated above, this objective has been further broken down in smaller items to allow for a better evaluation of Usability via the questionnaire. We will consider each sub-item in turn.

5.3.4.2.1 O5b1: Utility of STEP

The following questions were used to measure the sub-objective O5b1.

Objective	Questions Number	Questions Text
O5b1	5	Participating in Environmental Policy Making via STEP: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • a: Gave me enough information about the topic in question • b: Gave me enough time to consider the issues • c: Made it clear why I should get involved • d: Made policy makers seem more in touch with younger people • e: Increased the transparency of the decision making process • f: Had a genuine impact on the decision and policies made by the local municipality
	7	STEP Platform features: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • a: Help features were useful • b: Online chat / forums were enjoyable to use • c: Language translation was accurate • d: Social Media Mining tool allowed me to find

		posts of interest e: to me Idea sharing features were interesting
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The following is the table with the results for the objective in relation to question 5. The results for question 7 were presented under objective O4c and will not be repeated here.

Table 76 O5b1: Results against the target

Questions	Frequency (n=181) (SA+A)	Frequency (n=181) (SA+A+N)	% (SA+A)	% (SA+A+N)
5a	123	164	68	91
5b	115	168	64	93
5c ²⁹ (n=126)	77	121	61	96
5d	89	136	49	75
5e	92	153	50	84
5f	76	149	42	82
TARGET			100%	

We can see from the table above, that for some questions the Positive responses are below 50%, although displaying in all cases non-negative responses well above 70% or more. We have seen the analysis associated with some of sub-questions for both 5 and 7 (i.e. 5f was presented in O5a, 5d and 5e in O2b, 7d in O2d and 7c in O2e). We will concentrate here on two questions, which have not been discussed thus far: 5a and 5b.

Question 5a asked whether Young People had received enough information from the platform in order to be properly involved in the participatory policy making process. Overall, we have a solid 68% of Positive responses and 91% of Non-negative, where clearly STEP has fulfilled the role of providing relevant information. There are some pilot differences (graphs not presented here) but they are far less pronounced than, in some cases, we have seen before. For example, Valdemoro displays 29% of Neutral responses, where the highest relative percentage of Neutral responses comes from Locride (35.5%). The largest Positive responses percentage comes from Crete with 78%.

²⁹ Question was missing from 1 of the pilots

5. Participating in Environmental Policy Making via STEP Gave me enough information about the topic in question

Figure 64 General graph for question 5a

Question 5b presents the same dynamics of the previous question, although with a slightly higher number of Neutral responses. Positive responses are at 64% and Non-negative at 93%.

5. Participating in Environmental Policy Making via STEP Gave me enough time to consider the issues

Figure 65 General graph for question 5b

Generally, for question 5, the bottom three sub-questions present a relatively low set of positive responses (below 50%). Some improvements should be then undertaken in this area especially in the relation between policy-making at local-pilot level and the involvement of Young People. For question 7, the sub-questions 7b and 7d also have similar dynamics, however they are well above 50% of Positive responses. Generally, the outlook for the objective is positive.

5.3.4.2.2 O5b2: Usability, Accessibility of STEP

The following questions were used to measure the sub-objective O5b2.

Objective	Questions Number	Questions Text
O5b2	6a, 6b, 6c, 6d, 6e	The STEP Platform: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ a: is Intuitive to use ○ b: is Engaging ○ c: is Enjoyable to use ○ d: Has an attractive interface ○ e: Provides information that was relevant to me

The results table for objective O5b2 is presented below.

Table 77 O5b2: Results against the target

Questions	Frequency (n=181) (SA+A)	Frequency (n=181) (SA+A+N)	% (SA+A)	% (SA+A+N)
6a	110	152	60	83
6b	96	163	53	90
6c	106	156	59	87
6d	98	160	54	88
6e	124	168	69	93
TARGET			100	

We will consider four sub-questions here: 6a-6d where we have generally a set of positive responses with however some variations. The four main graphs are presented together for ease of comparison.

6. The STEP Platform (System Evaluation) is Intuitive to use

6. The STEP Platform (System Evaluation) is Engaging

Figure 66 General graphs for question 6a-6d

The question on how intuitive the platform is to use scored the highest in terms of Positives but also present the largest set of Negative ones (17%). After the main graphs, some pilot graphs are presented for further discussion. Most of the pilots display strong positives in relation to question 6a. The pilot of Hatay has 76% Positives, Valdemoro has 56% and Crete 70%. It is actually the Locride pilot which contributes much (with more than 1/3) to the relatively high number of Negatives here, and in part also to the Neutral responses as the below graph shows. We can see the striking differences if, for instance, we consider the Crete responses (which had a similar number of overall responses to Locride).

Table 78 6a Frequency Table Locride

Q6a	Frequency	%
Disagree	11	35
Neutral	12	39
Agree	6	19
Strongly Agree	2	6
Tot.	31	100

Figure 67 Graph for question 6a, Locride

Table 79 Q6a Frequency Table Crete

Q6a	Frequency	%
Strongly Disagree	1	4
Disagree	3	11
Neutral	4	15
Agree	7	26
Strongly Agree	12	44
Tot.	27	100

Figure 68 Graph for question 6a, Crete

Somehow, question 6b presents similar dynamics. In this case, we see clearly the Locride pilot presenting a large Neutral component as well as a relatively Negative one (22%), contrasting greatly with the positive responses received from Crete.

Table 80 Q6b Frequency Table Locride

Q6b	Frequency	%
Disagree	7	23
Neutral	18	58
Agree	4	13
Strongly Agree	2	6
Tot.	31	100

Figure 69 Graph for question 6b, Locride

Table 81 Q6b Frequency Table Crete

Q6b	Frequency	%
Disagree	1	4
Neutral	7	26
Agree	11	41
Strongly Agree	8	30
Tot.	27	100

Figure 70 Graph for question 6b, Crete

Question 6c and 6d have the exact same dynamics with the Locride pilot showing generally a high level of Neutral responses, coupled with relatively low level of Positives (we see Negatives between 22-25%). This can be seen by comparing also with Crete as we did for previous questions. It thus could be concluded that Usability/Accessibility is very positive in the Hatay, Crete and Valdemoro (where we still we have a relative number of Neutral). However in the Locride pilot there clearly are some issues associated with the usability and accessibility of the platform, which has then impacted overall on general responses. Some in-depth material associated with this specific issue for the Locride pilot can be read in the analysis of qualitative interviews in this Deliverable. We have seen indeed in some of previous objectives that the Locride pilot has very strong Positive scores, often with zero Negative responses.

Figure 71 Graphs for question 6c and 6d, Locride and Crete

5.3.4.2.3 O5b3: Effectiveness

The following questions were used to measure the sub-objective O5b3.

Objective	Questions Number	Questions Text
O5b3	9	<p>Gamification features of the STEP platform:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • a: Personalised greeting when using STEP • b: Being able to compare my Dialogue score with others using the platform • c: Being able to browse the profiles of others on the platform • d: Competing with other users for a position on the leaderboard Receiving points for activity • e: Receiving points for activity on the platform • f: Receiving badges/awards after gaining sufficient points
	10	<p>I found the following features of STEP to be useful:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • a: Online Chat / Discussion Forum • b: E-Petitions • c: Formal Consultation processes • d: Social Media Mining Tool • e: Language Translation • f: Ability to see Dialogues in other European countries • g: Links to relevant organisations

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Below there are the results related to question 9 and 10. They are presented in two tables for convenience, where in particular, question 9 is entirely focussed on evaluating the gamification component of the platform and question 10 evaluates each of the other components of the platform. We will present here the general graphs for each sub-question, graphs (differently than the tables) include the not-used/not-aware answers for completeness as this information also gives a sense of how much a specific feature/gamification aspect has not been used and it is perhaps interesting also to see differences across pilots for some questions.

Questions	Frequency (SA+A)	Frequency (SA+A+N)	% (SA+A)	% (SA+A+N)
9a (n=159)	97	144	61	90
9b (n=162)	104	148	64	91
9c (n=165)	101	154	61	93
9d (n=165)	103	154	62	93
9e (n=165)	112	155	68	94
9f (n=157)	101	146	64	93

Table 82- O5b3: Results against the target

Questions	Frequency (SA+A)	Frequency (SA+A+N)	% (SA+A)	% (SA+A+N)
10a (n=171)	98	156	57	91
10b (n=172)	100	160	58	93
10c (n=175)	103	162	59	93
10d (n=175)	89	156	51	89
10e	99	161	56	91

(n=177)				
10f (n=174)	116	160	67	92
10g (n=172)	108	158	63	92
TARGET			100	

The following are the general graphs for question 9, where we see generally good Positive responses, with in some cases the Strongly Agree being the largest set (i.e. 9d, 9e and 9f) and overall limited number of negative responses in all the six sub-questions. Much of the gap between positive responses and the objective target comes indeed from neutral responses which overall appear constant across the sub-questions (between 40 to 50 responses). After the general graphs we present some of the pilot graphs considering also the “not aware” responses.

9. Gamification features of the STEP platform
Personalised greeting when using STEP

9. Gamification features of the STEP platform
Being able to compare my Dialogue score with others using the platform

9. Gamification features of the STEP platform
Being able to browse the profiles of others on the platform

9. Gamification features of the STEP platform
Competing with other users for a position on the leaderboard

9. Gamification features of the STEP platform
Receiving points for activity on the platform

9. Gamification features of the STEP platform
Receiving badges/awards after gaining sufficient points

Figure 72 General graphs for question 9

As a case to exemplify this situation we propose the pilot graphs for question 9f (the one with the largest not aware, n=24). First of all it is interesting to see that while in absolute terms much of the “not aware” responses come from the Hatay and the Valdemoro pilots, in relative terms it is the Crete pilot which has the largest not-aware response, with a little less than a quarter of respondents stating they were not aware of this gamification feature (the badges). Overall we can also see that Valdemoro presents the lowest percentage of Positive responses, with the other pilots being instead all above 50% Positives and Locride having 58% of “Liked a lot” (the top item of the Likert scale). Negative responses appear in percentage terms equal among Hatay, Valdemoro and Crete. Mollet del Vallés and Thessaloniki graphs are reported for completeness.

9. Gamification features of the STEP platform
Receiving badges/awards after gaining sufficient points

9. Gamification features of the STEP platform
Receiving badges/awards after gaining sufficient points

Figure 73 Pilot graphs for question 9f

In relation to question 9f we offer also some observation in relation to age. Given the nature of the gamified experience, one would expect the youngest to be far more attracted by the gamification than the older groups and also to be those who have used gamification the most. This expectation does not appear however to be confirmed by existing data, we see that proportionally in the youngest age-band (16-20) we have the lowest number of Positive responses, the highest Number of neutral as well as the second highest “not aware” (after the 30+) set of responses. Considering Young People only (16-29) the contrary appears hence true, that gamification is seen more effective as age increases with the group 25-29 showing the largest positive set of responses and the lowest “not aware”, followed by the group 21-24.

Figure 74 Graphs for question 9f, age

We will see now the data from one of the above questions with the graphs stripped of “not aware” responses, we focus on question 9d - the leaderboard - largely because this, together with the badges, constitutes a core component of the STEP gamification. Below is the general graph stripped of the “not aware” responses and further down the pilot graphs (for the pilots with more responses, excluding thence Mollet del Vallés and Thessaloniki). We can see strong positive responses in Crete, Locride and to a lesser extent in Hatay. The larger percentage of neutral responses is present in the Valdemoro pilot, following a pattern we have observed multiple times throughout this analysis.

9. Gamification features of the STEP platform
Competing with other users for a position on the leaderboard

Figure 75 General and pilot graphs for question 9d

Overall, we can conclude that the gamification features have received a positive welcoming from Young People, where the questionnaire has seen high levels of “liked a lot” responses (often the majority, the equivalent of Strongly Agree in the other questions). The gamified experience is thus quite effective in supporting the participatory policy making process. Some work may still be required to make the gamification more visible to the end-users by reducing the number of people who may not become aware of it and to explain better how the gamification element is integral part of the STEP user experience. For the neutral responses we have seen that a good part of them are related with one specific pilot (e.g. with n=22 in question 9d, in Valdemoro they amount to 43% of neutral responses), showing a dynamic which has been experienced in most aspects of this evaluation, where this pilot has generally shown milder enthusiasm for the various solutions proposed.

For the results of question 10 we will follow the approach just used for question 9. All the general graphs (which include the “not used” responses) will be seen first, in order to get also an idea of which feature were used the most and the level of not-used across them. Then, in turn, we will see two sub-questions, one again including and one without the “not used” responses.

10. I found the following features of STEP to be useful
Online Chat / Discussion Forum

10. I found the following features of STEP to be useful
E-Petitions

10. I found the following features of STEP to be useful
Formal Consultation processes

10. I found the following features of STEP to be useful
Social Media Mining Tool

10. I found the following features of STEP to be useful
Language Translation

10. I found the following features of STEP to be useful
Ability to see Dialogues in other European countries

Figure 76 General graphs for question 10

Compared to question 9 on gamification, it is clearly visible that the number of “not used” responses is comparatively lower than before. The maximum of “not used” in question 10a amount to 10 responses, whereas in 9f we had a maximum of 24 “not aware” responses. Core STEP features thus have been used more widely than the gamification. To offer a better look at question 10 we focus here on the sub-questions associated with two core STEP components: e-petitions (10b) and formal consultation (10c). Indeed these are the core of the participatory policy making process as offered by the STEP platform.

We consider sub-question 10b with including the “not used” responses (graph seen before). The following are the pilot graphs. We see in relative terms the largest percentage of not-used in the Crete pilot at 18.5%, a pilot this that displays however also the strongest relative Positive response (at around 70%). Large Neutral responses are present in Valdemoro (following the pattern already observed, with milder enthusiasm) and this time also in Locride (at about 58%). This last result is perhaps the most surprising where the effectiveness of e-petitions for participatory making is not seen as playing that fundamental role which has for other pilots like Crete. The largest set of negative responses to the sub-question is clearly visible in the Hatay pilot where (once stripped of the not-used responses, n=3) the negative amount to 11.5% with 6 observations. Mollet del Vallés and Thessaloniki are reported for completeness and we can see in particular 1 not-used observation in the latter amounting to circa 10% of the total not-used.

Figure 77 Pilot graphs for question 10b

We consider now question 10c, this time stripped of the not-used responses and focusing on the four pilots with the most responses. The formal consultation feature clearly had significant effectiveness in the Crete pilot where we see 80% of Positive responses and also in Hatay with nearly 68% of Positives, although the Hatay pilot also has the largest Negative set (circa 12%). In Locride, positive responses are still the majority (circa 58%) however, clearly there was a much milder response with 39% of Neutral. Again the Valdemoro pilot shows the weakest Positive response rate (at about 35%) with striking differences if compared with the other pilots.

Figure 78 Pilot graphs for question 10c

Overall, from this analysis we can conclude that STEP has achieved a good level of effectiveness across the core features. Very strong Positive responses are seen across all the gamification aspects, although as already pointed out, there may need to be some work done to make the gamification aspects more visible, so that end-users can become more aware of it and how it functions in the overall context of participatory policy making. Core STEP features (associated with question 10) have also shown a good level of effectiveness although with far less “not used” responses than the gamification, but with slightly more neutral responses. We have unveiled some pilot dynamics associated with question 10. In question 10b we have seen a milder response in the Locride pilot, which is surprising if we consider the strong attitude that Young People in this pilot have shown toward the other questions of the questionnaire. Perhaps e-petitions have not yet delivered visible results in this pilot. On the other hand the Valdemoro pilot has kept showing milder attitudes towards the entire policy making process, as seen throughout the analysis.

5.3.5 O5c: Legal and Ethical Compliance

The following question has been used to measure the sub-objective O5c.

Objective	Questions Number	Questions Text
O5c	6h	The STEP Platform Gave me enough information regarding data protection issues

The target for this objective was a Yes over a Yes/No set of options. The following is the table with the results for this objective. Overall we have a positive figure, with above 60% of Strongly Agree and Agree responses and above 90% Non-negative, we have 11 negative responses in total (7%).

Table 83 O5c: Results against the target

Questions	Frequency (n=181) (SA+A)	Frequency (n=181) (SA+A+N)	% (SA+A)	% (SA+A+N)
6h	113	170	62	93
TARGET			Yes/No	

6. The STEP Platform (System Evaluation)
Gave me enough information regarding data protection issues

Figure 79 General graph for question 6h

What follows are the graphs for the pilots. There are again interesting differences to note and a pattern we seen in other objectives. Indeed the Valdemoro pilot presents the lowest number of Positive responses (less

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than 50%) and a relatively large chunk of Neutral responses (n=26) slightly below 50% of the total neutral responses. We also see that all the other pilots present Positive responses all above 50%, with Locride even without any Negative ones.

Figure 80 Pilot graphs for question 6h

5.4 Young People Questionnaire Summary

Overall, there can be reasonable satisfaction on the results of the Young People Questionnaire. In most questions, there is a good set of positive responses toward the participatory policy making as proposed through the STEP platform. Clearly Young People see the effectiveness of STEP and how the platform can support a participatory policy making process, as seen in the analysis of Objective O5b3. As we have seen a certain level of mistrust still exist going from Young People toward policy-making and this was clearly visible in relation to the analysis of questions associated with Objective O2b. While a platform like STEP can help reducing this trust gap, work needs to be conducted on this specific aspect independently of e-Participation tools, as part of Public Authorities activities. We have also seen that STEP can help Public Authority in getting a much clearer understanding of the opinion of Young People as seen in the discussion of objective O1c.

Several pilot dynamics have been unveiled by the analysis. In particular, the milder response of the Valdemoro pilot has been consistent throughout the questionnaire. In the Valdemoro pilot, there was initially a low number of participants, despite the fact that many people were reached through events, activities and workshops. Young People would be interested in using a new platform or app, but it should be well-known and be used by their peers. Overall, in this pilot there has been a low number of dialogues, with some dialogues appearing not entirely relevant to Young People. During the project life-time this pilot also has experienced a change of the Mayor also with some consequent impact on the pilot flow. Additionally only one pilot leader was working on the pilot, thence reducing the capacity to achieve better results. All these aspects very likely then justify the milder response received to the STEP questionnaire from Valdemoro. The Locride pilot has shown in most cases the largest Positive attitude toward STEP with many questions appearing without a single Negative response. However, we have seen that this attitude was much milder in relation to the usability of the platform. Qualitative details about the problems encountered by the Locride pilot with the usability can be seen in this deliverable where interviews are analysed. However, it would seem indeed that this pilot has not found the usability as straightforward as the other pilots and the questionnaire results and qualitative interviews cross-confirm this clearly. The Hatay pilot, only in relation to the question on Young People concerns voiced to policy makers, has shown a relative negative attitude. This specific pilot aspect may have much to do with local policy-making. Crete also has shown high level of positive responses with just occasionally milder attitudes. Only in relation to the impact of the platform on the local authority (question 5f) we have seen a very large set of Neutral responses, a sign that likely the participatory policy making has not yet delivered tangible results. From the analysis, much less can be said about the two other pilots - Mollet del Vallés and Thessaloniki - due to the relatively small number of responses received. On a final note, we think it is important to remember the results of question 15 asking whether Young People would recommend STEP to other Young People. Strong positive responses have been provided to this question (with Positives at 77%), showing overall a good satisfaction of Young People, to the point indeed in which they would recommend its use to others.

6 SWOT Analysis

In what follows we present a SWOT analysis, considering strengths and weaknesses (internal) as well as opportunities and threats (external) from four core aspects of STEP: the end-users, the business, the technology and the overall approach of STEP. This analysis has been performed individually by the WP Leader of Work Package 2, 3, 6 and by the Coordinator. The SWOT offers an at a glance view of the overall approach taken by STEP toward e-participation, highlighting relevant aspects as well as issues faced by the platform for the future.

Table 84 SWOT Analysis Table

AREA	STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES	OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
End-Users	STEP is seen as a trustworthy tool for e-participation by Young People and they are very keen to recommend its use to their peers. Also policy makers said they would recommend its use to their colleagues	Some aspects of usability need better fine tuning, especially for Young People, in order for STEP to reach its complete maturity as an e-participation platform.	STEP can help fill the trust gap between Young People and Policy makers in some areas, as STEP is seen as offering relevant information and helping Young People voice their concerns in the area of environmental issues.	A lack of trust between Young People and Policy Makers is particularly evident and has emerged in multiple occasions. Any e-participation effort is up against this challenge.
Business	STEP integrated and comprehensive suite of services offers an attractive engagement online platform that allows real-time interaction anywhere, in multiple languages and through any device. Its Business-to-Business-to-Consumer model supported by a Software-as-a-Service revenue stream offers an attractive price to penetrate the market of cost-efficiency driven public authorities.	STEP market penetration strategy highly depends on end-user adoption as even though public authorities find the commercial offering attractive, they won't invest if not enough users are using it. Hence, as users expect to have the same online experience that they have in popular social platforms, some usability aspects need better fine tuning.	Public authorities need scalable and cost-efficient tools to effectively engage citizens in political dialogues and to easily analyse their insights in order to become more citizen-centric in their decision-making process and operations.	Public authorities of large municipalities might have already invested in similar software and are mainly interested in StepSocialAnalytics. Public authorities of small municipalities have constrained budgets to guard and might be conscious to pay even a monthly fee for such service.
Technology	STEP has many off the shelf features based on a e-participation/dialogue management framework (e-petitions, questionnaires etc.). It has Android/iOS native app interfaces and supports social media mining, visualization and machine translation and text to speech capabilities.	Proprietary licensing model may prevent STEP to reach a large development base. This may create a weakness in the speed of development.	Municipalities that would like to start using STEP as their engagement platform can do easily. STEP is based on a SaaS approach and API based integrations approach, STEP is therefore easily extensible and not that hard to customize for municipalities.	Public administration users are not often that competent on technology usage and this hinders the usage of several provided features. We have experienced that features like chatting, round tables, timelines, maps, signatures, sms verification have not been used as expected by PA admins.
Overall Approach	STEP offers a comprehensive approach in the form of a tool, methodology, and engagement strategies,	For successful youth participation there has to be a true commitment of public authorities to open their procedures, and time is	At a time when there is a distrust of young people towards traditional forms of participation, STEP comes to offer a solution which is far	The successful implementation of the STEP approach relies on many factors which are beyond our control (such

	<p>which has been successfully demonstrated to support public authorities in engaging young people in implementing public participation procedures.</p>	<p>required to build trust. Therefore, the benefits of using the STEP approach cannot always be apparent in a short time period, which may lead to disappointment.</p>	<p>from the formalised approaches, and takes advantage of ICT technologies.</p>	<p>as political stability, trust, etc.)</p>
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7 Conclusion

The STEP deliverable 5.3 has presented the final evaluation results of the project. As part of the evaluation process we have conducted a number of qualitative interviews with relevant actors in the pilots (Public Officers, Policy Makers and Young People) as well as two questionnaires (with Young People and Public Officers/Policy Makers). We have also considered some data from the piloting activities and have seen the lessons learned from each individual pilot. Furthermore, a SWOT analysis has been presented covering relevant aspects of the platform. Overall the evaluation has shown that STEP has achieved good results and did well against the original targets, during piloting activities. However, it is also clear that the results across the pilots are different, with some successfully achieving good or excellent levels of e-Participation (Hatay, Crete and in particular Mollet del Vallés). Others have instead struggled to support the process of e-Participation and reach results (Valdemoro in particular). In any case, as these were piloting activities, the most relevant aspect is that several lessons have been learned around the mobilisation of Young People, about the topics of environmental participatory policy making, about the use of a new technology. The STEP platform through this experimenting has then achieved a good level of maturity and it can be seen as a reliable tool for e-Participation in the area of environmental issues, which can help Policy Makers opening up quickly and successfully participatory policy-making processes.

Overall interviews and questionnaire show a very good level of satisfaction among participants. Both Young People and Policy Officers interviewed have expressed their intent to use STEP again in the future and said they would recommend STEP to their respective peers. Clearly however, there also are some areas where improvements may still be necessary for the future, in order for STEP to reach a complete level of maturity. We have for example observed about the need to better “fine-tune” the usability of the platform and this was clear for example in the results of the Locride pilot. Another pilot (Hatay) experienced some issues with the speed of the platform. We have also seen that one of the pilots (Valdemoro) did not go necessarily very well and this has become quite visible in the analysis of the Young People questionnaire and consequently it has impacted on the perceived capacities of the platform to deliver e-Participation in environmental issues. We have also seen the problem of Trust of Young People toward policy makers, which has been consistent throughout the project, where clearly Young People do express a general level of mistrust both toward policy makers but also toward their motives and actions toward the enactment of participatory policy making. This is a gap which is difficult to fill and clearly goes beyond the goal of STEP. However STEP (like any other e-Participation platform) faces this as a clear external “threat”, which may impact the overall operational capacity of an e-Participation process conducted with the platform. In this regard however, we have also seen that the STEP platform is seen as a trustworthy tool for the conduction of participatory policy making around environmental issues and this offers good positive expectations on the capacity of the platform, to at least help achieve better trust relations between Young People and Policy Makers.

8 Appendices

Appendix A: Post Pilot Interview Questions

Introduction (Interviewer – please introduce yourself to the interviewee / ensure signed consent is obtained before proceeding. Participant should already have an information sheet).

Quick explanation of the Purpose of Interview / Focus Group and let the person know that their feedback is very valuable to us and to the process of developing an effective platform.

Young European Citizens Interview Questions:

- Demographic Questions: Age / City/ Municipality live in / occupation
Can you tell us how you became involved with the STEP eParticipation pilot trial.
 - How did you hear about it?
 - What made you want to get involved?
 - Have you been involved in a similar eParticipation activity before or is this the first time?
- Do you think that the opinions of young people are already adequately considered in your municipality?
 - Do you think that STEP will help to improve this issue?
- Was the process of (add in correct process, eg consultation) fully explained to you at the start?
- Do you think the timing of the process was adequate? (did you have enough time to participate fully / did you feel rushed?)
- What did you think of the STEP platform in general? Then specifically what did you think of..
 - Attractiveness?
 - Usability?
 - Interest – ie content.?
- For the specific eParticipation process you took part in (call for ideas / consultation process / e-Petitions / Round Table) what would you say was the best thing about taking part?
 - And the worst thing?
- In your opinion how could it have been made better?
- Did you use the social media mining tool? If yes.....
 - Did you find it useful
 - How regularly did you use it
 - What was the best thing about the tool
 - And the worst thing?
 - Any suggestions for improvement.
- Do you think you are more or less likely to participate in a similar eParticipation activity after taking part in the STEP pilot study? Reason?
- What level of interaction did you achieve on the platform? (did you speak to other YEC's, discuss anything with people from a different city? etc.)
- Did you share any information with others on the platform? If yes what was it and how did you share? ie on the platform / via other social media sites?)
- Did you feel that the information provided was trustworthy? Probe a little more here if necessary. political agenda etc.
- Do you think that the platform could help to develop a 'sense of community' for your local municipality?

- Do you think that this would help to increase young people's level of engagement?
- Anything else that you would like to comment on or share with us about your experience?

Thank Participant for taking part and ask if they would like to be informed on future developments regarding the project.

Public Officer Interview Questions:

- Demographic Questions: Age / City/ Municipality live in / occupation
- Prior to the STEP project do you think that the opinions of young people were adequately considered in your municipality?
 - Do you think that STEP will help to improve this issue?
- Which process did you set up / participate in?
- For this process (eg call for ideas) do you think the timing was adequate? (ie enough to enable you to use the platform and to give young people enough time to participate fully ?)
- What did you think of the STEP platform in general, was the experience positive / negative or a mixture of both ? Then specifically what did you think of..
 - Attractiveness?
 - Usability?
 - Interest – ie content?.
- Were you in charge of setting up a specific eParticipation process? If Yes..
 - How did you find the admin features?
 - Did you watch the training videos beforehand?
 - Did you have to seek assistance at any point?
 - Was the help provided useful / enough for you to achieve your goals
- For the specific eParticipation process you took part in (call for ideas / consultation process / e-Petitions / Round Table) what would you say was the best thing about taking part?
 - And the worst thing?
- In your opinion how could it have been made better?
- Did you use the social media mining tool? If yes.....
 - Did you find it useful?
 - How regularly did you use it?
 - What was the best thing about the tool?
 - And the worst thing?
 - Any suggestions for improvement.
- Compared to the old way of engaging with young people on environmental matters, Do you think that using the STEP platform is a better way? Reason?
- What level of interaction with young people did you achieve on the platform? (did you discuss anything other people
- Do you think that the platform could help to develop a 'sense of community' for your local municipality?
 - Do you think that this would help to increase young people's level of engagement?
- Do you think that the platform has helped to promote trust between young people and policy makers / public officers?
- Anything else that you would like to comment on or share with us about your experience with STEP?

Thank Participant for taking part.

Appendix B

Issue Reporting via the STEP Platform

The table below summarises the issues reported via the Dialogue set up to capture problems. This mechanism was a quick and easy way for non-technical members of the project to be able to report issues using the familiar STEP dialogue posting mechanism. Technical members could then add any issues to their developer issue tracking system.

STEP Functionality	Issues Reported via STEP platform (Issue Reporting Dialogue)	Actions
Set Up / Profiles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Difficulty deleting profiles 	Ensure profiles can be deleted – now implemented for next release
Social Media Monitoring Tool	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Difficulty Accessing SMMT Keyword Entry Issues Start Search button issue Speed issues 	Improve the functionality of the SMMT to address the issues identified (still to improve this)
Dialogues Multimedia option	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Young People want to post multimedia in response to other posts – currently only text reply 	Allow multimedia uploads in response to posts (not just new posts)
Reaching Young People	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Difficulty inviting YP to dialogue No mechanism for letting YP know when a new dialogue is posted 	Push notification is now implemented for inviting YP and for informing them of new dialogues
Sharing Social Media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Irrelevant images associated with post 	Correct – provide clearer images
Europe-Wide Timeline	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Usability issue with Post-it-Notes Issue with 'Engage in other Surveys' link 	Amended appropriately
PO saving Dialogue Data to Docs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inability to download & save the dialogue posts as a document 	Issue resolved
Translation Issues	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inability to display the calendar tool in the correct language (Italian) 	Issue resolved

Table 85 Issues reported via the issue reporting dialogue (last two issues are new after D5.2)

Figure 81 Issue reporting dialogue for STEP Pilots

Appendix C

Evaluation Questionnaire for each of the 7 pilots.

STEP Pilot Partners Evaluation

Thank you for agreeing to take part in this evaluation survey for STEP e-participation platform. With this survey we aim to collect further details and reflections regarding the applicability of this e-participation tool to your local context and the methods for audience engagement. Be assured that all answers you provide will be kept in confidentiality.

* Απαιτείται

Profile Information

1. Name *

2. Entity (Municipality, Regional Authority, other) *

3. City *

4. Job title / Department title *

5. Duration in your current position (months) *

Local Context

6. As a Municipal/Regional Authority, do you have an established Department for Citizen Engagement? *

Να επισημαίνεται μόνο μία έλλειψη.

Yes

No

7. Evaluate the level of citizen participation in your local decision making process? *

Να επισημαίνεται μόνο μία έλλειψη.

1 2 3 4 5

very low very high

8. If rated level 3,4 or 5 in the previous question, which citizen participation tools do you use? *

Επιλέξτε όλα όσα ισχύουν.

- community meetings
- on street questionnaires
- participatory budget platform
- e-participation platform
- N/A
- Άλλο: _____

9. How familiar are digital tools to your citizens? *

Να επισημαίνεται μόνο μία έλλειψη.

	1	2	3	4	5	
very little	<input type="radio"/>	very much				

10. Please briefly explain your previous answer.

11. As a Municipal/Regional Authority, do you have an established Youth Council or an elected Youth Mayor? *

Να επισημαίνεται μόνο μία έλλειψη.

- Yes
- No

12. Evaluate the level of youth participation in your local decision making process? *

Να επισημαίνεται μόνο μία έλλειψη.

	1	2	3	4	5	
very little	<input type="radio"/>	very much				

13. Please briefly explain your previous answer.

Platform Administration

14. Who was the administrator of the STEP platform? (Department, job title) *

15. Can you briefly describe the role/ responsibilities of this job position or Department? *

16. Who was responsible to create the content of the STEP dialogues? (Department, job title) *

17. Was the same person responsible to approve the content of the STEP dialogue? *

Να επισημαίνεται μόνο μία έλλειψη.

Yes

No

18. If no, who was responsible for approving the content? *

Audience Engagement

19. Briefly describe your audience engagement strategy. What methods did you use to engage youth audience? *

Επιλέξτε όλα όσα ισχύουν.

hardcopy flyers, posters etc.

social media campaigns

presentations in relevant events

creating preliminary short term STEP dialogues before introducing the main themes

Άλλο: _____

20. Did you collaborate with any local educational or youth institutions (schools, universities, NGO's)? If yes, please list them below and describe briefly to what extent did you collaborate with them. (i.e. co-hosting an awareness event, co-designing a STEP dialogue etc.) *

21. Did you use STEP as a stand alone pilot campaign or did you integrate it to an ongoing campaign? *

22. Did you edit the STEP dialogue text to be more attractive to youth or did you choose to keep the formal scientific language in order to describe the environmental issue? Explain your answer. *

STEP Platform Results

23. How did you present or plan to present the outcomes of the STEP dialogues to the public? *

Επιλέξτε όλα όσα ισχύουν.

- create a report for the Municipal/ Regional Authority
- visualize the results and share on social media
- visualize the results and publish in local press
- haven't decided yet

24. Have you presented/ introduced the STEP platform internally to your entity? (for example to other relevant City/Regional Departments such as Dept. of Education, Dept. of Environment, Dept. of Infrastructure etc.) *

Να επισημαίνεται μόνο μία έλλειψη.

- Yes
- No

25. If yes, please list them below *

26. Did you have political support/commitment for the content of your STEP dialogues ? *

Να επισημαίνεται μόνο μία έλλειψη.

Yes

No

27. If yes, please briefly describe the case.

28. Has your Municipal/Regional administration institutionalized any of the STEP results by creating new policies or integrating the results to existing policies or action plans? *

Να επισημαίνεται μόνο μία έλλειψη.

Yes

No

29. If yes, please briefly describe the case.

Thank you for your time!

Appendix D

Eu pilot dialogue reports

STEP dialogue on the 17 Sustainable Development Goals

Youth and their role in the achievement of the goals

Europe's future depends on its youth. Promoting youth participation is fundamental in the EU policy. Especially for environmental issues, the participation of young people in decision making is extremely important, as decisions taken now on matters such as climate change, the depletion of resources, and the loss of biodiversity will have long-term consequences that will affect the future generations. Young people will have to live longer with the consequences of current decisions, and have special concerns and responsibilities in relation to the environment. [1]

In this context, the STEP project aims to open up information and participative decision-making processes on environmental issues within a region or municipality, or at a wider European level. The STEP project (step.green platform) specifically targets young European citizens to increase their participation in decision-making procedures, policy process, collaborating with others, and reaching consensus to bring about positive and effective

responses to environmental related issues.[2] This is done through e-participation tools such as dialogues, roundtables, calls for e-petitions or public consultations etc.

One dialogue conducted at the European level ('STEP EU pilot' page) focused on the topic of UN's Sustainable Development Goals, which define the main topics and priorities that the world should focus on until 2030. They were developed around three main "pillars of development": the economic pillar, the social pillar and the environmental pillar. [3]

What is the current role of young people in the SDGs

Events and articles have been showing that, even if the goals are not making any reference to youth, young people play a very important part in making the SDGs reach their targets. Some of the goals could be involving them more – such as the strive for quality education, good health and well-being, reduced inequalities, or decent work and economic work.

In the informal summary of the ECOSOC Youth Forum, which took place in January 2017, it is mentioned that “all governments perform better when they take their youth population’s concerns seriously; embracing new media, technology and scientific breakthroughs. Young people, therefore, need to be empowered as innovators in the development process, not just beneficiaries or consumers.”

In the same time, by analyzing the data from Europe and North America, it showed that “young peo-

ple were very aware of issues related to sustainable development, but did not specifically know about the SDGs. Young people were not accessing their rights, including political rights, and the social model is not protecting young people anymore. Too many young people lived in poverty with precarious employment, low-paid jobs and no job security; especially Roma, asylum seekers, and other vulnerable groups are most affected.” [4]

There is a great potential for youth to be the beneficiary, as well as a driving force in reaching the SDGs targets. For this reason, we conducted the online dialogue on the STEP platform (step.green) which asked young people to have a look at the 17 SDGs and choose the 5 most important in their opinion.

Next we are presenting the results of the dialogue.

Dialogue results and analysis

The online dialogue was open on the STEP platform between August 1st and August 31st 2017 and it involved 182 participants. A total of 792 'responses' were given to the 17 SDGs. The goal with the highest number of votes was Goal 4, "Quality education"

(90), followed by Goal 6, "Clean water and sanitation" (84) and Goal 13, "Climate Action" (74). The last goals in young people's prioritization were "Industry, innovation and infrastructure" (20), "Life on land" (12) and "Life below water" (10):

	Quality education	90
	Clean water and sanitation	84
	Climate action	74
	Zero hunger	74
	Good health and well-being	68
	Peace, justice and strong institutions	56
	Responsible consumption and production	53
	No poverty	44
	Affordable and clean energy	41
	Gender equality	41
	Reduced inequalities	37
	Decent work and economic growth	33
	Sustainable cities and communities	32
	Partnership for the goals	23
	Industry, innovation and infrastructure	20
	Life on land	12
	Life below water	10
TOTAL		792

Based on our assumptions, we believe that participants opted mostly for the Goals 4, 6 and 13 because, possibly, they can relate more easily to topics such as education, water and climate change. Education can be considered something that would directly impact and 'speak' particularly to young people. From discussions of the network Youth and Environment Europe (YEE) with young people who participated in the dialogue at the NGO Island during Sziget festival on 9-15 August 2017, we gathered that educa-

tion should be at the base of everything and the lack of education can impact negatively other developments in the political, economic, social or environmental fields.

Furthermore, climate change is a topic that is becoming more and more present among young people. It is also a very significant environmental topic addressed by YEE, the partner organisation who disseminated the dialogue among its members. As many of the respondents are connected with the

YEE network, they are already aware of the topic and, some of them are aware of its increasing importance nowadays.

We also analyzed the data based on the age range of participants, by creating four groups of age: 16-20; 21-24; 25-29; 30+. The results were as following:

What is your age group?	16-20	21-24	25-29	30+
Quality education	19%	29%	22%	30%
Clean water and sanitation	14%	22%	26%	38%
Climate action	25%	19%	25%	32%
Zero hunger	22%	20%	23%	35%
Good health and well-being	16%	25%	22%	36%
Peace, justice and strong institutions	26%	17%	21%	36%
Responsible consumption and production	13%	38%	26%	23%
No poverty	19%	14%	19%	47%
Affordable and clean energy	24%	21%	7%	48%
Gender equality	20%	26%	20%	34%
Reduced inequalities	17%	24%	21%	38%
Decent work and economic growth	18%	25%	21%	36%
Sustainable cities and communities	10%	20%	10%	60%
Partnership for the goals	26%	26%	16%	32%
Industry, innovation and infrastructure	0%	23%	15%	62%
Life on land	0%	22%	22%	56%
Life below water	0%	43%	29%	29%

	16-20
Climate action	12%
Quality education	12%
Zero hunger	11%
Peace, justice and strong institutions	10%
Clean water and sanitation	8%
Good health and well-being	8%
Affordable and clean energy	6%
Gender equality	6%
No poverty	6%
Decent work and economic growth	4%
Partnership for the goals	4%
Reduced inequalities	4%
Responsible consumption and production	4%
Sustainable cities and communities	3%
Industry, innovation and infrastructure	0%
Life below water	0%
Life on land	0%

		21-24
	Quality education	14%
	Responsible consumption and production	10%
	Clean water and sanitation	10%
	Good health and well-being	10%
	Zero hunger	8%
	Climate action	7%
	Gender equality	6%
	Peace, justice and strong institutions	5%
	Reduced inequalities	5%
	Decent work and economic growth	5%
	Affordable and clean energy	4%
	Sustainable cities and communities	4%
	No poverty	3%
	Partnership for the goals	3%
	Industry, innovation and infrastructure	2%
	Life below water	2%
	Life on land	1%

		25-29
	Clean water and sanitation	13%
	Quality education	12%
	Climate action	11%
	Zero hunger	11%
	Good health and well-being	9%
	Responsible consumption and production	8%
	Peace, justice and strong institutions	7%
	No poverty	5%
	Gender equality	5%
	Reduced inequalities	5%
	Decent work and economic growth	5%
	Sustainable cities and communities	2%
	Partnership for the goals	2%
	Affordable and clean energy	2%
	Industry, innovation and infrastructure	2%
	Life on land	2%
	Life below water	2%

		30+
	Clean water and sanitation	11%
	Quality education	9%
	Zero hunger	9%
	Good health and well-being	9%
	Climate action	8%
	Sustainable cities and communities	8%
	No poverty	7%
	Peace, justice and strong institutions	6%
	Affordable and clean energy	6%
	Gender equality	5%
	Reduced inequalities	5%
	Decent work and economic growth	4%
	Responsible consumption and production	4%
	Industry, innovation and infrastructure	3%
	Partnership for the goals	3%
	Life on land	2%
	Life below water	1%

Based on our assumptions, the highest percentage of people aged 16-20 chose “Climate action” among their 5 options because climate change trending topic among younger people interested in environmental protection and because it is a topic widely promoted within the youth network of YEE. People aged 21-24 chose “Quality education” the most among their 5 options because, we believe, they are those who might have already spent many years in education and they have a clearer view about what

is important/what should be improved in education systems. Furthermore, most people aged over 25 chose “Clean water and sanitation” among their 5 options. We believe that this could be based on the fact that they, even if maybe it is not an issue in their immediate reality, are aware of it and could still relate to its importance, globally speaking, and that they consider it as a significant aim to fulfil for as many communities and municipalities as possible.

.....

Further suggestions and recommendations

In our opinion, young people are interested to share their opinions regarding the SDGs; however, some of them were not familiar with the 17 SDGs per se, but rather with the topics on which the goals are focusing. All 17 goals were mentioned in the participants’, to a bigger or smaller extent (as seen in the tables above). In this context, we believe that young

people could and should have an important role in addressing the completion of the SDGs until 2030.

Below are few recommendations on how this can further take place:

- inform young people or provide informational material about the SDGs in educational spaces, youth centres etc.

- outline the ways in which youth is directly impacted by each of the goals
- encourage youth to share their opinions regarding the goals, progress done towards completion (e.g. via e-participation tools, discussions within youth organisations etc.)
- encourage youth to spread the knowledge further (help them act as multipliers)
- organise events/workshops/work groups for young people that will enable them to work together to generate ideas and solutions for a better achievement of the SDGs.

[1] <http://step4youth.eu/>

[2] STEP deliverables - D2.4 Report on coproduction of services (September 2017)

[3] <http://www.mn.undp.org/content/mongolia/en/home/presscenter/speeches/2017/02/22/role-of-youth-in-making-the-sustainable-development-goals-a-reality-in-mongolia.html>

The 17 Sustainable Development Goals can be consulted here: <http://www.un.org/sustainabledevelopment/sustainable-development-goals/>

[4] <https://www.un.org/ecosoc/sites/www.un.org.ecosoc/files/files/en/2017doc/2017-youth-forum-summary.pdf>

Learn more about STEP

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STEP dialogue on Climate Change

Youth and their role in tackling Climate Change

Today's youth generation are the first to feel the impacts of climate change but also the ones that can team up and demand change.

Climate change is now affecting every country on every continent. It is affecting lives, costing people, disrupting national economies, affecting communities and countries dearly today and even more tomorrow.

In this context, the STEP project aims to open up information and participative decision-making processes on environmental issues within a region or municipality, or at a wider European level. The STEP project (Step.Green platform) specifically targets

young European citizens to increase their participation in decision-making procedures, policy process, collaborating with others, and reaching consensus to bring about positive and effective responses to environmental related issues. This is done through e-participation tools such as dialogues, roundtables, calls for e-petitions or public consultations etc.

One of the dialogues conducted at the European level ('STEP EU pilot' page) focused on "Climate Change" and its main purpose was to obtain information about youths' perception of climate change and how they suggest that it can be tackled.

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Dialogue results and analysis

The “Tackling Climate Change” dialogue was open on the STEP platform from September 1st to October 20th, 2017 and it involved 108 participants. A significant percentage of the respondents (95%) declared that they do worry about climate change (from a little to a great deal), with the majority responding that they worry a great deal (57%).

92% of the respondents consider that climate change is directly related or a result of Human activities (Question 2 – Q2). If we analyse those two questions (Q1 & Q2) and the respective responses deeper, we identify a strong correlation among the level of concern and the “main cause of climate change”. A strong correlation between High levels of concern and Human factor as main cause of Climate Change is witnessed alongside lower concern and Natural causes as main cause of climate change (see Cross-Ref. 1 and Cross Ref. 2 diagrams below).

It shall also be noted that responses are relatively aligned and distributed, even within different age groups; with respondents age group (from 25 to 29) being the more environmentally concerned and aware.

In their majority (89%, Question 3 – Q3), the respondents consider that we already live and feel the results of Climate Change (it's already happening) and that Climate Change directly affects their everyday life (87%, Question 4 – Q4).

95% Of the respondents consider that we can take actions to mitigate the effects of Climate Change, with a 58% considering that our action will only slow down the effects and an 37%, being more optimistic, considering that we can reverse the effects of Climate change (Question 5 – Q5).

Respondents also agree that “addressing Climate Change effects” cannot be a sole personal or individual task, on the contrary it shall be the result of a strategic plan (Question 6 – Q6), communicated and implemented by National Governments (45%), followed by International organisations (29%) and assisted by individual actions (22%).

To support those “mitigation actions” information and communication is essential, and respondents seem to require for “expert’s knowledge”; highlighting that they would trust information coming from Scientists and Environmental Organizations and showcasing their misbelief towards information coming from the media and the National governments (Question 7 – Q7).

Finally, more than half of the respondents (55%) do take regularly action(s) that they consider would cumulatively assist towards mitigating the effects of climate change (Question 8 – Q8).

Based on the findings above, we could perform a few assumptions with regards to Youths perception and suggestions to tackle Climate Change. They showcase a high level of awareness and they consider that humans and human actions are responsible for the current Climate Change effects. They ask from national governments, scientist and environmental organisations to step up and lead an effective plan to slow down the Climate Change effects. They do ask for Scientists and Env. ironmental Organizations to communicate new research findings, and inform the public.

Further suggestions and recommendations

Based on the questionnaire analysis it can be concluded that, young people are interested to share their opinions regarding Climate Change; and they wish and can have a significant role in the planning and development of actions and measures in the “global” attempt to mitigate Climate Change

effects. The “level of readiness” and awareness of youths with regards to tackling climate change, was evident to the STEP team even from the first EU-wide dialogue, on the topic of 17 SDG's, where “Climate Change” was placed/selected high in the prioritisation list.

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